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Asteroseismic probing of the internal structure of main-sequence stars

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Dissertation présentée en
vue de l'obtention du grade
de Docteur en Sciences

Liège 2007

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Ringraziamenti

Innanzitutto ringrazio Josefina per questi quattro anni di lavoro insieme, per i consigli, lo spirito critico, i continui suggerimenti e scambi d'idee.

Je remercie Arlette pour son aide, sa compétence, pour son authentique passion pour la science, ainsi que pour l'enthousiasme manifesté à chaque nouvelle idée. Merci Richard et Anne, pour vos conseils pendant la thèse et pour m'avoir accueilli si aimablement dans le group.

Je remercie également Marc-Antoine pour sa disponibilité et sa compétence. Merci Patrick pour ton apport "rotationnel" ainsi que pour les nombreuses discussions. Un grand merci pour le soutien et l'encouragement à Nicolas, qui bien représente la chaleur et la gentillesse des gens de Liège. Merci à Pierre-Olivier, à Sylvie et aux collègues du +1, pour avoir créé un environnement de travail très agréable. Thank you Conny for pushing a "solar-type" person to get also interested in hotter stars!

I thank all the members of the jury for the time spent reading this thesis, in particular Ian Roxburgh for his one-day trip from London.

Mille e mille grazie ai miei genitori, a mia sorella Anna, ad Anzio e a Sara, per avermi sempre sostenuto e spinto in ogni scelta.

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1

Introduction and overview of the thesis

1.1 Introduction

Stars represent the fundamental units of the observed universe, therefore understanding stellar structure and evolution plays a privileged role in astrophysics. Classical observations, however, provide information which is mainly confined to the superficial layers of stars and give no direct knowledge about their interior. The lack of information on stellar interiors is well expressed by a famous quote from the opening paragraph of Sir Arthur Eddington's book *The internal constitution of stars* (Eddington, 1926):

At first sight it would seem that the deep interior of the Sun and stars is less accessible to scientific investigation than any other region of the universe. Our telescopes may probe farther and farther into the depths of space; but how can we ever obtain certain knowledge of that which is hidden behind substantial barriers? What appliance can pierce through the outer layers of a star and test the conditions within?

At that time Eddington considered that the only scientific mean to bore those *substantial barriers* and to investigate stellar interiors was an *analytical boring device*, i.e. theory (Eddington, 1920).

However, to be considered a reliable and trustworthy description of stars, a theory must pass observational tests. In fact Eddington himself, in a later book, *Stars and atoms* (Eddington, 1927), already indicated a *material appliance* that could provide theoretical models with observational tests:

Ordinary stars must be viewed respectfully like objects in glass cases in museums; our fingers are itching to pinch them and test their resilience. Pulsating stars are like those fascinating models in the Science Museum provided with a button which can be pressed to set the machinery in motion. To be able to see the machinery of a star throbbing with activity is most instructive for the development of our knowledge.

Eighty years ago stellar pulsations were already indicated as a unique tool to test our understanding of stars! The goal of the observation and the study of stellar pulsation modes (asteroseismology) is indeed to disclose the information carried by the frequencies of oscillation. Each mode of oscillation sounds differently the inner regions of the star and represents then a unique tool to probe stellar interiors.

There are several beautiful examples on how the study of resonant oscillation modes gives us information otherwise inaccessible to any other probe (see e.g. the general introduction to asteroseismology by Kurtz, 2006). In geophysics, for instance, the study of seismic waves allows to infer the internal structure of the earth. Asteroseismology has a similar objective: to allow us to “see” inside stars and learn about their internal structure.

In the case of the Sun, a detailed picture of its internal structure was obtained thanks to helioseismology, the study of solar global oscillations. Since the first detection of the five-minute oscillations in the Sun by Leighton et al. (1962), and their interpretation as global acoustic oscillation modes (Ulrich, 1970; Leibacher & Stein, 1970), helioseismology led to several major scientific results (see e.g. Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2002, for an exhaustive review). Helioseismology gave us access to the properties of the internal regions of the Sun, namely the sound-speed and density profile and the internal rotation rate. One of the most successful results was the precise determination of the depth of the solar convective envelope ($d_{cz} = 0.287 \pm 0.003 R_{\odot}$, Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1991) which allowed to show that the inclusion of helium settling in the theoretical models was needed to significantly reduce the sound speed differences between the Sun and the models (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1993). This provided indeed a strong evidence of the importance of diffusion in stellar interiors.

Following the success of helioseismology, there have been major efforts to detect in other stars multiperiodic variations of luminosity/radial velocity that can be interpreted as global oscillation modes. In the last few years, in particular, large observational campaigns from ground (see Handler, 2006, for a recent review) as well as space-based observations such as MOST (Matthews, 1998) and WIRE (Buzasi, 2003) allowed to detect number of radial and non-radial oscillation frequencies in a large variety of stars along the Hertzsprung-Russel diagram. Moreover, the realisation of stabilized spectrographs to search for extra-solar planets allowed to reach a sufficient accuracy to detect small amplitude pulsations in solar-like stars (see e.g. the review by Bedding & Kjeldsen, 2007).

In the very near future, observational asteroseismology will take an even larger step forward: the long and uninterrupted photometric observations from space that are currently being gathered by CoRoT (Baglin et al., 2006) will allow to determine oscillation frequencies with unprecedented precision. A further advance in the observation of oscillations will result from the asteroseismic programme of the forthcoming Kepler space-mission (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 2007) and from ground- and space-based asteroseismology projects such as SIAMOIS (Mosser & The Siamois Team, 2007), SONG (Grundahl et al., 2006) and PLATO¹ (Roxburgh et al., 2007).

While recent advances in the observational side of asteroseismology will soon allow the determination of precise oscillation frequencies in different stars, we have to face a new challenge: can we infer the internal structure of other stars with the same level of detail as we know the Sun? Do we expect to get the same information on their internal structure as in the solar case? While the answer is negative in general, this does not imply that the scientific achievements we expect to get from seismology of other stars will necessarily be minor compared to those

¹http://www.lesia.obspm.fr/~catala/plato_web.html

of helioseismology. There are of course limiting factors for asteroseismology that should not be overlooked. Asteroseismology has, however, two main prerogatives:

- *the variety of pulsating stars*, which means the opportunity to test our models under physical conditions that can be significantly different than in the Sun,
- *the diversity of the oscillation modes excited in pulsating stars along the HR diagram*. In addition to high-order pressure modes observed in solar-like stars, asteroseismology will benefit from the information provided by other types of pulsations that probe different regions of the star. In the case of main-sequence pulsators, for instance, low-order pressure modes are detected in δ Scuti and β Cephei stars. Moreover, the detection of gravity modes and modes of mixed pressure-gravity character provides the exciting possibility to probe in detail the core structure of stars. These modes are observed in several classes of pulsators on or near the main sequence, in particular mixed modes are expected to appear in the spectrum of solar-like oscillations in subgiant stars, whereas low-order g modes are detected in δ Scuti and β Cephei stars. Finally, the variability observed in γ Doradus and Slowly Pulsating B stars is attributed to high-order gravity modes.

1.1.1 The goals of asteroseismology

The information that can be gathered from the oscillation frequencies strongly depends on the number of available observational constraints, on the precision of asteroseismic data and on the structure of the star itself (and thus on its seismic properties). For simplification, we can however regroup the potential achievements of seismology in two broad categories:

- Seismology helps determining with precision *global parameters of stars* (e.g. age, radius, mass) by adding strong constraints to the available observational data (such as luminosity, effective temperature and chemical composition). Binary stars are evidently the most favorable cases since the orbital parameters increase furthermore the number of observational constraints. A precise determination of global parameters for a large number of stars will give us a more detailed picture of the evolution of stars and stellar populations, and thus improve our knowledge of the chemical evolution of the galaxy.

A further interesting application, in the case of solar-like oscillations, is the combined study of exoplanets and their parent stars (see e.g the review by Charbonneau et al., 2007). The observation of the so-called large frequency separation in the parent star allows to put tight constraints on its radius and

thus on the radius of the planet detected by a photometric transit. Similarly, an estimate of the mass of the star allows to better constrain the orbital parameters of the planet and its mass (see e.g. Stello et al., 2007).

- If adding precision to the determination of global parameters is certainly an interesting application, we have to keep in mind that the determination of parameters relies on the stellar models we use to compute oscillation frequencies. Rather than assuming models right and deriving parameters, asteroseismology can lead to major scientific achievements by supplying observational evidence to prove our models wrong and/or inaccurate. This brings to the second, ambitious objective of asteroseismology: to *use stars as laboratories* to test physical inputs of the models. This, on the one hand, would add accuracy and not only precision to the determination of global parameters and, on the other hand, it would allow a deeper knowledge of physics in the conditions reached in the stellar interiors.

Which are the ways to proceed in order to reach these ambitious objectives? Let us have a closer view on the strategies that can be adopted to infer properties of stars from the observation of their pulsation modes.

1.2 Strategies for asteroseismic inferences

The link between the observation of oscillation frequencies in stars and the final goal of asteroseismology, which is to learn about stellar interiors, is not straightforward. We here describe some of the strategies adopted by asteroseismologists to process this information: this is by no means intended to be a comprehensive review of all the approaches, we rather try to highlight the main scientific questions that motivated this thesis.

1.2.1 Inferences from excitation

Why does a star pulsate? Which are the physical mechanisms responsible for the excitation of the observed oscillation modes? Answering these questions allows us to test the physical properties of the region that contributes the most to the excitation (or damping) of the modes. If we consider different classes of pulsating stars along the main sequence, we find a variety of excitation mechanisms that represent a source of information on distinct physical assumptions we include in our models.

For instance, the amplitudes, lifetimes and the frequency domain of the observed stochastically excited *solar-like oscillations* depend on the physical properties of the near-surface convective layers (see e.g. Samadi et al., 2007; Houdek, 2007; Carrier et al., 2007).

The role of convection in the driving of oscillation modes is also crucial in the case of γ Dor stars in which the instability of high-order g modes is attributed to the “convective blocking” (Guzik et al., 2000; Warner et al., 2003; Dupret et al., 2004). In these stars the transition region of oscillation modes of the observed periods is located near the bottom of the convective envelope (CE). The radiative luminosity has a sudden drop at the base of the CE and, at the hot phase of the pulsation cycle, energy cannot be transported by radiation in the convective zone. As the convective timescale at the bottom of the CE is longer than the periods of oscillation, the convective flux cannot adapt immediately to the changes due to oscillations: the energy is periodically blocked and transformed in mechanical work, providing a source of excitation for the oscillations. For this mechanism to be effective in these stars, and to excite the observed range of frequencies, the base of the convective envelope in the models needs to be located in a well defined temperature range ($T_{\text{bce}} \sim 2\text{--}4.8 \times 10^5$ K, see Guzik et al. 2000). This represents a valuable constraint to current stellar models since the depth of the convective zone is sensitive to different theoretical prescription of convective transport and to other physical processes such as microscopic diffusion (see Montalbán et al., 2007a).

As a further example we shall consider δ Scuti stars, where the instability of low-order p and g modes is explained via the κ - γ mechanism acting in the HeII ionization region. While the location of the theoretical blue edge of the instability strip is mainly dependent on the helium abundance (see e.g. Pamyatnykh, 2000), in stars near the red edge, convection plays an important role in the stabilisation of pulsation modes. In order to reproduce the observed location of the cool border of the instability strip it is necessary to introduce in the models a treatment of the interaction between convection and pulsation (Houdek, 2000; Xiong & Deng, 2001; Dupret et al., 2004).

Not all the excitation mechanisms in main-sequence stars are sensitive to the treatment of convection (and to its uncertainties). This is the case for pulsating B stars. The driving of oscillation modes in β Cephei and *Slowly Pulsating B* stars is due to the κ mechanism acting in the so-called “metal opacity bump” (see Sec. 3.7). We should nonetheless recall that the envelope of these stars is not entirely radiative: thin convective zones appear in the helium ionization regions and in the metal opacity bump layers in models of $M \gtrsim 10 M_{\odot}$. However, in such near-surface regions, convection transports only a negligible fraction of the luminosity and does not affect the excitation and damping of modes. This makes the comparison between observed and theoretically predicted instability domains for main-sequence B stars a precious opportunity to probe stellar opacity. In this context, recent observational studies have shown that current models fail to reproduce the instability of the observed modes in some of the best studied β Cep stars as well as the pulsation of B-type stars in low-metallicity environments (Ausloos et al., 2004; Pamyatnykh et al., 2004; Handler et al., 2006; Kołaczkowski

et al., 2006). While an increase of the opacity in stellar models near the “metal opacity bump” is likely to be the solution to this discrepancy, the physical reason why standard models underestimate opacity in the driving region is still a matter of debate. For instance, Pamyatnykh et al. (2004) suggested as a possible solution a local increase, induced by radiative levitation, of Fe-group elements in the driving region of the modes. We think that a more detailed study on the uncertainties in the opacity used in standard stellar models is needed to try to solve this challenging discrepancy. This is the reason why in Chap. 4 we analyze how the current uncertainties in the adopted metal mixture and in opacity computations (see Sec. 2.3.3) affect the theoretical instability domains of main-sequence B stars.

1.2.2 Inferences on stellar cores through gravity modes

Besides understanding the mechanisms that excite pulsations, the ultimate goal of asteroseismology is to make use of the frequencies of global oscillation modes to infer properties of the internal structure of stars. It was indeed the success of helioseismology in constraining properties of the solar structure through the study of global oscillation modes, that triggered the development of asteroseismology. One of the main factors that contributed to the growth of helioseismology was certainly a deep theoretical understanding of the properties of high order pressure modes. This led to an effective exploitation of the information carried by the observed frequencies through the development of analysis tools adapted to the observed oscillation modes (see e.g. the review by Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2002).

In the case of solar-like oscillations in other stars, analysis tools used in the interpretation of the pulsation spectra are in turn suggested by the profound theoretical knowledge of the properties of solar global oscillations. For example, in addition to the basic asymptotic large and small frequency spacings (Sec. 3.6.2), local information on abrupt changes in the stellar structure (on scales smaller or of the same order as the wavelength of the modes), can be gathered from periodic deviations from the simple frequency spectrum predicted by the asymptotic approximation. These signatures bear information on the location of the *boundary of the convective envelope* (see e.g. Monteiro et al., 2000; Ballot et al., 2004) and on the *envelope helium abundance* (see e.g. Monteiro & Thompson, 1998; Perez Hernandez & Christensen-Dalsgaard, 1998; Miglio et al., 2003; Basu et al., 2004; Verner et al., 2006; Houdek & Gough, 2007). Moreover, inversion procedures to reconstruct the *internal rotation profile* (e.g. Lochard et al., 2005) as well as the *core-structure* of solar-type stars (see e.g. Roxburgh & Vorontsov, 2002a,b; Basu et al., 2002; Roxburgh & Vorontsov, 2003a) were also adapted from helioseismology, and promise to provide detailed information on stellar interiors once precise frequencies of solar-like oscillations will be available.

Contrarily to case of high-order p modes, the properties of gravity modes in

main-sequence stars have been less extensively studied in the literature. The analyses based on the first order asymptotic approximation of gravity modes (that will be described in Sec. 3.6.3) in particular, neglect the information provided by deviations from the asymptotic solution. The latter, in analogy with the case of pressure modes, give information on localized sharp transitions in the stellar structure. We believe that a more detailed theoretical analysis of gravity modes is needed for the interpretation of the observed high-order gravity modes in γ Dor and SPB stars, as well as for a deeper understanding on how the detailed properties of stellar cores affect low-order g modes and mixed modes, with possible applications to the seismic analysis of β Cephei, δ Scuti stars and subgiants stars showing solar-like oscillations.

We thus decided to investigate in more detail the properties of gravity modes in main-sequence stars. Our analysis, presented in Chap. 5, is inspired by the seminal works by Berthomieu & Provost (1988) and Dziembowski et al. (1993) and by the detailed study of high-order g modes in the case of white dwarfs seismology (see e.g. Brassard et al., 1992). We analyze how the detailed shape of the chemical composition gradient that develops near the edge of the convective core perturbs the spectrum of g modes. We also discuss extra mixing processes acting near the core (e.g. turbulent mixing, overshooting) in search for observable effects on the oscillation frequencies.

1.2.3 Inferences from solar-like oscillations in visual binaries

Theoretical studies demonstrating that stellar oscillation frequencies (and their excitation) are sensitive probes of the internal structure provide indeed a strong scientific motivation for the development of asteroseismology. This alone however, is a necessary but not sufficient requirement to ensure the success of asteroseismic inferences. Which are the limiting factors for asteroseismology? Which are the number and precision of the oscillation frequencies needed for seismic inferences? How much of the information on the stellar structure carried by the frequencies can be disentangled from the uncertainties in other stellar parameters? These are questions of no simple and general answer, and are beyond the competence of this thesis; we shall therefore restrict this type of analysis to a particular domain of pulsations: solar-like oscillations in stars on or near the main sequence.

As we discussed in Sec. 1.1.1, the goal of asteroseismology is not only the determination of global parameters of stars, but also to use stars as laboratories to test physical inputs of the models. This second objective is the one that mainly attracted our interest and, as explained in the following, it needs favourable conditions to be reached. Besides the need of a precise determination of the oscillation frequencies, the availability of additional non-seismic constraints in the modelling is obviously very valuable to constrain a larger number of model parameters (see

e.g. Brown et al., 1994; Creevey et al., 2007).

Binary stars are known to provide additional constraints to the modelling and have been widely used in the literature as stringent tests for theoretical models (see e.g. Maceroni, 2006, for an overview). When modelling a binary system, we assume for both components a common initial chemical composition and the same age. Moreover, in the favourable case of visual binaries, the masses of the components are also determined. We thus further concentrate our interest on visual binaries with solar-like pulsating components, and we analyze in detail two cases: α Centauri and 12 Boötis.

The visual binary system α Centauri is amongst the promising targets in this context. Besides the availability of precise luminosities, masses ($M_A = 1.105$ and $M_B = 0.934 M_\odot$) and chemical composition for both components, interferometric and seismic constraints have recently been obtained for this system. The linear radii of both α Cen A and B are known with high precision thanks to the combination of a precise parallax (Söderhjelm, 1999) and angular diameters measured with the interferometer VINCI (Kervella et al., 2003). Moreover solar-like oscillations have been detected first in α Cen A by Bouchy & Carrier (2002), and then in component B by Carrier & Bourban (2003). Additional detections of oscillations in both components were later provided also by Bedding et al. (2004); Kjeldsen et al. (2005); Fletcher et al. (2006) and Bazot et al. (2007). The numerous and precise available observational constraints make α Cen AB a suitable target to test models of stellar structure and evolutions in conditions that are slightly different than those in the Sun. This is the reason why in Chap. 6 we present a thorough modelling of this system. The aim of this work is not just to derive the fundamental parameters of α CenA+B, but also to analyze the dependence of these parameters on the observables, on their uncertainty, on the different physics used in stellar modelling, and to investigate the capability of solar-like oscillations to constrain the properties of this system.

A most promising target for seismology that could represent a relevant step in understanding the structure of intermediate-mass stars is the binary system 12 Boötis. 12 Boo is a double-lined spectroscopic binary whose orbit has been resolved by interferometry: this allowed the determination of the masses of both components ($M_A = 1.416$ and $M_B = 1.374 M_\odot$) with a relative precision of about 0.3 % (Boden et al., 2005; Tomkin & Fekel, 2006). Although the masses of the components are very similar, their different luminosities, when compared to theoretical predictions, suggest that the secondary component is still in the central-hydrogen burning phase, while the primary is more evolved and burning hydrogen in a shell. As presented by Boden et al. (2005), however, this conclusion is highly dependent on the models and deserves further investigation. A detailed modelling of the system is reported in Chap. 7, where we study the capability of solar-like oscillations to distinguish between theoretical models obtained by including dif-

ferent mixing processes in the core.

The analysis of these binary systems represent a clear example of the potential of seismology to go beyond the determination of global parameters of stars and to allow inferences on the internal structure, provided that, as discussed in Chap. 6 and 7, the oscillation frequencies are determined with a sufficient precision.

Part I

Scientific framework

2

Stellar models: input physics and uncertainties

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter we do not intend to provide a general introduction to stellar modelling, that can be found in several excellent text books and lecture notes (see e.g. Kippenhahn & Weigert, 1990; Hansen & Kawaler, 1994; Noels, 2003; Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2000). We rather describe some recent updates in the physical inputs of stellar models and some of the known uncertainties that limit our understanding of main-sequence stars.

2.2 Basic equations of stellar structure and evolution

A thorough description of CLES, the stellar structure and evolution code used in this thesis, is given in Scuflaire et al. (2007b). We here recall the four differential equations that describe the structure of a star under the hypothesis of spherical symmetry, that is when forces such as rotation and magnetic fields are neglected:

A. Continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial r}{\partial M_r} = \frac{1}{4\pi\rho r^2}, \quad (2.1)$$

where M_r is the mass contained within a sphere of radius r and ρ is the density.

B. Hydrostatic equilibrium:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial M_r} = -\frac{GM_r}{4\pi r^4}, \quad (2.2)$$

where P is the pressure and G the gravitational constant.

C. Energy conservation:

$$\frac{\partial L_r}{\partial M_r} = \epsilon_{\text{nucl}} + \epsilon_{\text{grav}} - \epsilon_{\nu}, \quad (2.3)$$

where L_r is the energy passing outwards through a sphere of radius r , ϵ_{nucl} is the energy generation rate due to nuclear reactions, ϵ_{ν} is the energy loss rate by neutrinos and ϵ_{grav} is the gravitational energy generation rate.

D. Energy transport:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial M_r} = -\frac{GM_r T}{4\pi r^4 P} \nabla, \quad (2.4)$$

which is just the definition of the temperature gradient ∇ , that has to be replaced with the appropriate expression for the respective transport mechanism (radiation, convection or conduction, the latter playing a minor role in

main-sequence stars). In the case of radiative zones, ∇ can be written as:

$$\nabla = \nabla_{\text{rad}} = \frac{3\kappa L_{\text{r}} P}{16\pi a c G M_{\text{r}} T^4}, \quad (2.5)$$

where κ is the radiative opacity (see Sec. 2.3.3), a is the radiation constant and c the speed of light.

In addition to the differential equations presented above, equations describing the evolution of the chemical composition need to be supplemented. The chemical composition varies in time mainly due to nuclear burning and can also change because of other mixing processes taking place in the star, such as convection and diffusion. The equations describing the evolution of the abundance of the element i can be written as (see e.g. Scuflaire et al., 2007b):

$$\frac{dX_i}{dt} = \sum_j R_{ij} - \frac{1}{\rho r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho w_i X_i), \quad (2.6)$$

where R_{ij} accounts for the contribution of the j -th nuclear reaction to the variation of the chemical species i and where w_i is the diffusion velocity of the element i . On its turn w_i may depend on the gradients of the species, on thermal gradients and on external forces, such as gravitation and radiative accelerations. As previously recalled, convection is also responsible for mixing in stars: in fully convective regions the mixing speed is so fast that instantaneous mixing is usually assumed and the region is thus considered to be homogeneous (see e.g. Scuflaire et al., 2007b).

The differential equations described above need to be supplemented with boundary conditions (see e.g. Hansen & Kawaler, 1994, for a detailed discussion). In the centre of the star, defined by $m = 0$, it is required that $r = 0$ and $L = 0$. Surface boundary conditions must also be given and are usually obtained by joining smoothly the interior solution to a pre-computed atmosphere model.

In order to find a solution of these differential equations, we need to know κ , ϵ_{nuc} , ϵ_{ν} , and a relation to derive ρ in terms of $\{P, T, \text{chemical composition}\}$. These are provided by thermodynamics, nuclear and atomic physics: this fundamental contribution represents the connection between stellar physics and what we might call “micro-physics”. Moreover we need prescriptions to compute diffusion velocities and a convective stability criterion to define radiative and convective zones. In the latter a treatment of convection is also needed to compute ∇ .

In the next section we describe recent updates that have become available for some of the “micro-physics” usually adopted in stellar models. In Sec. 2.4 we will just briefly recall some of the major uncertainties in the modelling of the so-called “macro-physics”, i.e. transport and mixing processes inside stars.

For most of the different physical inputs presented in the following sections, we computed solar models and compared their properties with those of the standard

model S96 (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1996). We included the outcome of these calibrations in Appendix C.

2.3 Microphysics

2.3.1 Nuclear reactions

One of the main inputs in the computation of ϵ_{nuc} are the cross sections (σ) of the nuclear reactions under the typical conditions of stellar interiors. The evaluation of σ for astrophysical purposes resides often in the extrapolation at the low-energy end of laboratory measurements. Thermonuclear reactions in a star take place in a narrow energy window called the Gamow peak, far below the Coulomb barrier. Their cross section $\sigma(E)$ drops steeply with decreasing energy and can be parameterised as (see e.g. Hansen & Kawaler, 1994):

$$\sigma(E) = \frac{S(E)}{E} e^{-2\pi\eta}, \quad (2.7)$$

where E is the energy of the particles in the centre-of-mass system, S is the so-called astrophysical S-factor, and $\eta \propto E^{-0.5}$ is the Sommerfeld parameter (see e.g. Hansen & Kawaler, 1994). The very low value of $\sigma(E)$ at stellar Gamow peak energies makes it difficult to measure σ in laboratories.

In the recent years, however, there have been significant improvements in the measurements of reaction rates that have a direct impact on the modelling of main-sequence stars, where the fusion of hydrogen into helium is accomplished in two main ways: the proton-proton (pp) chains and the CNO cycle (see e.g. Hansen & Kawaler, 1994).

NACRE

Some 10 years after the popular compilation of nuclear reaction rates given in Caughlan & Fowler (1988) (hereafter CF88), the Nuclear Astrophysics Compilation of REaction Rates (NACRE, Angulo et al. 1999) has provided the community with a well documented and up-to-date sets of experimental data and theoretical predictions. The impact of the updated reaction rates on solar models was discussed in Morel et al. (1999). The authors noticed that the difference between the two compilations which is the most relevant in the solar case, is the lower ${}^3\text{He}({}^3\text{He}, 2p){}^4\text{He}$ reaction rate in NACRE compared to CF88. They also showed that the reduction of this reaction rate leads to calibrated solar models with a larger temperature and helium content in the core, and that the introduction of NACRE reaction rates worsens the agreement between predicted and observed sound speed profile between the Sun and the models.

Figure 2.1: Comparison between stellar models computed with CF88 and NACRE reaction rates: *Upper-left panel:* behaviour of the convective core mass fraction for main-sequence models of masses between 1 and $2 M_{\odot}$ computed with CF88 (continuous lines) and NACRE (dotted lines). *Upper-right panel:* Evolutionary tracks on the H-R diagram for the models shown in the previous panel. *Lower-left panel:* Fraction of the energy generation rate in the centre of the star provided by hydrogen burning through the pp chains. *Lower-right panel:* Evolutionary tracks of $10 M_{\odot}$ models computed with CF88 and NACRE reaction rates.

In order to investigate the effects of updating nuclear reaction rates from CF88 to NACRE on a wider domain of masses, we consider a grid of stellar models in a mass range between 1 and 10 M_{\odot} (see Appendix C for a more detailed description of the grid and of the comparisons). We find that the largest effect of NACRE, compared to CF88, is to favour the appearance of a convective core in stars with masses $M \simeq 1.1 - 1.2 M_{\odot}$ (see Fig. 2.1, upper-left panel). This effect is also clear in the evolutionary tracks shown in the upper-right panel of Fig. 2.1 and becomes relevant in the domain of stellar masses where both CNO cycle and pp chains significantly contribute to the total $\epsilon_{\text{nucl}} = \epsilon_{pp} + \epsilon_{\text{CNO}}$.

In models with NACRE, the decrease of the rate of one of the main reactions involved in pp chains leads to a larger contribution of CNO cycle, which is known to favour the appearance of a convective core, due to the large sensitivity of ϵ_{CNO} to temperature. This is shown in the lower-right panel in Fig. 2.1: in NACRE models between 1 and 1.2 M_{\odot} the relative fraction of energy generation rate due to CNO cycle in the centre of the star is increased compared to models assuming CF88 rates.

In stars where hydrogen burning through the CNO cycle dominates, no significant differences between models computed with CF88 and NACRE are found (see e.g. the case of a 10 M_{\odot} model presented in the lower-right panel of Fig. 2.1).

Revised $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate

As we consider stars with masses $M \gtrsim 1 M_{\odot}$, hydrogen burning through the CNO cycle becomes more and more the dominant source of energy generation in the stellar core as M increases. The key reaction that determines the efficiency of the CNO cycle is the radiative proton capture $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$. The cross section of this reaction was recently determined, for low energies near the Gamow peak in H-burning stars, by a new experiment performed at the underground Gran Sasso facility by the LUNA collaboration (Formicola et al., 2004). The measured value of the astrophysical S -factor at zero energy is almost a factor two smaller than the one assumed in the NACRE compilation ($S_{\text{LUNA}}(0) = 1.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ keV b}$, $S_{\text{NACRE}}(0) = 3.2 \pm 0.8 \text{ keV b}$, see also Fig. 2.2).

The implication of this revised reaction rate on the estimate of the ages of globular clusters was discussed in Imbriani et al. (2004) and Degl’Innocenti et al. (2004). The authors found that considering the revised rate leads to an increase of the age of the oldest globular clusters of about 0.7-1 Gyr with respect to the previous estimates. The main-sequence stars observed in globular clusters have masses smaller than the Sun and thus they burn hydrogen mainly through the pp chains. Nonetheless, as clearly explained in Imbriani et al. (2004), as these low-mass stars depart from the main sequence (turnoff), and increase their central temperature, hydrogen burning switches to the CNO cycle. When the new $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ rate is considered in the models, the lower efficiency of the CNO cycle leads to a more

Figure 2.2: $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate relative to the NACRE rate as a function of the temperature. Dot-dashed line: NACRE rate. Solid (dashed) line: LUNA results with more than 90% (more than 50%) of the Gamow peak covered by experimental data. Dotted line: Extrapolation-based rate from Imbriani et al. (2005). The shaded areas indicate quoted upper and lower limit for the NACRE rate and $\pm 1\sigma$ statistical uncertainty for the rate from Imbriani et al. (2005). Taken from LUNA Collaboration et al. (2006)

luminous turnoff and thus to a larger age-estimate for globular clusters.

The impact of the revised Formicola et al. (2004) reaction rate on more evolved models was presented in Weiss et al. (2005), where the authors considered in detail the effects on helium-burning low- and intermediate-mass stars.

We now consider in Fig. 2.3 the effects of updating the $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate on a grid of main-sequence models between 1 and $10 M_{\odot}$. In the mass domain where hydrogen burning through both pp and CNO contribute significantly to the total ϵ_{nuc1} , the decrease in the efficiency of CNO reactions leads to a larger relative contribution of ϵ_{pp} (Fig. 2.3, lower-left panel). This, for a model of a given mass, reduces the size of the convective core on the main sequence (upper panels of Fig. 2.3).

We also notice that, in stars where $\epsilon_{\text{nuc1}} \simeq \epsilon_{\text{CNO}}$, the whole evolutionary track in the HR diagram is displaced to higher effective temperatures (Fig. 2.3, lower-right panel). The origin of this displacement can be found in the last phase of the pre-main sequence where the evolution depends on the readjustment of CNO-cycle nuclear reactions. The lower $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate leads to a larger accumulation of ^{14}N before an equilibrium abundance can be reached at a higher luminosity (see Appendix C for a more complete set of comparisons).

Figure 2.3: As in Fig. 2.1 but comparing models computed with CF88 and CF88+the revised $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate determined by Formicola et al. (2004).

2.3.2 Equation of state

An equation of state (EOS) is a set of relations which determines all necessary thermodynamic properties of matter connecting, for instance, pressure, density, temperature and chemical composition. Present-day stellar models are based on sophisticated equations of state that include several effects such as partial ionization from temperature and pressure, degeneracy and non-ideal gas effects (see Däppen & Guzik, 2000, for an exhaustive review).

There are two basic approaches to realize a non-ideal equation of state: the *chemical picture* and the *physical picture*. The first approach is based on considering a mixture of atoms, ions, etc. and including physical effects in an intuitive and heuristic way. This approach is used in the computation of several EOS, such as CEFF (Christensen-Dalsgaard & Däppen, 1992), MHD (Däppen et al., 1988), FreeEOS¹ and SAHA-S (Gryaznov et al., 2004). One of the main advantages of such formulation is the consistency of the thermodynamic quantities derived; moreover, its analytical formulation makes it a flexible tool and allows, for instance, to change at will the metal mixture assumed in the computations.

The OPAL EOS (Rogers et al., 1996; Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002), on the other hand, follows the *physical* approach, which provides a systematic method to include non-ideal effects in the EOS (Däppen & Guzik, 2000). In this method the state of the gas is derived by considering only basic constituents (electrons and nuclei) interacting through their Coulomb potential, and no a-priori assumption on the presence of atoms and ions is taken. Because of its complexity, results have only been published as pre-computed tables, for a range of chemical compositions relevant for stellar models and for a fixed metal mixture (which includes H, He, C, N, O, and Ne from the solar abundances by Grevesse et al. 1991).

Helioseismology is known to be a sensitive test of the equation of state, in particular the convective envelope of the Sun represents a laboratory to test different formulations of the EOS (see e.g. Basu & Christensen-Dalsgaard, 1997). The main reason for this is that its stratification is nearly adiabatic and thus its properties are, to a large extent, independent from other physical inputs, such as opacities and nuclear reaction rates.

To show which are the differences between some of the EOS available “on the market” we compare the first adiabatic exponent $\Gamma_1 = (\partial \ln P / \partial \ln \rho)_{\text{ad}}$ for the (T, ρ, X, Z) structure of a calibrated solar model. The equations of state we consider in this simple comparison are: CEFF, FreeEOS v.1.4, OPAL 2001 (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002) and OPAL2005². We assume as a reference Γ_1 computed with the OPAL2001 EOS, where we take from the pre-computed tables P , C_v (specific heat at constant volume), $\chi_\rho = (\partial \ln P / \partial \ln \rho)_T$ and $\chi_T = (\partial \ln P / \partial \ln T)_\rho$ and derive all other quantities (including Γ_1) through thermodynamical identities (see

¹<http://freeeos.sourceforge.net/>

²http://phys.llnl.gov/Research/OPAL/EOS_2005/

Figure 2.4: For the structure of a solar model, relative differences in Γ_1 due to the use of different EOS. The reference Γ_1 is computed with OPAL 2001 taking C_v from the tables. *Left panel:* Differences in Γ_1 when using OPAL 2005 (dotted lines) or OPAL 2001 but taking $\Gamma_3 - 1$ instead of C_v from the tables (full lines). *Right panel:* Same as left panel but comparing the reference Γ_1 with that computed with CEFF (full line) or FreeEOS (dot-dashed line).

Scuflaire et al., 2007b).

It was shown by Boothroyd & Sackmann (2003) that the thermodynamical quantities in OPAL 2001 tables suffer from inconsistencies. As shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.4, taking $\Gamma_3 - 1 = (\partial \ln T / \partial \ln \rho)_{\text{ad}}$ instead of C_v from the OPAL tables leads to relative differences in Γ_1 in the hydrogen and helium ionisation zones that reach 0.7% in the structure of a solar model. Such differences lead to a non negligible effect on the theoretical oscillation frequencies of calibrated solar models (see e.g. the calibrated solar models presented in Appendix C).

The source for these thermodynamical inconsistencies (that mainly affect C_v) was traced by the OPAL team and a revised version of the EOS tables (OPAL 2005) was released; in this version a number of small changes in the physics were also made³. The comparison presented in Fig. 2.4 shows that OPAL 2005 is much closer to the OPAL 2001 EOS when $\Gamma_3 - 1$ is taken from the tables. Apart from the inconsistencies in C_v , intrinsic differences between 2001 and 2005 tables remain, and their effect could be interesting for helioseismic studies (see Appendix C).

As a further example we show (Fig. 2.4, right panel) the differences between Γ_1 computed with the OPAL 2001 and with two equations of state derived with the *chemical* approach: CEFF and FreeEOS. The largest differences are located near

³see http://phys.llnl.gov/Research/OPAL/EOS_2005/README for more details.

the ionization region of abundant elements. We also notice, when comparing left and right panels, that Γ_1 computed with FreeEOS is very close to that of OPAL 2005 and OPAL 2001($\Gamma_3 - 1$). As previously recalled, one of the advantages of the EOS computed in the *chemical* picture is to allow to change the metal mixture assumed in the computation: we briefly address this effect in Sec. 2.3.4.

2.3.3 Opacity

Opacity, defined as the photon absorption coefficient per unit mass, takes into account all the processes of interaction between radiation and matter. The calculation of κ involves several distinct disciplines, in particular a detailed knowledge of the equation of state and of atomic physics (see e.g. Däppen & Guzik, 2000, for a detailed description of opacity calculations).

Opacity is a key ingredient in stellar modelling as it determines the energy transport by radiation and thus ∇_{rad} (see Eq. 2.5), and it also has a large impact on the modelling of stellar pulsations. The study of stellar pulsations highlighted discrepancies between theoretical models and observations (the disagreement between predicted and observed period ratios in Classical Cepheids, as well as the missing pulsation mechanism for β Cephei stars) and led to the suggestion (see e.g. Simon, 1982) that an increase of stellar opacity could solve these long-standing problems. Though such a large increase in the opacities was first excluded by Los Alamos calculations (Magee et al., 1984), two distinct projects to calculate opacities were started: OPAL and OP.

The OPAL code was developed at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, whereas an international collaboration known as the Opacity Project (OP) was set up to calculate the extensive atomic data required to estimate stellar opacities. These efforts have resulted in large increases (by a factor of 3) in the opacity near temperatures of a few hundred-thousand degrees (see e.g. Iglesias & Rogers, 1991a,b; Rogers & Iglesias, 1992; Seaton et al., 1994; Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) which helped solving the problems we mentioned above (see e.g. Moskalik et al., 1992; Cox et al., 1992; Kiriakidis et al., 1992; Moskalik & Dziembowski, 1992; Dziembowski et al., 1993). The major reason that led to a significant opacity increase was the use of improved atomic physics in the calculations of partially ionized Fe atoms.

In order to give an estimate of the differences between current opacity calculations, we compare the latest OPAL (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) and OP (Badnell et al., 2005) opacities for the structure of two main-sequence stars: a model of the Sun and a $10 M_{\odot}$ model (Fig. 2.5, dashed lines). In the region where the solar model is the most sensitive to the opacity (i.e. the radiative region, $\log T \gtrsim 6.3$) OP and OPAL opacities agree within 2.5%. The small increase in the OP opacity compared to OPAL, leads however to a slightly better agreement between the

Figure 2.5: Comparison between opacities computed with OPAL and OP for the structure of a calibrated solar model and a $10 M_{\odot}$ model on the ZAMS. The comparison is made at fixed Z

helioseismic constraints and the solar model (see Appendix C).

If we consider the structure of the $10 M_{\odot}$ model we notice significant differences ($\sim 25\%$) near the local opacity maximum located at $\log T \simeq 5.3$, usually known as the Z -bump. OP opacities have a larger high-temperature wing of the Z -bump, and this is likely due to “the greater sophistication of the OP atomic data-work” (Seaton & Badnell, 2004). These differences, as will be described in detail in Chap. 4, have an important effect on the theoretical predictions of the excitation of pulsation modes in β Cephei and Slowly Pulsating B stars.

In the current opacity estimations only a limited number of elements (the most abundant) is included in the computations. In particular, OPAL includes 19 elements up to Ni and OP 15 elements (the same as OPAL, except for P, Cl, K and Ti that are not included in the metal mixture). The contribution to the opacity of elements heavier than Ni was considered in Rogers & Iglesias (1995) and Iglesias et al. (1995). The authors have shown that even though heavy elements are strong photon absorbers (due to their large number of bound electrons), their small abundance leads to a marginal effect on the opacity in stars with a solar metal mixture. As suggested by the authors, there are nonetheless two interesting exceptions: stars where the abundances are markedly peculiar with respect to the solar metal mixture (e.g. peculiar A stars), and for $5 \lesssim \log T \lesssim 6$ in the low-density conditions that are reached, for instance, in the envelope of massive stars. In these

$\rho - T$ conditions, neglecting the contribution of heavier elements leads to a $\sim 5\%$ systematic underestimation of the opacity for a Grevesse & Noels (1993) metal mixture (Iglesias et al., 1995).

Another factor that affects the opacity calculations is the choice of the relative abundance of elements defining Z (the metal mixture). This will be discussed in the following section.

2.3.4 Metal mixture

As we described in the previous sections, the fundamental material properties (nuclear energy generation rates, equation of state, opacity) in stellar models depend on the chemical composition of the matter. The latter is usually expressed in terms of the hydrogen (or helium) mass fraction X (Y) and Z , the mass fraction of the remaining “heavy elements”.

To fully define the chemical composition, the relative abundances of the elements composing Z (the metal mixture) needs to be specified. In the computation of stellar models the solar mixture is usually assumed in the computations. While until recently the solar metal mixture by Grevesse & Noels (1993) was adopted, the recent revision of the solar abundances by Asplund et al. (2005) has led to a significant decrease of C, N and O solar abundances, as well as a total solar metallicity 30% smaller. A major effect on the models of such a revision in the solar photospheric chemical composition is a decrease of the opacity ($\sim 20\%$) at the base of the convective envelope of the Sun (see Fig. 2.6), ruining the good agreement between the standard solar model and the seismic one.

It is indeed thanks to helioseismic constraints that we can state that current solar models computed with the revised abundances are incompatible with observations, and thus that there are major lacks in our understanding of either the physical picture of the solar interior or the determination of the abundances (or both). We should refer the reader to Guzik (2006) for an excellent review on this subject.

We do not intend to address here the effects of the revised abundances on solar models; they were treated in numerous papers in the last few years (see also Appendix C). We just recall some general effects of such a revision on the nuclear reaction rates, equation of state and opacities.

In this discussion we consider the metal mixture by Grevesse & Noels (1993) (GN93), the one revised by Asplund et al. (2005) (AGS05) and mixtures based on Asplund et al. (2005) but enriched in Ne (AGS05+Ne). An enhancement of the Neon abundance by a factor of ~ 4 has indeed been proposed by Antia & Basu (2005) and Bahcall et al. (2005) as a possible solution to recover the agreement between standard model and helioseismology. The increase of Ne would compensate for the opacity loss due to the O abundance drop. The problem is that Ne cannot

Figure 2.6: Relative opacity change between a solar model calibrated with the Asplund et al. (2005) metal mixture and metallicity ($Z/X = 0.0165$) and one computed with Grevesse & Noels (1993), $Z/X = 0.0245$. The vertical dashed line denotes the location of the base of the convective envelope derived from helioseismic inferences (see e.g. Basu & Antia, 1997). Differences between the two models are computed at fixed radius.

be directly measured in the solar photosphere. Cunha et al. (2006) suggested that determining non-LTE Ne abundances in a sample of eleven B-stars members of the Orion association could help solving the problem of Ne abundance. The result of the analysis by Cunha et al. (2006) is a Ne abundance in B-type stars 0.3 dex larger than in Asplund et al. (2005) mixture, but CNO in agreement with the new solar abundances.

Effects on nuclear reactions

A downward revision of the abundances of C, N and O leads to a lower efficiency of the nuclear reactions in the CNO cycle.

As we described in Sec. 2.3.1, the mass at which a transition is made between stars that have radiative or convective cores is sensitive to the relative contribution of CNO and pp to the overall nuclear reaction rate ϵ_{nucl} . As we see in Fig. 2.7, for given mass and Z , models computed with AGS05 metal mixture have slightly less massive cores on the main sequence.

This effect has also been analyzed in the recent work by VandenBerg et al. (2007), where the authors discuss the implications of the revised metal mixture and Z_{\odot} on model predictions of the turnoff gap for the old open cluster M67. The appearance of a gap in a color-magnitude diagram is related to the rapid contraction

phase that follows the exhaustion of hydrogen in stars that have a convective core on the main sequence. Turnoff stars in M67 have a mass near the value M_{Lcc} at which the transition is made between stars that have a radiative or a convective core on the main sequence. Since M_{Lcc} is sensitive to the assumed metallicity and CNO abundances, so is the presence of a gap in M67 models.

The study by VandenBerg et al. (2007) shows that, while isochrones computed with Grevesse & Noels (1993) abundances are able to reproduce the gap observed in M67, the new Asplund et al. (2005) metallicity for the Sun presents some difficulties when fitting solar abundance models to the M67 color-magnitude diagram, as they do not predict a gap near the turnoff where one is observed. The authors warn, however, that whether or not stellar models predict a gap at the observed magnitude in M67 depends not only on the assumed CNO abundances, but also on other uncertainties in the models (overshooting, diffusion) that affect the value of M_{Lcc} .

Another interesting effect of a decrease in the C, N, O abundances concerns the pre-main sequence evolution, as described by Alecian et al. (2007a) and Alecian et al. (2007b). The authors noticed that the revised Asplund et al. (2005) abundances allow to reproduce the observational constraints of the A-type binary system RS Chamaleontis, whereas Grevesse & Noels (1993) abundances do not. As explained in Alecian et al. (2007a), a decrease in the O abundance lowers the L/m ratio in the central regions of the models ($M \simeq 1.9 M_{\odot}$) and delays the onset of a convective core in the evolutionary state of the binary components. This allows to reproduce the luminosities and masses determined by observations. This effect is also described in the lower-right panel in Fig. 2.7 where we show that, for a model of a given mass, the onset of the convective core in the PMS happens later if we consider AGS05 metal mixture instead of GN93.

Effects on the equation of state

The behaviour of Γ_1 in the stellar structure is known to be sensitive to the ionizations of abundant elements. Γ_1 , for instance, is reduced (relative to the value of $5/3$ for a fully ionized ideal gas) in the ionization regions of hydrogen and helium. In particular, the reduction of Γ_1 in the second helium ionization zone affects the frequencies of solar oscillations and give a mean to estimate the helium abundance in the solar convective envelope (see the review by Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2002). Does the relative abundance of heavy elements composing Z also affect Γ_1 ? A general study on the influence of heavy elements in thermodynamic quantities is given, e.g., in Gong et al. (2001).

We here estimate the effect of considering different metal mixtures by comparing Γ_1 computed assuming GN93, AGS05 and a Ne-rich metal mixture (AGS05 + Ne \times 4, where the relative Ne abundance has been increased by a factor 4, as suggested by Antia & Basu 2005 to reconcile solar models and helioseismic con-

Figure 2.7: Comparison between stellar models computed with Caughlan & Fowler (1988) reaction rates but considering different metal mixtures: GN93 and AGS05 and same Z . *Upper-left panel:* behaviour of the convective-core mass fraction for main-sequence models of masses between 1 and $2 M_{\odot}$ computed with GN93 (continuous lines) and AGS05 (dotted lines). *Upper-right panel:* Evolutionary tracks on the H-R diagram for the models shown in the previous panel. *Lower-left panel:* Fraction of the energy generation rate in the centre of the star provided by hydrogen burning through the pp chains. *Lower-right panel:* Convective-core mass fraction in the pre-main sequence phase as a function of the age for models of 2, 1.5 and $1.2 M_{\odot}$. In models computed with the AGS05 metal mixture the appearance of the convective core in this evolutionary phase is retarded.

Figure 2.8: Effects on Γ_1 of considering different metal mixtures in the FreeEOS equation of state. The reference Γ_1 is computed with GN93 for a structure of a solar model. The full and dotted lines describe, respectively, the effect of considering AGS05 mixture and AGS05 with Ne enhanced by a factor of 4 as suggested by Antia & Basu (2005). The comparisons are for a given (ρ, T, X, Z) structure.

straints). The equation of state used for these comparisons is FreeEoS since it allows to evaluate thermodynamical quantities assuming different metal mixtures.

As presented in Fig. 2.8, the relative difference between Γ_1 in the solar convective envelope is modest (up to 0.07% when considering a Ne-rich mixture), but might be within reach of current helioseismic inferences, provided that this effect can be isolated from the effects of considering different Y, Z and of other uncertainties in the EOS.

Thorough analyses of these fine effects, and of the capability of helioseismic inversions to distinguish between different metal mixtures and heavy-element abundances, have been addressed in the recent pre-print by Lin et al. (2007). The authors concluded that the sensitivity of Γ_1 on Z/X allows to use solar oscillations data to indicate that models constructed with $Z/X = 0.0165$, i.e., the total metallicity of AGS05, are not consistent with the Sun. This conclusion is particularly interesting since, differently from the discrepancy on the location of the convective envelope that can be resolved by an upwards revision of the opacities, the discrepancies in Γ_1 are not affected by increasing the opacity. As noticed by the authors, this is an indication that a revision of the opacity will not resolve all discrepancies.

A further interesting conclusion of the work by Lin et al. (2007) comes from the analysis of models with enhanced neon abundance. They noticed that the mod-

Figure 2.9: Comparison between opacities computed with OPAL but with different metal mixtures for the structure of a calibrated solar model and a $10 M_{\odot}$ model on the ZAMS.

els with the abundance of neon enhanced with respect to the AGS05 values do better than the AGS05 models, but that the improvement appears to be a result of an increase in Z/X , rather than in the neon abundance. In fact, Lin et al. (2007) noted that increasing neon while keeping Z/X fixed makes the agreement between the Sun and models worse, suggesting that increasing neon abundance alone does not help in resolving the discrepancy between helioseismic constraints and solar models.

Effects on opacities

The effects on the opacity of changing the metal mixture alone are shown in Fig. 2.9 for a (T, ρ, X, Z) structure of a solar model (left panel) and of a $10 M_{\odot}$ model (right panel). In the case of the solar model, considering the AGS05 mixture leads to an increase in the opacity up to 15% compared to GN93. We have to recall however that the revised AGS05 solar abundances imply a lower value of $(Z/X)_{\odot}$ (0.0165 compared to 0.0245 in Grevesse & Noels 1993), and that the overall effect on a solar model is thus a significant ($\sim 20\%$) opacity reduction near the base of the convective envelope (see Fig. 2.6). This, as previously recalled, ruins the agreement between current solar models and helioseismic observations.

In the case of a $10 M_{\odot}$ model (Fig. 2.9, right panel) the opacity increase is mainly located near the Z -bump at $\log T \simeq 5.3$. Such increase is mainly due to

the higher relative Fe and Ni mass fractions in the AGS05 metal mixture compared to GN93. For completeness we also show in Fig. 2.9 the effect on κ of considering AGS05 metal mixture with the increase of Ne abundance proposed by Cunha et al. (2006). In the $10 M_{\odot}$ models, the higher relative Ne abundance compared to AGS05 lowers the Fe mass fraction and reduces the opacity by about $\sim 6\%$ near $\log T \simeq 5.3$.

A detailed analysis on how different metal mixtures affect the opacity and thus the pulsational properties of B stars will be given in Chap. 4.

We also notice that, for a given chemical composition and mass, the larger opacity in models computed with AGS05 affects the position of the evolutionary tracks on the HR diagram. As shown in the upper-right panel of Fig. 2.7, the higher κ displaces AGS05 tracks to lower L and T_{eff} compared to those computed with GN93 metal mixture.

2.4 Macrophysics

In addition to the knowledge of the properties of stellar matter discussed in the previous sections, the computation of stellar models involves a number of simplifying assumptions which include, for instance, a description of convection, of element settling and diffusion, and possibly of the effects on the stellar structure of rotation, magnetic fields, internal waves and mass loss (see e.g. the reviews by Chiosi 1998, Roxburgh 1998, Maeder & Meynet 2000, Demarque 2001, Talon 2007, Mathis et al. 2007 and references therein). An illustration of the complex interactions between the different processes of the so-called “macro-physics” is given in Fig. 2.10.

A general overview on these topics is beyond our competence and will not be presented here. Nonetheless, the aspects of the macro-physics relevant for our investigations will be recalled directly in the chapters describing our results, since one of the aims of our work is to investigate the effectiveness of stellar oscillations to give information on some of these processes.

As an example, in Chap. 5 we discuss how gravity oscillation modes are sensitive probes of the chemical composition gradient that develops near the convective core. In that chapter we recall how the extension of convective motions beyond the boundary set by the stability criterion (overshooting) affects the structure and evolution of main-sequence stars. Besides convection, other transport processes may alter the distribution of elements near the core of a star. The effects of element settling and diffusion and of the turbulent mixing that can be due, for instance, to rotationally-induced mixing (see e.g. Maeder & Meynet, 2000, for a review), are also described in Chap. 5.

Figure 2.10: A view of the intricate connections between various mixing and transport processes acting in a star (taken from Mathis 2007).

In the chapters dedicated to the modelling of specific stars (α Cen and 12 Bötis, in Chap. 6 and 7), we shall also recall the effects on the structure and on the seismic properties of solar-like stars of diffusion, overshooting and of considering different theoretical treatments of convection (the commonly adopted mixing-length (Böhm-Vitense, 1958) and the formulation by Canuto & Mazzitelli 1991).

3

Stellar oscillations: a general introduction

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we describe the basic theory underlying linear, adiabatic, non-radial stellar oscillations. We will briefly review the physical nature of the modes of oscillation starting from simple solutions of the perturbed ideal fluid equations. We underline the hypotheses we are assuming and the further approximations we take in order to obtain analytical solutions. Most of the topics presented in this chapter are treated in more detail in reference books such as Unno et al. (1989b) and lecture notes (Aerts, 2004; Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2003; Scuflaire, 2004)

3.2 Hydrodynamics equations

Since the proper theoretical environment to set and develop the theory of stellar oscillations is hydrodynamics, we will first recall, following Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003), the fundamental equations of fluids, then the linear perturbation equations and finally simple examples of wave motions.

3.2.1 Basic equations

The continuity equation This equation is an expression of mass conservation, which in a differential form can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}(\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\rho \mathbf{v}$ is the *mass flux density*.

The equation of motion The equation of motion considered hereafter is written under the hypothesis of an ideal fluid; we are therefore ignoring processes of energy dissipation, which may occur as a consequence of thermal conduction and internal friction (viscosity).

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \mathbf{f}, \quad (3.2)$$

where \mathbf{f} is the body force per unit volume.

The only volume force considered hereafter is the gravitational force per unit volume $\rho \mathbf{g}$, we then neglect the effects of magnetic fields and apparent forces due to stellar rotation. The gravitational acceleration \mathbf{g} can be expressed by means of the gravitational potential Φ :

$$\mathbf{g} = \nabla \Phi, \quad (3.3)$$

where Φ satisfies Poisson's equation:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = -4\pi G \rho. \quad (3.4)$$

The energy equation The energy equation provides a thermodynamic relation between p and ρ , which will complete the set of equations previously presented.

For the purpose of calculating stellar oscillation frequencies, to a high degree of precision, we assume the motion to be adiabatic. This assumption can be justified in stellar interiors by an estimate of the heating term in the energy equation (see Christensen-Dalsgaard 2003). When this term is negligible we may write:

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{\Gamma_1 p}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dt}, \quad (3.5)$$

or simply write the equation of entropy conservation:

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

where s is the entropy per unit mass.

3.2.2 Perturbation analysis

The equations of hydrodynamics form a set of non-linear, coupled differential equations which is often too complicated to be solved, even numerically. Nonetheless, stellar oscillations can be regarded, in most cases, as small perturbations on a static equilibrium structure.

We then consider every variable as developed around the equilibrium state, e.g. the pressure:

$$p(\mathbf{r}, t) = p_0(\mathbf{r}) + p'(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (3.7)$$

where p' is a small perturbation at a given point (Eulerian perturbation). We then linearize the equations in the perturbations, neglecting all terms of order higher than one in the perturbed variables. We obtain, for the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (3.8)$$

for the equations of motion:

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -\nabla p' + \rho_0 \mathbf{g}' + \rho' \mathbf{g}_0, \quad (3.9)$$

for Poisson's equation:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = -4\pi G \rho', \quad (3.10)$$

and for the energy equation in the adiabatic approximation:

$$p' + \delta \mathbf{r} \cdot \nabla p_0 = \frac{\Gamma_{1,0} p_0}{\rho_0} (\rho' + \delta \mathbf{r} \cdot \nabla \rho_0), \quad (3.11)$$

where the velocity \mathbf{v} is the local time derivative of the displacement $\delta \mathbf{r}$.

3.2.3 Pressure waves

In a compressible fluid, an oscillatory solution with small amplitude can be found assuming spatial homogeneity, adiabatic motion and neglecting the perturbation in the gravitational potential. Combining equations (3.8)-(3.11) we obtain the so-called *wave equation*

$$\frac{\partial^2 \rho'}{\partial t^2} - c_0^2 \nabla^2 \rho' = 0, \quad (3.12)$$

where

$$c_0^2 = \Gamma_1 \frac{p_0}{\rho_0}$$

is the squared adiabatic sound speed. Substituting a monochromatic plane wave of frequency ω and wave vector \mathbf{k} , i.e. $\rho' = \text{const} \times e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)}$, in the wave equation, we obtain the *dispersion relation* for acoustic waves:

$$\omega^2 = c_0^2 |\mathbf{k}|^2. \quad (3.13)$$

Writing the real solutions for p' and $\delta \mathbf{r}$ (obtained using Eq. 3.11 and 3.9), we see that the displacement $\delta \mathbf{r}$ is in the direction of the wave vector \mathbf{k} , hence acoustic waves are *longitudinal* waves.

3.2.4 Surface gravity waves

The free surface of a fluid in equilibrium in a gravitational field is generally an equipotential surface which is a sphere for a self gravitating object as a star, a plane if the field is uniform and parallel. If, under the action of some external perturbation, the surface is moved from its equilibrium position at some point, motion will occur. These perturbations will affect the interior of the fluid as well, but less and less as depth becomes greater.

To derive the equation for surface waves we consider a fluid at constant density ρ_0 , incompressible and with the boundary condition for an ideal fluid at a free surface, that is requiring the lagrangian pressure perturbation to be zero on the surface. The dispersion relation for surface gravity waves, in the “deep water” approximation, i.e. with the additional requirement that the perturbation does not diverge at great depths, is:

$$\omega^2 = g_0 k_h, \quad (3.14)$$

where k_h is the horizontal component of the wave vector. A solution for a wave traveling in the x direction is:

$$x - x_0 = -A \frac{k}{\omega} e^{kz_0} \cos(kx_0 - \omega t) \quad (3.15)$$

$$z - z_0 = -A \frac{k}{\omega} e^{kz_0} \sin(kx_0 - \omega t), \quad (3.16)$$

where z is a vertical coordinate increasing downwards. The fluid particles describe circles about the points (x_0, z_0) with a radius which diminishes exponentially with increasing depth. These expressions can be easily generalized to a boundary at finite depth, and the resulting dispersion relations are useful to explain, for instance, some fundamental behaviours of sea waves.

3.2.5 Internal gravity waves

There is another kind of gravity waves which can propagate inside the fluid; unlike surface gravity waves which are generated by a discontinuity in density on the surface of a fluid, *internal gravity* waves are caused by inhomogeneities due to the gravitational field. The argument presented hereafter follows the one given in Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003), but similar results are also achieved in Landau & Lifshitz (1959). The fluid can be treated again as incompressible, even if it is stratified in pressure under gravity; this means that we neglect density changes due to pressure perturbations but we consider those due to entropy stratification. The perturbations in the gravitational potential are also neglected.

In spherical coordinates, the privileged direction of the gravitational field suggests to separate both the displacement $\delta\mathbf{r}$ and the wave vector \mathbf{k} into radial and horizontal components:

$$\delta\mathbf{r} = \xi_r \mathbf{a}_r + \boldsymbol{\xi}_h \quad (3.17)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = k_r \mathbf{a}_r + \mathbf{k}_h \quad (3.18)$$

Looking for solutions in the form of plane waves, e.g. $\mathbf{v} = \text{const} \times e^{i(\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}-\omega t)}$ we obtain from the perturbed equation of continuity:

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{k} = 0, \quad (3.19)$$

i.e., the fluid velocity is everywhere perpendicular to the *wave vector* \mathbf{k} , that is internal gravity waves are *transverse* waves.

Considering small frequencies it is possible to take further approximations and deduce the following dispersion relation:

$$\omega^2 = \frac{N^2}{1 + k_r^2/k_h^2}, \quad (3.20)$$

where N^2 is the buoyancy frequency, defined as:

$$N^2 = g_0 \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_{1,0}} \frac{d \ln p_0}{dr} - \frac{1}{\Gamma_{1,0}} \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dr} \right). \quad (3.21)$$

When N^2 is positive the motion is oscillatory, with a maximum frequency N^2 which corresponds to modes with infinitely small horizontal wavelength. It is instructive to notice that the condition $N^2 > 0$ implies convective stability of the equilibrium structure.

3.3 Equations of stellar linear oscillations

The equations describing stellar linear adiabatic oscillations are obtained rewriting equations (3.8)-(3.11), using explicitly the spherical symmetry of the equilibrium structure. These equations will describe *nonradial* oscillations, i.e. the perturbations themselves are not assumed to be spherically symmetric, thus the case of *radial* oscillations is contained as a special case.

The problem of finding solutions to this system of equations could be set, with an amazing mathematical similarity to the Schrödinger equation for a particle in a central potential ¹, as finding the spectral properties of a differential operator in a properly defined Hilbert space. This latter approach is particularly useful when considering in the oscillations equations small effects of non-adiabaticity, rotation or small variations in the equilibrium structure.

3.3.1 Equations of stellar linear adiabatic oscillations

It is useful to separate the displacement $\delta \mathbf{r}$ into radial and horizontal components:

$$\delta \mathbf{r} = \xi_r \mathbf{a}_r + \xi_h. \quad (3.22)$$

If we take the divergence of the equation of motion for the horizontal displacement, combine it with the continuity equation (Eq. 3.8), taking into account that the horizontal gradients of the equilibrium quantities are zero, we obtain:

$$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \left[\rho' + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho_0 \xi_r) \right] = \nabla_h^2 p' + \rho_0 \nabla_h^2 \Phi'. \quad (3.23)$$

The radial component of the equation of motion is:

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial^2 \xi_r}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{\partial p'}{\partial r} - \rho' g_0 + \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Phi'}{\partial r}, \quad (3.24)$$

and Poisson's equation:

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \Phi'}{\partial r} \right) + \nabla_h^2 \Phi' = -4\pi G \rho'. \quad (3.25)$$

The equation of energy, in the adiabatic approximation, becomes:

$$\rho' = \frac{\rho}{\Gamma_1 p} p' + \rho \xi_r \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dr} \right). \quad (3.26)$$

¹The spherical symmetry of both central potential and the equilibrium structure of a star obviously plays a fundamental role

3.3.2 Separation of variables

It is useful to notice that in the set of equations (3.23)-(3.25) the derivatives with respect to the angular variables θ and ϕ only appear in the combination ∇_h^2 . Moreover the dependence on time appears only in the linear perturbations. We thus may seek a solution for the dependent variables in the form:

$$f(r, \theta, \phi, t) = \sqrt{4\pi} f'(r) Y_\ell^m(\theta, \phi) e^{-i\omega t} \quad (3.27)$$

where $Y_\ell^m(\theta, \phi)$ is a spherical harmonic, i.e. $Y_\ell^m(\theta, \phi)$ an eigenfunction of the angular Laplace operator ∇_h^2 :

$$\nabla_h^2(Y_\ell^m(\theta, \phi)) = -\frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r^2} Y_\ell^m(\theta, \phi). \quad (3.28)$$

Using equation (3.28), the radial dependence will be found by solving the following set of equations, obtained from (3.23)-(3.25) substituting the density perturbation ρ' from the energy equation (3.26) and the expression (3.27) for each perturbed variable (the subscript 0 for the equilibrium variables has been suppressed):

$$\frac{d\xi_r}{dr} = -\left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr}\right) \xi_r + \frac{1}{\rho c^2} \left(\frac{S_\ell^2}{\omega^2} - 1\right) p' - \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{\omega^2 r^2} \Phi' \quad (3.29)$$

$$\frac{dp'}{dr} = \rho(\omega^2 - N^2) \xi_r + \frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} p' + \rho \frac{d\Phi'}{dr} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{d\Phi'}{dr} \right) = -4\pi G \left(\frac{p'}{c^2} + \frac{\rho \xi_r}{g} N^2 \right) + \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r^2} \Phi' \quad (3.31)$$

where we introduced the characteristic acoustic frequency or *Lamb frequency* S_ℓ^2 :

$$S_\ell^2 = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)c^2}{r^2}, \quad (3.32)$$

and N^2 is the buoyancy or *Brunt-Väisälä* frequency:

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1} \frac{d \ln p}{dr} - \frac{d \ln \rho}{dr} \right). \quad (3.33)$$

This set of equations is a fourth order system of differential equations, in four dependent variables $\{p', \rho', \xi_r, \Phi'\}$. In order to solve it, boundary conditions are needed.

Useful relations The mean square displacements, radial and horizontal, averaged on time and on the stellar surface are:

$$\delta_r^2 = \frac{1}{2} |\xi'(r)|^2$$

Figure 3.1: Representation of spherical harmonics Y_ℓ^m . ℓ varies with each column beginning with $\ell = 1$ on the right, ending with $\ell = 5$ and m varies on each line, from top to bottom starting with $m = 0$ ending with $m = \ell$. The polar axis has been inclined by 30° relative to the plane of the page.

$$\delta_h^2 = \frac{1}{2} \ell(\ell+1) |\xi_h^2(r)|$$

Finally, if the oscillations are regarded locally as plane waves, $e^{i(\mathbf{k}x - \omega t)}$, where $\mathbf{k} = k_r \mathbf{a}_r + \mathbf{k}_h$ we may make the identification:

$$\frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r^2} = k_h^2, \quad (3.34)$$

where k_h is the length of the horizontal component of the wave vector. Thus, for example, the horizontal surface wavelength of the mode is given by

$$\lambda_h = \frac{2\pi}{k_h} \simeq \frac{2\pi R}{\sqrt{\ell(\ell+1)}} \quad (3.35)$$

and ℓ is then approximately the number of surface nodal lines. From Eq. (3.27) we may also identify m as the number of nodal meridional planes. An example of the real part of some spherical harmonics is given in Fig. 3.1.

3.3.3 Boundary conditions

Four boundary conditions, discussed in detail in Unno et al. (1989b), have to be provided to the fourth order set of equations (3.29)-(3.31).

Conditions at the center By expanding the solutions near the singular point $r = 0$, it can be shown that ξ_r' scales² as $r^{\ell-1}$, Φ' and p' instead as r^ℓ . From this expansion two conditions are obtained:

$$\xi_r \simeq \ell \xi_h \quad (3.36)$$

$$\frac{d\Phi'}{dr} \simeq \frac{\ell}{r} \Phi' \quad (3.37)$$

Surface conditions Surface boundary conditions, as for the set of equations describing the equilibrium model of a star, are rather more complicated since they directly involve the way stellar atmospheres are modelled. We will only recall simple surface conditions, see e.g. Christensen-Dalsgaard (1997) for a more detailed treatment.

A first condition is obtained imposing zero *lagrangian* pressure perturbation, i.e. :

$$\delta p = p' + \xi_r \frac{dp}{dr} = 0 \text{ at } r = R. \quad (3.38)$$

A second condition is found by requiring the continuity of Φ' and of its gradient at the boundary:

$$\frac{d\Phi'}{dr} + \frac{\ell+1}{r} \Phi' + 4\pi G \rho \delta r = 0 \text{ at } r = R. \quad (3.39)$$

²In the case of radial perturbations, i.e. $\ell = 0$, ξ_r goes as r .

3.4 Functional analysis of non-radial, adiabatic oscillations

The oscillation equations can be presented as a linear eigenvalue problem in a properly defined Hilbert space. After separation of the time dependence, the perturbed equations of motions (3.9) can be written as:

$$\omega^2 \delta \mathbf{r} = F(\delta \mathbf{r}) \quad (3.40)$$

where

$$F(\delta \mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla p' - \mathbf{g}' - \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} \mathbf{g}_0 . \quad (3.41)$$

It can be shown that F is a linear function of the displacement $\delta \mathbf{r}$.

3.4.1 Effects on frequencies of a small change in the oscillation equations

The operator F , in the case of adiabatic oscillations is hermitian (see Chandrasekhar 1963 and Chandrasekhar 1964):

$$\langle \xi, F_a(\eta) \rangle = \langle F_a(\xi), \eta \rangle , \quad \text{for } \xi, \eta \in D(F) , \quad (3.42)$$

where the inner product is defined, e.g., in Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003). From this property it follows that, if we consider a small perturbation on the oscillation equations, and therefore a new operator $F_a + \delta F$, the perturbation on the frequencies can be calculated, to the first order, using the eigenfunctions of the unperturbed operator F , i.e.

$$\delta \omega^2 = \frac{\langle \delta r_0, \delta F(\delta r_0) \rangle}{\langle \delta r_0, \delta r_0 \rangle} \quad (3.43)$$

where $F(\delta r_0) = \omega^2 \delta r_0$. The same property is used, for example, in stationary perturbations on the time-independent Schrödinger's equation, where generally to evaluate the n -th order perturbation on the eigenvalue, the $(n - 1)$ th order perturbation on the eigenfunction is needed (see e.g. Cohen-Tannoudji & Laloë (2000)).

The perturbation term in the operator in Eq.(3.43) can arise from adding new terms in the oscillations equations, or from considering small variations in the equilibrium models. As an example of the latter case in Chapter 5 we use the variational principle to estimate the first order effects of a sharp variation in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency on the periods of gravity modes.

3.5 Properties of oscillation modes

The equations presented here can be solved numerically, nonetheless analytical solutions are useful to have a physical insight into the characteristics of the modes.

The Cowling approximation A first approximation is to neglect the perturbation in the gravitational potential Φ' . The fourth order system of differential equations then reduces to a second order system of coupled equations:

$$\frac{d\xi_r}{dr} = -\left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{1}{\Gamma_1} H_p^{-1}\right) \xi_r + \frac{1}{\rho c^2} \left(\frac{S_\ell^2}{\omega^2} - 1\right) p' \quad (3.44)$$

$$\frac{dp'}{dr} = \rho(\omega^2 - N^2)\xi_r + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1} H_p^{-1} p'\right) \quad (3.45)$$

where

$$H_p = -\left(\frac{d \ln p}{dr}\right)^{-1} \quad (3.46)$$

is the *pressure scale height*, i.e. the distance over which the pressure changes by a factor e . It can be shown (see Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2003, 1991) that this approximation is justified:

- when ℓ is large,
- when n is large (n being the radial order of the mode, which is roughly given by the number of nodes in the radial displacement eigenfunction).

3.5.1 Physical nature of the modes

Accurate approximations that lead to analytical solutions of the oscillation equations, are presented later in Sect. 3.6. Here we recall a simple approximation (see Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2003), useful for a qualitative treatment and classification of the oscillation modes in stars.

A first crude approximation is to neglect, for oscillations of high radial order, the terms in Equations (3.44) and (3.45) containing only derivatives of equilibrium quantities, which are supposed to vary much more slowly than the perturbed variables. The set of equations is then reduced to a single second order ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{d^2 \xi_r}{dr^2} = -K(r)\xi_r, \quad (3.47)$$

where

$$K(r) = \left(1 - \frac{S_\ell^2}{\omega^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{N^2}{\omega^2}\right). \quad (3.48)$$

The local solutions of such equation depend on the sign of $K(r)$: when $K(r)$ is positive the solution is an oscillating function of r , that can be written as:

$$\xi_r(r) \sim \cos\left(\int K^{1/2} dr + \phi\right), \quad K > 0$$

ξ_r has an exponential behaviour when $K < 0$

$$\xi_r(r) \sim e^{\pm \int |K|^{1/2} dr + \phi}, \quad K < 0$$

The solution oscillates when

$$\omega > |S_\ell| \quad \text{and} \quad \omega > |N| \quad (3.49)$$

or

$$\omega < |S_\ell| \quad \text{and} \quad \omega < |N|, \quad (3.50)$$

and behaves exponentially when:

$$\omega < |S_\ell| \quad \text{and} \quad \omega > |N| \quad (3.51)$$

or

$$\omega > |S_\ell| \quad \text{and} \quad \omega < |N|. \quad (3.52)$$

A mode is then generally oscillating in regions where condition (3.49) or (3.50) is fulfilled and will decay exponentially otherwise. The solution is said to be *trapped* between two regions of exponential behaviour, the boundaries of the trapping region are generally at points where

$$K(r) = 0.$$

Low frequency modes, satisfying condition (3.50) are classified as *g modes*, whereas those satisfying (3.49) are labeled *p modes*. Since both *Lamb* and *buoyancy* frequencies play a fundamental role in determining the behaviour of the oscillations, in Fig. 3.2 we shown the behaviour of both S_ℓ and N as a function of fractional radius.

3.5.1.1 p modes

The region where p modes are trapped is bounded by the surface of the star and by r_t , so that $S_\ell^2(r_t) = \omega^2$, i.e., for a mode with given cyclic frequency ω :

$$c^2(r_t) \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r_t^2} = \omega^2. \quad (3.53)$$

The trapping point at the surface of the star is not contained in the simple analysis presented in this section, but it can be explained by a general asymptotic description of the oscillations derived in Deubner & Gough (1984).

Typically for p modes we have that $\omega \gg N$, so that K can be approximated by:

$$K(r) \simeq \frac{1}{c^2}(\omega^2 - S_\ell^2). \quad (3.54)$$

This relation reveals the physical nature of these modes: they are acoustic waves as their characteristics are, to a first approximation, determined by the variation of the sound speed with r .

Figure 3.2: Propagation diagram for a solar model. The solid line represents the Brunt-Väisälä frequency N , the short- and long-dashed line the Lamb frequency S_ℓ for, respectively, $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$. All the quantities are shown as a function of the fractional radius. The frequency domain of solar-like oscillations (high-order pressure modes) falls within the horizontal dotted lines. The heavy horizontal lines indicate the propagation region of a pressure and of a gravity mode.

3.5.1.2 g modes

In the case of g modes the turning points are determined by the condition $N = \omega$. The presence and extension of convective regions in the star determine the trapping points of these low frequency modes, since the physical condition of convective instability ($N^2 \leq 0$) excludes the presence of g modes, sought as oscillating perturbations around a stability condition. As shown in Fig. 3.2 the trapping points of such modes are independent from ℓ . For high order g modes $\omega^2 \ll S_\ell^2$ and K becomes:

$$K(r) \simeq \frac{1}{\omega^2} (N^2 - \omega^2) \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{r^2}. \quad (3.55)$$

The properties of gravity modes are therefore determined by the behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency in the stellar interior.

3.5.1.3 Mixed modes

The classification of stellar oscillation modes goes beyond this simple distinction between p and g modes: there are, for instance, cases where the oscillation modes have a mixed pressure and gravity character.

Figure 3.3: Same as in Fig. 3.2 but this time for a $1.4 M_{\odot}$ subgiant star. The heavy horizontal line indicates the propagation region of mode of mixed pressure and gravity character.

As an example we show in Fig. 3.3 the behaviour of S_{ℓ} and N in a model of a $1.4 M_{\odot}$ subgiant star, where N reaches large values in the core as the model leaves the core hydrogen-burning phase (see Chap. 7 for a detailed discussion). In this case K may be positive at relatively high frequency both in the outer parts where ω is greater than both S_{ℓ} and N , the mode thus behaving as a p mode, and in the core where $\omega < S_{\ell}, N$ and the mode behaves like a g mode. Such mixed modes have a particularly interesting diagnostic potential on the core-structure of stars, as will be discussed in Chap. 5 and 7.

3.6 Asymptotic approximation of stellar oscillations

Equations of linear adiabatic stellar oscillations can be solved numerically, nonetheless, as already discussed in Ledoux & Walraven (1958), analytical but necessarily approximated solutions provide a powerful tool to reveal the fundamental physical parameters that determine the properties of oscillation spectra. We will only briefly recall the basic assumptions that are taken in such an approximation and refer to the work of Tassoul (1980) and to Chapter 7 in Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003) for an exhaustive treatment. Accurate analytical approximations for the solutions of stellar oscillation equations have also been obtained in the series of papers by Smeyers (e.g. Smeyers 2006, and references therein) and by Roxburgh & Vorontsov (see e.g. Roxburgh & Vorontsov 1994a,b, 2000a,b, 2001).

In this section we present an asymptotic approximation of the equations of stellar oscillations introduced in Deubner & Gough (1984) and also reported in Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003).

The starting point of the asymptotic treatment is the second order set of equations (3.44)-(3.45). This set is obtained applying to the fourth order system (3.29)-(3.31) the so-called *Cowling approximation*, that is, the perturbations in the gravitational potential are neglected; this approximation, as described in Section 3.5, is accurate for high ℓ or n modes.

The next, somewhat tricky, step is to rewrite the equations in the independent variable X , related to the radial displacement by

$$X = c^2 \sqrt{\rho} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{r},$$

where c and ρ represent the adiabatic sound speed and density of the equilibrium model. After considerable manipulation and making the assumptions that the variations of \mathbf{g} and r are negligible with respect to those of the perturbations, it is possible to rewrite the equations as one second order differential equation in X :

$$\frac{\partial^2 X}{\partial r^2} + K(r)X = 0. \quad (3.56)$$

$K(r)$ is expressed by:

$$K(r) = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \left[1 - \frac{\omega_c^2}{\omega^2} - \frac{S_\ell^2}{\omega^2} \left(1 - \frac{N^2}{\omega^2} \right) \right] \quad (3.57)$$

and depends on the *cutoff frequency* ω_c (see Fig. 3.4),

$$\omega_c^2 = \frac{c^2}{4H} \left(1 - \frac{dH}{dr} \right), \quad (3.58)$$

where H is the local density scale height,

$$H^{-1} = -\frac{d \ln \rho}{dr}.$$

The sign of $K(r)$, that can indeed change in different regions of the star, determines whether the behaviour of the solution is exponential or oscillatory. The so-called *trapping* points of a mode of oscillation, are determined as the location where the perturbation loses its oscillatory behaviour to start decaying exponentially (see Section 3.5.1).

Near the surface of the star, S_ℓ^2 is small due to its c/r scaling, $K(r)$ is then:

$$K(r) \simeq \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \left(1 - \frac{\omega_c^2}{\omega^2} \right)$$

so for frequencies lower than ω_c , $K(r)$ is negative and the behavior of the perturbation is exponentially decaying, that is the mode, with $\omega < \omega_c$ is “trapped” inside the star; when $\omega > \omega_c$, the mode propagates through the atmosphere and rapidly loses energy.

Figure 3.4: The acoustic cutoff frequency ω_c in the outer parts of a $1.0 M_\odot$, $X_c = 0.30$ star.

It is easier to derive some other qualitative properties of the solutions writing K as

$$K(r) = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \left(1 - \frac{\omega_{\ell,+}^2}{\omega^2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\omega_{\ell,-}^2}{\omega^2} \right). \quad (3.59)$$

In the interior of a star:

$$\omega_{\ell,+} \simeq S_\ell \quad \omega_{\ell,-} \simeq N$$

we then find again the trapping conditions described in Section 3.5.1.

3.6.1 The JWKB approximation

JWKB (Jeffreys, Wentzel, Kramers and Brillouin) is a general method to find approximated solutions of wave equations in the so-called “semi-classical” limit. It is, for example, useful to obtain a semi-classical solution of the Schrödinger equation, reliable in the short-wavelength limit (see Sakurai (1994) and Fröman & Fröman (1965) for the mathematical foundation of this method). The assumption is that the solution varies rapidly compared to the equilibrium variables, $K(r)$ in the case of Equation (3.56), that is:

$$\xi'_r(r) = a(r)e^{i\Psi(r)}, \quad (3.60)$$

where $a(r)$ varies slowly with r compared to $\Psi(r)$, so that the local radial wave number k_r :

$$k_r = \frac{d\Psi}{dr}$$

is large. Substituting the expression above in the equations and neglecting terms in the second derivative of a , we find $a(r) = |K(r)|^{-1/4}$. We can obtain local sinusoidal or exponential solutions if $K(r)$ is, respectively, positive or negative. To find a solution that holds throughout the star we need to apply boundary conditions and require that exponential and oscillatory solutions connect continuously and smoothly where $K(r) = 0$, which represents a turning point of the wave. Such a connection is achieved by approximating the solution near the turning point with Airy’s functions. We refer to Gough (2007) for an exhaustive discussion of the JWKB approximation and its application in the case of stellar oscillations.

The result of this approach provides, after some manipulations, asymptotic expressions of the eigenfunctions and of the frequencies of pressure and gravity modes.

3.6.2 Asymptotic expression of p-mode frequencies

In the case of p modes, where $\omega^2 \gg N^2$, the approach followed by Tassoul (1980) is to retain in the approximation, terms up to the order $1/\omega$. This leads, for high-order low-degree modes, to:

$$\nu_{nl} \simeq \left(n + \frac{\ell}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \alpha\right)\Delta\nu - (A\ell(\ell + 1) - \delta) \frac{\Delta\nu^2}{\nu_{nl}}, \quad (3.61)$$

where

$$A = \frac{1}{4\pi^2\Delta\nu} \left[\frac{c(R)}{R} - \int_0^R \frac{dc}{dr} \frac{dr}{r} \right] \quad (3.62)$$

and

$$\Delta\nu = \left(2 \int_0^R \frac{dr}{c} \right)^{-1}. \quad (3.63)$$

$\Delta\nu$ represents the inverse of twice the acoustic radius of the star, that is the time it takes for a sound wave to propagate from the center to the surface of the star, and approximatively scales as the mean density of the star. From Eq. 3.61 we see that, for a given ℓ , the frequencies are asymptotically equally spaced by $\Delta\nu$. Eq. 3.61 also suggests that, in this approximation, the oscillation spectrum can be characterized by two frequency spacings: the “large” frequency separation:

$$\Delta\nu_{n,\ell} \equiv \Delta\nu_\ell(n) = \nu_{n,\ell} - \nu_{n-1,\ell} \simeq \Delta\nu \quad (3.64)$$

and the “small” frequency separation:

$$\delta\nu_{n,\ell} \equiv \delta\nu_{\ell\ell+2}(n) = \nu_{n\ell} - \nu_{n-1,\ell+2} \simeq -(4\ell + 6) \frac{\Delta\nu}{4\pi^2\nu_{n\ell}} \int_0^R \frac{dc}{dr} \frac{dr}{r}, \quad (3.65)$$

where the term in $c(R)$ has been neglected, since the value of the sound speed at the surface is small compared to the other quantities. The small frequency separation is sensitive to the core structure of the star, because of the $1/r$ dependence of the integrand in equation (3.65).

Roxburgh & Vorontsov (2003b) recently proposed as an additional seismic indicator r_{02} , the ratio between the small and large frequency separations defined by:

$$r_{02}(n) = \frac{\delta\nu_{n,0}}{\Delta\nu_{n,1}} = \frac{\nu_{n,0} - \nu_{n-1,2}}{\nu_{n,1} - \nu_{n-1,1}}. \quad (3.66)$$

This combination of frequencies represents a reliable indicator of the conditions in the deep stellar interior as it is nearly independent of the outer layers of the star. *This is the reason why in Chapter 6, which is dedicated to the modelling of α Centauri AB, we choose r_{02} as a constraint to determine the fundamental parameters (primarily the age) of the binary system.*

3.6.3 Asymptotic expression of g-mode periods

In the case of gravity modes the properties of the eigenfunctions depend essentially on the zeros of N and so on the number and location of convective regions.

We shall examine the case of a model consisting of an inner convective core and an outer radiative envelope, and we refer to the work by Tassoul (1980) for a complete analysis of other possible cases. The first order asymptotic approximation shows that the periods of low-degree, high-order g modes (where $N^2 \gg \omega^2$) are given by:

$$P_k = \frac{\pi^2}{L \int_{x_0}^1 \frac{|N|}{x} dx} (2k + n_e), \quad (3.67)$$

Figure 3.5: The comb-like structure of the oscillation spectrum of the sun, the ordinate is normalized to show velocity power per frequency bin. (from Elsworth et al., 1995)

where $L = [\ell(\ell + 1)]^{1/2}$, n_e is the effective polytropic index of the surface layer, x , the normalized radius and x_0 , the boundary of the convective core. To avoid confusion with n_e the radial order of g modes is represented by k .

The periods are asymptotically equally spaced in k and the spacing decreases with increasing L . It is therefore natural to introduce, in analogy to the large frequency separation of p modes, the *period spacing* of gravity modes, defined as:

$$\Delta P = P_{k+1} - P_k . \quad (3.68)$$

In Chapter 5 we will show that deviations from a constant ΔP contain information on the chemical composition gradient left by a convective core evolving on the main sequence.

3.7 Excitation and damping of stellar oscillations

Stellar oscillations may be excited in two different ways: by being self-excited and by being intrinsically damped but externally forced, typically by convection (as in the Sun). The linear adiabatic theory presented so far predicts the characteristics of the resonances of the star (eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions), but gives no information whether the mode considered is excited to an observable amplitude.

To illustrate the damping and excitation of pulsation modes, we write the time dependence of the oscillations as $\exp(-i\omega t)$ separating the angular frequency ω into a real and an imaginary part as $\omega = \omega_r + i\omega_i$ (see Eq. 3.27). The amplitude of the mode grows or decays with time depending on whether $\omega_i > 0$ or $\omega_i < 0$.

A positive growth rate therefore means that the mode is unstable and so, *self excited*, a negative linear growth rate implies the stability of the mode, which could still be excited by an external forcing, as in the case of solar-like oscillations described below.

3.7.1 Stochastically excited pulsators

Non-adiabatic calculations taking convection into account generally find that modes in stars on the cool side of the classical instability strip (e.g. the Sun) are stable. The excitation of the observed modes is attributed to stochastic forcing by the near-surface convection which leads to the excitation of p modes in a wide range of frequencies.

A stochastically excited mode will show, in the power spectrum of time series, a peak with a finite width inversely proportional to the decay time of the mode, as in a simple damped harmonic oscillator forced with a function whose power spectrum weakly depends on the frequency.

The amplitudes of these oscillations are determined by the balance between the excitation and damping, and are expected to be rather low. Estimates of the amplitudes and frequencies of solar-like oscillations in a broad range of stellar parameters were given in Christensen-Dalsgaard & Frandsen (1983). These results were later used by Kjeldsen & Bedding (1995) to show that the amplitudes of solar-like oscillations are expected to scale as L/M , where L is the luminosity of the star and M , its mass. The increase of the amplitudes with luminosity was confirmed by the estimates obtained by Houdek et al. (1999), who determined the damping and excitation rates for radial modes introducing a nonlocal, time-dependent mixing-length model for convection (Gough, 1977) in the calculations.

Recent theoretical estimates of mode excitation rates have been obtained in Samadi et al. 2007 (and references therein). In this work the authors included the outcome of numerical 3D simulations of surface convective zones to characterize the turbulent spectra and the convective velocities in the uppermost part of the convective zone of several solar-type stars.

3.7.2 Self-excited pulsators: the case of β Cephei and Slowly Pulsating B stars

We hereafter recall some of the main properties of the mechanism responsible for the excitation of oscillation modes in B stars; we refer to Dziembowski et al.

(1993), Dziembowski & Pamiatnykh (1993), Pamiatnykh (1999) and Dupret (2002) for an exhaustive description.

For a physical interpretation of the driving mechanism in B stars we consider (see e.g. Ledoux, 1965) the following simplified expression for ω_i :

$$\omega_i = -\frac{1}{2\omega_r^2} \frac{\int_0^M \frac{\delta T}{T} \left(\frac{d\delta L}{dm} - \delta\epsilon \right) dm}{\int_0^M \xi_r^2 dm} \quad (3.69)$$

where $\delta\epsilon$, δT and δL represent the Lagrangian perturbations of the nuclear reactions, temperature and luminosity. This expression is obtained for the case of a radial mode, neglecting the perturbations of the convective luminosity and in the quasi-adiabatic approximation (the eigenfunctions obtained in the adiabatic approximation are used in the expressions, see e.g. Dupret 2001 for a detailed discussion). Even if obtained under these restrictive hypothesis, Eq. 3.69 is very instructive for a qualitative understanding of the excitation mechanism of pulsations.

Neglecting the perturbation of nuclear reaction, we see in Eq. 3.69 that the regions contributing to the driving are those where δL is decreasing outwards at the hot phase ($\delta T > 0$). In order to estimate in which situations this condition can be reached we express the luminosity perturbation as:

$$\frac{\delta L}{L} = \left(4\frac{\xi_r}{r} + 3\frac{\delta T}{T} - \frac{\delta\kappa}{\kappa} + \frac{\partial\delta T/\partial r}{dT/dr} \right), \quad (3.70)$$

and we focus on the term $-\delta\kappa/\kappa$ which plays a dominant role in the excitation mechanism of opacity-driven pulsators such as β Cephei and Slowly Pulsating B stars (κ mechanism).

In the quasi-adiabatic approximation, we can write:

$$\frac{\delta\kappa}{\kappa} = \kappa_{\text{PS}} \frac{\delta P}{P} = \frac{(\Gamma_3 - 1)\kappa_T + \kappa_\rho}{\Gamma_1} \frac{\delta P}{P}, \quad (3.71)$$

where $\kappa_T = (\partial\kappa/\partial T)_\rho$ and $\kappa_\rho = (\partial\kappa/\partial\rho)_T$.

In usual circumstances (e.g. Kramers opacity law, complete ionization) $\kappa_{\text{PS}} \simeq -0.8$ and thus, since $\delta P/P$ is generally increasing outwards at the hot phase, the opacity term contributes to the damping of the pulsations, as δL increases outwards. The situation is different in the ionization regions of elements that have a significant contribution to the opacity: for B stars this is the case for the region of the Z opacity bump at $\log T \simeq 5.3$ (see Fig. 3.6, panel a). In this region κ_{PS} has a steep increase outwards and can take positive values (Fig. 3.6, panel b). Consequently, the contribution of $\delta\kappa/\kappa$ implies that $\delta L/L$ decreases outwards at the hot phase, and has a driving effect on the pulsations. Let us notice however that the hot wing of an opacity bump has generally a damping effect.

Besides the behaviour of κ , we recall (see e.g. Pamiatnykh, 1999), that there are two additional conditions that have to be fulfilled to excite a pulsation mode:

Figure 3.6: Opacity (*panel a*) and $(\partial \ln \kappa / \partial \ln P)_{\text{ad}}$ (*panel b*) as a function of the temperature in the structure of a $10 M_{\odot}$ model computed with OPAL (full lines) and OP (dotted lines). The initial chemical composition of the model is $(X_0, Z_0) = (0.7, 0.02)$ and its $\log T_{\text{eff}} \simeq 4.327$. Differential work integral $-dW/d \log T$ (*panel c*) and work integral (*panel d*) as a function of temperature for the low-order ($k = 3$), $\ell = 2$ gravity mode g3. Results obtained with OPAL and OP are represented, respectively, by full and dotted lines.

Figure 3.7: As in Fig. 3.7 but for the high-order ($k=20$), $\ell = 2$ gravity mode g_{20} .

- the amplitude of the pressure eigenfunction $\delta P/P$ must be large and vary slowly with r in the driving region;
- in the driving zone the thermal timescale, $\tau_{\text{th}} = \int_r^R T c_V dM/L$, must be comparable or longer than the oscillation period. If this is not the case, then the potentially driving region remains in thermal equilibrium during the pulsation cycle.

In order to give an example on the effectiveness of the κ mechanism in B stars, and in particular to show how this excitation mechanism is sensitive to the properties of stellar opacity, we illustrate in Fig. 3.6 and 3.7 the stability analysis of two $\ell = 2$ pulsation modes in a $10 M_\odot$ model on the main sequence. The results were obtained using two different opacity tables OPAL (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) and OP (Badnell et al., 2005) in the code MAD (Dupret, 2001), that solves the full set of equations describing non-adiabatic stellar oscillations. The pulsation modes considered are: a β Cephei-type pulsation (the low-order gravity mode g3) and an SPB-type mode (the high-order gravity mode g20).

In the case of g3 the conditions for excitation are reached with both OPAL and OP opacities, and the main contribution to the driving of the mode is found in the region of the Z opacity bump at $\log T \simeq 5.3$. This is presented in Fig. 3.6 by means of the differential dimensionless work integral $-dW/d \log T$ (panel c) and the dimensionless work integral W (panel d). The dimensionless work integral W is defined as follows (see Dupret, 2002, for more details):

$$W(m) = -\frac{R^{3/2}}{2\sqrt{GM}\omega_r} \frac{\int_0^m \text{Im} \left(\frac{\delta \rho^*}{\rho} T \delta S \right) (\Gamma_3 - 1) dm}{\int_0^M (|\xi_r|^2 + \ell(\ell+1)|\xi_h|^2) dm}, \quad (3.72)$$

where $*$ denotes the complex conjugate. $W(r)$ is defined so that its value at the surface is proportional to the growth rate ($W(M) \propto \omega_i$, thus $W(M) > 0$ if the mode is excited). The regions where W has a positive derivative contribute to the excitation of the mode, whereas the regions where $-dW/d \log T < 0$ are damping the mode.

The case of the g20 mode is somewhat different: if OPAL opacities are used, this oscillation mode suffers from a substantial damping in the region of the hot wing of the local opacity maximum and is therefore stable (Fig.3.7, full lines). If we now consider the results obtained with OP opacity tables, the differences in the opacity and in its derivatives in the hot wing of the Z-bump (see Fig. 3.7, panel a and b) affect substantially the work integral of mode g20 (panel c and d) so that the mode is predicted to be excited (panel d, dotted line).

3.8 Pulsating stars on the main sequence

We here briefly recall some of the basic properties of the classes of main-sequence pulsating stars that are related to the work presented in this thesis. A broader overview on different types of pulsators including stars in more advanced evolutionary phases can be found, e.g., in Aerts (2004) and Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003).

Solar-like pulsators - *high-order p modes*

As recalled in Sec. 3.7.1, solar-like oscillations are excited by near-surface convection and we thus expect such oscillations to be excited in all stars with outer convection zones.

If we consider stars near or on the main-sequence this implies that solar-like oscillations are predicted from the coolest low-mass stars up to objects with spectral type F (see Fig. 3.8). However, the oscillations due to stochastic excitation lead to very small amplitudes (less than 1 m s^{-1} in velocity and a few parts per million in intensity), which makes them hard to detect, particularly for the low-mass main-sequence stars. The amplitudes of solar like oscillations, as discussed in Sec. 3.7.1, roughly scale as L/M : we therefore expect very low amplitudes for stars less massive than the Sun and the largest amplitude for the more luminous stars.

The periods of solar-like oscillation are of the order of a few minutes for main-sequence stars (5 min for the Sun), and become larger for more evolved stars (a few hours for red giant stars). An overview of the frequency domain of solar-like oscillations observed in different stars is presented in Fig. 3.9. A first estimation of the typical frequencies of solar-like oscillations is given in Kjeldsen & Bedding (1995), where it is shown that the frequency corresponding to the maximum amplitude ν_{max} can be expressed as:

$$\nu_{max} = \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{\sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}/5777}(R/R_{\odot})^2} 3.05 \text{ (mHz)}.$$

As recalled in the introduction, the recent development of very stable spectrographs for radial-velocity measurements to search for extra-solar planets has provided the accuracy needed to detect the small-amplitude solar-like oscillations in stars other than the Sun. Observations of solar-like oscillations are nowadays accumulating rapidly, and measurements have now been reported for several main-sequence and subgiant stars such as τ Cet, 70 Oph A, α Cen A and B, μ Ara, HD49933, β Vir, Procyon A, β Hyi, δ Eri, η Boo and ν Ind (see e.g the recent overview given in Bedding & Kjeldsen 2007).

The list of stars where solar-like oscillations are detected will grow even more rapidly in the very near future, thanks to the ongoing and to the forthcoming space-

Figure 3.8: A Hertzsprung-Russell diagram showing the instability strips of different classes of pulsating stars. Taken from Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003).

Figure 3.9: Power spectra of 13 stars showing solar-like oscillations detected with the spectrograph CORALIE (except for 70 Oph that was observed with HARPS). From top to bottom: low-mass main-sequence stars (e.g. 70 Oph A), subgiant stars (e.g. η Boo) and red giants (e.g. ϵ Oph). The frequency domain corresponding to solar-like oscillations is enclosed by full lines. The power scale is arbitrary and the power at the lowest frequency (which is substantial compared to the amplitude of the oscillations in the case of the low-mass stars) is due to noise. (Courtesy of Fabien Carrier).

based ultra-precise photometric observations of stellar pulsations with CoRoT (Baglin et al., 2006) and KEPLER (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 2007).

γ Doradus stars - *high-order g modes*

γ -Doradus are main-sequence stars with masses around $1.5 M_{\odot}$ (see e.g. Guzik et al., 2000) that show both photometric and line profile variations. Their spectral class is A7-F5 and their effective temperature is between 7200-7700 K on the ZAMS and 6900-7500 K above it (Handler, 1999). γ -Dor stars are multiperiodic oscillators with periods between 8 hours and 3 days (high order g-modes). The modulation of the radiative flux by convection at the base of the convective envelope was proposed as the excitation mechanism for such stars (see e.g. Guzik et al., 2000; Dupret et al., 2004).

δ Scuti variables - *low-order p and g modes*

δ Scuti are variable stars with masses between 1.5 and $2.5 M_{\odot}$ and are found at the crossing of the main sequence with the Cepheid instability strip (see Fig. 3.8). The oscillation modes (low-order pressure and gravity modes) are driven by the κ mechanism acting in the HeII ionization region (see e.g. Pamyatnykh, 2000). The observed periods are in the range between 30 minutes and 6 hours. A review on their observational properties is given, e.g., in Rodríguez & Breger (2001). At present, the best observed δ Scuti star is FG Virginis, for which more than 75 oscillation frequencies are detected (Breger et al., 2005).

Even though the largest fraction of the known δ Scuti stars are in the main-sequence or immediate post-main-sequence stage of evolution, δ Scuti pulsations can also occur among pre-main sequence stars (see e.g. the review by Marconi & Palla, 2004).

Slowly Pulsating B stars - *high-order g modes*

Slowly pulsating B stars (SPB) are multiperiodic main-sequence stars with masses from about 3 to $8 M_{\odot}$ and spectral type B3-B8 (Waelkens, 1991). High order g-modes of periods typically between 1 and 3 days are found to be excited by the κ -mechanism activated by the Z opacity bump (see Sec. 3.7.2). Recent observations (see Jerzykiewicz et al., 2005; Handler et al., 2006; Chapellier et al., 2006) and theoretical instability analyses (see Chap. 4) also suggest high-order g-modes being excited in a large fraction of the more massive β Cephei pulsators (see below): the seismic modelling of these hybrid pulsators looks very promising as it would benefit from the information on the internal structure carried by both low-order p and g modes (β Cephei type oscillation modes) and high-order g modes (SPB-type pulsation).

β Cephei stars - low-order p and g modes

β Cephei stars are main-sequence stars with spectral type between B0 and B3. They have masses between ~ 7 and $20 M_{\odot}$ and exhibit periodic variations in the range 2-8 hours detected via both photometric and spectroscopic observations. These variations are interpreted as low-order radial and non-radial pressure modes and gravity modes. We refer to Stankov & Handler (2005) for a recent review on their observational properties.

The mechanism responsible for the excitation of pulsations in β Cep stars is the same as in SPB stars (see Sec. 3.7.2). The progresses in both the observational side and in the seismic interpretation of β Cephei stars have shown that stellar models fail to reproduce the observed oscillation frequencies in the best-studied stars (see e.g. Pamyatnykh et al., 2004; Aussenloos et al., 2004; Handler et al., 2006). A more detailed description and analysis of this problem, together with suggested possible solutions, is given in Chap. 4.

Part II

Probing stellar interiors through asteroseismology

4

Revised instability domains of SPB
and β Cephei stars

The results presented in this chapter are published in the following papers:

Miglio, A., Montalbán, J., Dupret, M.-A.: *Instability strips of SPB and β Cephei stars: the effect of the updated OP opacities and of the metal mixture*, (2007), MNRAS 375, L21-L25

Miglio, A., Montalbán, J., Dupret, M.-A.: *Revised instability domains of SPB and β Cephei stars*, (2007), CoAst, 151, 48-56

Miglio, A., Bourge, P.-O., Montalbán, J., Dupret, M.-A.: *Instability strips of SPB and β Cephei stars: a parametric study of iron enhancement*, (2007), CoAst, 150, 209-210

4.1 Introduction

At the beginning of the nineties, OPAL opacity tables (Rogers & Iglesias, 1992) signified a revolution in stellar physics. In particular, an increase of the Rosseland mean opacity (κ) as large as a factor 3 for temperatures near $3 \cdot 10^5$ K (known as “Z–bump”) allowed to solve the long-standing problem of B-type pulsators: β Cep and Slowly Pulsating B-stars (SPB) pulsate due to κ -mechanism activated by this metal opacity bump (Cox et al., 1992; Kiriakidis et al., 1992; Moskalik & Dziembowski, 1992; Dziembowski et al., 1993). Subsequent improvements in opacity calculations by including other iron-group elements in the metal mixture (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) have led to an additional enhancement of opacity at $\log T \sim 5.2$ and low densities and, therefore, to a decrease of the discrepancies still remaining between theoretical pulsation models and observations. The stability analysis of B-stars by Pamyatnykh (1999) for models computed with updated OPAL and OP opacity tables (Opacity Project, Seaton, 1996, and references therein) allowed to conclude that at that time theoretical standard models were able to explain most of the observed β Cep and SPB stars.

However, as observational capabilities progress, B-type pulsators are now found in low metallicity environments (see e.g. Kołaczkowski et al., 2006, and references therein), and a large number of pulsation modes is being detected in B stars, with frequency domains sometimes revealing new discrepancies between theory and observations. For instance, the two β Cep stars 12 Lacertae and ν Eridani (see Handler et al., 2006; Jerzykiewicz et al., 2005) present low order p-modes with frequencies larger than those predicted by pulsation models, as well as high-order g-modes (SPB type oscillation).

It is known (see e.g. Moskalik & Dziembowski, 1992) that stellar pulsation models are sensitive to $\sim 20\%$ changes in opacity. There are two major factors that determine the opacity in a stellar model for a given (T, ρ, X, Z) -structure: the metal mixture adopted in the definition of Z and the opacity calculations themselves. The latter, due to their complexity, are usually included in stellar structure

codes as pre-computed tables (see Sec. 2.3.3). In the following Sections we analyse in more detail the current uncertainties on both factors and, as a second step, we describe the effects of these uncertainties on the instability domains of B stars (see Sec. 4.5).

4.2 Metal mixtures

Stellar opacity can be influenced by the choice of a global metal mixture, as well as by local variations of metal relative abundance due e.g. to the accumulation of a chemical element in a region of the star.

4.2.1 Local accumulation of iron

In order to explain the excitation of the pulsation modes in the broad frequency range observed in ν Eri (in particular of the highest frequency mode $\nu \simeq 7.9$ c/d), Pamyatnykh et al. (2004) proposed a local enhancement of iron in the “Z-bump” region, as Cox et al. (1992) suggested to overcome the difficulties in explaining β Cep pulsations with the first OPAL opacity tables. An enhancement of iron in the driving region could be physically justified by the effect of selective radiative forces that can locally overcome the gravitational force. Though local accumulation of iron due to radiative levitation has successfully explained the pulsation properties of sdB stars (see e.g. Charpinet et al., 1996), in the case of β Cephei models, fully consistent calculations including radiative accelerations are still needed to validate the proposed solution. Steps forward in this line of work have recently been taken by Bourge (2007) and Bourge et al. (2007), where it was shown that for a $10 M_{\odot}$ model even though radiative forces are able to accumulate iron in the driving region, the theoretical modelling (especially the treatment of near-surface layers) still needs improvements to be quantitatively predictive. Moreover, as recently pointed out by Dziembowski (2007), the detailed calculations for B stars (though for models only up to $4 M_{\odot}$) by Seaton (1999) together with the results by Bourge (2007), tend to show that, if radiative forces are efficient enough to accumulate iron in the driving region, a significant Fe-enhancement would also be expected in the photosphere and should therefore be detectable. This is however currently not supported by detailed abundance analysis (see e.g. Morel et al., 2006), where the analyzed sample of β Cephei stars shows Fe abundances typical of B dwarfs in the solar-neighborhood.

It is clear that calculations of models including radiative accelerations, diffusion and possibly additional mixing processes (e.g. induced by rotation and wind) are needed to have a physically consistent picture of the outer layers of a β Cephei star. Even though these calculations will be extremely valuable, due to their large computational cost they will hardly be available in the near future for large

grids of models that are commonly needed to make seismic modelling of these stars. A qualitative effect of local iron enhancement on the excitation of pulsation modes can nonetheless be estimated by simple parametric approaches (provided that the parameters are calibrated on fully-consistent models).

As a first exploratory study, which needs further refinements and that we therefore only outline here, we have investigated the effect of local iron enhancement on the stability of SPB and β Cep stars in a grid of main-sequence models at different metallicities. We based our parametric description on Fe accumulation profiles as found in models of A-F stars with diffusion and radiative accelerations (Richard et al. 2001; see also Bourge & Alecian 2006; Bourge et al. 2007 for B stars). At each time step in the evolution we increase the Fe mass fraction in the chemical mixture, keeping Z fixed. The increase is described by a Gaussian function centred at $\log T \sim 5.2$, where this value is justified by calculations of radiative accelerations using the OP webserver¹. We then calculate the opacity by interpolating between several OPAL tables computed with different mass fractions of Fe in the chemical mixture. The behaviour in the stellar interior of the opacity and of the iron-enhancement profile resulting from this simple parametrisation are shown in Fig. 4.1 for a $12 M_{\odot}$ main-sequence model.

Concerning the effects on the excitation of pulsation modes, though the results clearly depend on the Fe accumulation rate, we find (see Fig. 4.2 and 4.3) that the SPB/ β Cep instability strips get wider in T_{eff} , higher frequency modes are excited in β Cep models and a larger number of β Cep models is found to be excited for $Z=0.01$. A further result of this simple study is shown in Fig. 4.3 in the case of $10 M_{\odot}$ models: even though iron accumulation modifies the properties of the driving region of the pulsation modes, leading e.g. to the excitation of higher overtones p modes, it does not significantly change the oscillation frequencies. This is reassuring as it suggests that the oscillation frequencies observed in β Cep stars can be used to infer properties of stellar interior even in cases where their excitation is not satisfactorily explained by standard models, due to a poor modelling of the near-surface regions.

While local iron accumulation remains a viable explanation for the observed discrepancies (provided that it becomes quantitatively supported by detailed calculations), in this Chapter we will analyze in more detail another source of uncertainty in our predictions of the excitation of B-type pulsation: the current uncertainties concerning the basic physical inputs adopted in standard models.

4.2.2 Different global metal mixtures

The recent re-analysis of solar spectrum by Asplund et al. (2005) (hereafter AGS05) including NLTE effect as well as tri-dimensional model atmosphere computations,

¹<http://vizier.u-strasbg.fr/topbase/op.html>

Figure 4.1: Behaviour of the opacity as a function of $\log(T)$ in the structure of a $12 M_{\odot}$ model computed with and without parametric Fe accumulation (respectively dashed and continuous lines). The behaviour of χ_{Fe} (the Fe mass fraction, normalized by the initial Fe abundance) is described by a dotted line. The flat χ_{Fe} profile at $\log T \sim 5.2$ is due to a convective zone appearing near the local maximum of the opacity.

Figure 4.2: Instability strips represented in a $\log T_{\text{eff}}\text{-log } P$ diagram. In each panel, the two regions of unstable modes represent β Cep- and SPB-type pulsations.

Figure 4.3: Frequencies of pulsation modes as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ for main-sequence models of a $10 M_{\odot}$ $Z=0.02$ star. Unstable modes are described by gray squares and large black dots when models are computed with and without parametric Fe accumulation respectively.

has led to a significant decrease of C, N and O solar abundances leading to a solar metallicity 30% smaller than the value provided by the “standard” GN93 mixture (Grevesse & Noels, 1993). The corresponding decrease in solar opacity ($\sim 20\%$) at the base of the convective envelope ruins the good agreement between the standard solar model and the seismic one. These new CNO abundances, however, agree with spectroscopic measurements in B-type stars, and solve the old discrepancy between a supermetallic Sun and the chemical composition of B-type stars and HII regions in the solar environment (Turck-Chièze et al., 2004; Cunha et al., 2006, and references therein). On the other hand, while the lower O abundance in AGS05 mixture decreases the opacity at the bottom of the convective envelope and increases the discrepancy between standard solar model and helioseismology, an iron mass fraction 25% larger in the new mixture with respect to GN93 one, will favorably affect the excitation of β Cep and SPB pulsation modes in early-type stars.

Among the different solutions suggested to recover the agreement between standard model and helioseismology, an enhancement of the Ne abundance by a factor ~ 3.5 with respect to the Asplund et al. (2005) value has been proposed by Antia & Basu (2005) and Bahcall et al. (2005). The increase of Ne would compensate for the opacity loss due to the O abundance drop. The problem is that Ne cannot be directly measured in the solar photosphere. Cunha et al. (2006) suggested that determining non-LTE Ne abundances in a sample of eleven B-stars members of the Orion association could help solving the problem of Ne abundance. The studied stars span an effective temperature range from 20000 K to 29000 K. The

result of this work is a Ne abundance in B-type stars 0.3 dex larger than in Asplund et al. (2005) mixture, but CNO in agreement with the new solar abundances.

In the following sections we consider models computed with the Asplund et al. (2005) metal mixture and a Ne abundance $\log A(\text{Ne}) = 8.11$ from Cunha et al. (2006) (AGS05+Ne), and compare results obtained with the “standard” GN93. The re-normalization of AGS05+Ne to keep the same Z results finally in an enhancement of $\sim 20\%$ in the iron and nickel mass fractions with respect to GN93. In Fig. 4.4 the dotted curves show the relative differences in the Rosseland mean opacity between GN93 and AGS05+Ne (for the same metal mass fraction $Z=0.02$) for the structure of a 4 and a $10 M_{\odot}$ models. The effect of the enhancement of Fe and Ni is to increase the height and the width of the Z-bump of the Rosseland mean opacity (κ).

Since the Ne increase proposed by Cunha et al. (2006) is still a matter of debate, it is worth recalling that the effect of considering the Asplund et al. (2005) metal mixture without the higher Neon abundance is to further increase the Fe relative mass fraction by $\sim 5\%$. In a $10 M_{\odot}$ model (and for a given value of Z) this induces a further increase of the opacity at $T \sim 2 \times 10^5$ K up to 6%, that only slightly modifies the outcome of the stability analysis presented here (see Sec. 4.5.3).

4.3 Opacities: OPAL versus OP

OP opacity tables have been recently updated including data for the inner-shell transitions, inter-combination lines and improvements in photoionization cross-sections (Seaton, 2005; Badnell et al., 2005). These changes result in an enhancement of κ at high density and temperatures, and an increase of $\sim 18\%$ of opacity in the Z-bump due to the new Fe atomic data. The new OP opacity tables are much closer to the OPAL ones than they were previously (Seaton et al., 1994). In particular, the differences at high temperature and high density have almost disappeared. Some differences remain, however, at low temperatures ($\log T < 5.5$): the OP Z-bump in κ presents a hot wing slightly larger than the OPAL one. The comparisons between OP and OPAL by Badnell et al. (2005) at fixed $\log R$ ($R = \rho/T_6^3$) show that for high densities the differences are of the order of 5–10%, but at low density ($\log R \sim -4$), differences up to 30% appear due to the differences in the high-temperature wing of the Z-bump.

The previous OP tables (Seaton et al., 1994) already presented a Z-bump in κ shifted by 15000–20000 K to higher temperatures compared with OPAL. The effect of this difference on the instability strip of β Cep and SPB stars was studied by Pamyatnykh (1999). In that study, however, OP and OPAL opacity tables had also small differences in heavy elements abundances: Ni 5% more abundant in OP than in OPAL, and Ne and Fe $\sim 2 - 3\%$ more abundant in OP.

Figure 4.4: Comparison between opacities computed with OPAL, OP and with different metal mixtures in the structure of a 4 and $10 M_{\odot}$ models on the ZAMS.

Ni and Fe are the main contributors to the Z-bump, and Ni contributes to the Z-bump in κ at higher temperatures than Fe (see e.g. Jeffery & Saio, 2006). In order to separate metal mixture effects from opacity calculation ones, we obtained OP opacity tables from the OP webserver for the same GN93 and AGS05+Ne metal mixture as OPAL. The abundances of the four elements that are not included in OP (P, Cl, K, Ti) are redistributed among the other 15 elements. Doing so, the abundance differences between OP and OPAL opacity table computation are at maximum 0.06%.

In Fig 4.4 we show the difference in opacity for the internal structure of two stellar models with the typical masses of an SPB ($4 M_{\odot}$) and a β Cep ($10 M_{\odot}$). We see that for the lower-mass model the opacity differences in the Z-bump region are of the order of 20%, and up to 50% for the $10 M_{\odot}$ model.

As we discussed in Sec. 2.3.3, another approximation is made when estimating stellar opacity: only a limited number of elements is included in the metal mixture (in both OPAL and OP calculations). The contribution to the opacity of elements heavier than Ni was estimated in Iglesias et al. (1995). The authors showed that for the $\rho - T$ conditions reached in the envelope of massive stars, neglecting the contribution of heavier elements, leads to a small but systematic underestimation up to $\sim 5\%$ of the opacity near the Z opacity bump for a Grevesse & Noels (1993) metal mixture and $Z = 0.02$.

4.4 Stellar models

The stellar models used in our analysis have been computed with the code CLES (Code Liégeois d'Evolution Stellaire, Scuflaire et al. 2007b). The main physical inputs are: OPAL2001 equation of state (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002) and Caughlan & Fowler (1988) nuclear reaction rates with Formicola et al. (2004) for the $^{14}\text{N}(p,\gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ cross-section. Convective transport is treated by using the classical Mixing Length Theory of convection (Böhm-Vitense, 1958), and a convective overshooting parameter $\alpha_{\text{OV}} = 0.2$ was assumed in all the models. For the chemical composition we have considered: GN93 and AGS05+ $\log A(\text{Ne}) = 8.11$. We have computed models with: *i*) OPAL opacity tables with GN93 and with *ii*) AGS05+Ne chemical composition, then models with *iii*) OP opacity tables assuming GN93 and *iv*) AGS05+Ne mixtures. We have also included for completeness calculations performed using OP opacities and AGS05 metal mixture, without the increased Ne abundance proposed by Cunha et al. (2006). All the opacity tables are completed at $\log T < 4.1$ with the corresponding GN93 and AGS05 low temperature tables by Ferguson et al. (2005). The masses considered span from 2.5 to 18 M_{\odot} , and the chemical composition considered are: $X=0.70$ for the hydrogen mass fraction and three different metal mass fractions, $Z=0.02, 0.01$ and 0.005 . For all the models the evolution was followed from the Pre Main Sequence.

4.5 Stability analysis

Since oscillations in β Cep and SPB stars are driven by the κ -mechanism acting in the Z opacity bump, the location of the instability strip in the HR diagram and the frequency of the excited modes are determined by the properties of the metal opacity bump that, as previously described, can significantly be affected by the choice of the opacity tables (OP-OPAL) and of the metal mixture (GN93-AGS05+Ne).

We perform stability analyses of main-sequence models from our grid using the non-adiabatic code MAD (Dupret et al., 2003). We present our results (Figs. 4.5-4.13) by means of three types of plots: frequency- T_{eff} diagram showing pulsation modes of a 10 M_{\odot} model on the main sequence, instability strips in the HR diagram, and Period- T_{eff} diagrams showing excited modes for different combinations of opacity tables and metallicity (Fig. 4.9) and giving information on how the instability domains depend on the degree ℓ of the modes (Fig. 4.13).

4.5.1 Effects of the metal mixture

The Fe-mass fraction enhancement in the AGS05+Ne mixture, compared with GN93, has the main effect of extending towards higher overtones the range of excited frequencies. Fig. 4.6 shows the $\ell = 0, 1$ and 2 excited p-modes for 10 M_{\odot}

Figure 4.5: Frequencies of pulsation modes as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ for main-sequence models of a $10 M_{\odot}$ $Z=0.02$ star computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{\text{OV}} = 0.2$) and $X=0.7$. Unstable modes are described by large black dots and gray squares when models are computed, respectively, with OPAL-GN93 and OP-GN93 opacity tables. Lower panels represent high-order g-modes.

Figure 4.6: As in Fig. 4.5 but comparing models computed with OPAL-GN93 and OPAL-AGS05+Ne opacity tables.

main sequence models calculated with OPAL opacity tables for the two different metal mixtures.

While the different profile of κ in OP and OPAL computations modifies the blue border of the instability strips, a larger Fe-mass fraction in the metal mixture provides slightly wider instability bands, and the relative effect increases as the metallicity decreases (see Fig. 4.11 and panels c and d of Fig. 4.9). Thus, *the number of β Cep pulsators expected with AGS05+Ne is more than three times larger than with GN93 for $Z=0.01$.*

For completeness, we discuss the effect on the excitation of considering models computed with OP and the AGS05 metal mixture without the Ne abundance increase proposed by Cunha et al. (2006). As anticipated in Sec. 4.2, a further $\sim 5\%$ increase in the Fe relative mass fraction in the metal mixture only slightly increases the number of unstable modes in $Z=0.02$ models. However, in models computed with a lower metallicity ($Z=0.01$, see Fig. 4.8) the effect becomes more relevant.

Figure 4.7: As in Fig. 4.5 but comparing models computed with OPAL-GN93 and OP-AGS05+Ne opacity tables.

4.5.2 Effects of OP vs. OPAL

In models with the new OP opacity tables, the driving region, that is, the region where $\kappa_T = (\partial \log \kappa / \partial \log T)_\rho$ increases outwards, is found deeper in the star with respect to the models computed with OPAL. As a consequence, we expect hotter B-type pulsators with OP models compared to OPAL ones.

Let us first consider models with $Z=0.02$. Fig. 4.5 shows different effects of OP and OPAL on the p-modes excitation (upper panels) and on the high-order g-modes excitation (lower panels) for main sequence models of a $10 M_\odot$ star with GN93 metal mixture. For p-modes (or low-order g-modes), we see that in the common instability region, OPAL and OP predict the same excited modes, and their frequencies are not affected by opacity differences. There is, however, a significant effect on the hottest unstable models: while OPAL models with excited radial modes are expected only for $X_c < 0.5$, ZAMS OP models show excited $\ell = 0$ modes.

In the case of a $10 M_\odot$ star, the differences between OP and OPAL are even more pronounced for high-order g-modes: there are many more excited modes in OP models than in the OPAL ones. For instance, the $10 M_\odot$ OP model with $X_c = 0.2$ presents excited modes of $\ell = 2$ going from g_{16} to g_{21} , and the TAMS model has $\ell = 1$, $g_{31}-g_{43}$ and $\ell = 2$, $g_{28}-g_{53}$ excited. In OPAL models, instead,

Figure 4.8: As in Fig. 4.5 but comparing models computed with OP-AGS05+Ne and OP-AGS05 opacity tables and $Z=0.01$.

no $\ell = 1$ high-order g-mode is excited; the first excited $\ell = 2$ g-modes appear at $X_c = 0.1$, and in the TAMS model the order of the excited g-modes goes from $n = 34$ to $n = 48$. The T_{eff} domain for which we find excited SPB-modes is therefore ~ 3000 K larger than for OPAL models. As a consequence, the number of expected hybrid β Cep–SPB objects is also larger for OP models (see right panels in Fig. 4.5 and Fig 4.9a). These results are similar to those obtained by Pamyatnykh (1999) with the previous OP opacity tables. In fact, the higher Fe and Ni abundances in the original OP mixture are balanced now by a 18% higher opacity at the Z-bump. Pamyatnykh (1999) noted that the shift of the Z-bump towards higher temperatures leads to an increase of the β Cephei and SPB instability domains towards higher T_{eff} and luminosity with respect to OPAL models. These results, however, have not been taken into consideration to explain the high order g-modes detected in the β Cep stars 12 Lac and ν Eri.

OP opacities also predict a hotter blue border of the β Cep instability strip (see Fig.4.10). This is particularly relevant in the high-mass domain of the grid, where models present excited modes already on the ZAMS, displacing the hot border of instability strips by ~ 2500 K. The instability strips in a Period- T_{eff} diagram for OP and OPAL models, with GN93 mixture and metallicity $Z=0.02$ and $Z=0.01$, are shown in Fig. 4.9 (panels a and b). We notice that the impact of the different

Figure 4.9: Instability strips represented in a $\log T_{\text{eff}}-P$ diagram. In each panel, the two regions of unstable modes represent β Cep- and SPB-type pulsations. The models are computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{\text{OV}}=0.2$), $X=0.7$ and have masses in the range $2.5-18 M_{\odot}$. In the stability analysis we considered only main-sequence models.

Figure 4.10: Instability strips of β Cep- and SPB-type pulsations in the HR diagram for $Z=0.02$. Evolutionary tracks are represented by dotted lines. The models are computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{OV}=0.2$), $X=0.7$ and have masses in the range $2.5\text{--}18 M_{\odot}$.

OP–OPAL opacities is more important for low metallicity: for $Z=0.01$, for instance, the number of β Cep pulsators predicted with OP is more than twice larger than estimated from OPAL stellar models.

4.5.3 Combined effects

If we consider the combined effect of OP opacities and AGS05+Ne metal mixture, we see that the large difference in κ (compared to OPAL with GN93) described in Fig. 4.4 is reflected in wider instability strips, in the excitation of higher overtones

Figure 4.11: Same as Fig. 4.10 but for $Z=0.01$, $X=0.7$.

Figure 4.12: Same as Fig. 4.10 but for $Z=0.005$, $X=0.7$

in β Cep models and in a significantly larger number of β Cep pulsators for $Z=0.01$ (see Fig. 4.9, panel e and f).

In the Period- T_{eff} diagrams shown in Fig. 4.13 we present the comparison between the results obtained with OPAL-GN93 and OP-AGS05+Ne for the whole range of masses considered, and show how the location of the instability domains depends on the degree ℓ . In particular, as illustrated in Fig. 4.11 and 4.13, while OPAL-GN93 models with $Z=0.01$ are hardly able to produce a narrow instability strip at the end of MS with excited modes only for $\ell > 1$, the OP-AGS05+Ne models present $\ell=0-3$ excited modes already for an evolutionary state corresponding to $X_c \simeq 0.3$. Similar effects are found in the excitation of modes in a $10 M_{\odot}$ $Z=0.02$ model (see Fig. 4.7).

Finally, computations for the lowest metallicity considered ($Z=0.005$) show that none of the different OP/OPAL and GN93/AGS05+Ne evolutionary tracks for masses up to $18 M_{\odot}$ predicts β Cep pulsators, whereas we find SPB-type modes excited when considering OP or AGS05+Ne metal mixture, but not with OPAL and GN93 (see Fig. 4.12).

4.6 Summary

We have shown that the current uncertainties on opacity calculations, and on the solar metal mixture adopted in standard stellar models, have a considerable effect on the excitation of pulsations in β Cep and SPB stars. Compared to models computed with OPAL opacities and GN93 metal mixture, we find that:

- with OP opacities high-order g-modes are predicted to be excited in hotter stars,
- higher overtones are excited if the AGS05+Ne (or AGS05) metal mixture is considered,
- for low metallicities, such as $Z=0.01$, a larger number of models with excited modes is also found.

These findings help solving, at least partly, the discrepancies between theoretical predictions and observations of β Cep in low-metallicity environments and of a large domain of excited modes detected in some β Cep and hybrid SPB- β Cep pulsators.

First encouraging results have recently been obtained in the modelling of the β Cep star θ Ophiuchi (Briquet et al., 2007b), where OP opacities with AGS05+Ne metal mixture successfully explain the excitation of the observed pulsation modes, whereas the commonly adopted OPAL+GN93 fail. A similar case is that of the β Cep HD 180642 (a CoRoT primary target) where a preliminary modelling shows that the excitation of the dominant observed mode (identified as a radial mode) can

Figure 4.13: Instability strips represented in a $\log T_{\text{eff}}-P$ diagram for $Z=0.02$, 0.01 and different degree ℓ . In each panel, the two regions of unstable modes represent β Cep- and SPB-type pulsations. The models are computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{\text{OV}}=0.2$), $X=0.7$ and have masses in the range $2.5-18 M_{\odot}$. In the stability analysis we considered only main-sequence models.

be recovered when using OP-AGS05+Ne opacities (see Aerts et al. 2007). However, thorough analysis including the modelling of the β Cephei stars ν Eri and 12 Lac are still needed to ascertain if the discrepancies between “standard” models and observations can be explained adopting the new OP opacities and AGS05 metal mixture.

5

Probing the properties of stellar cores
through g modes

5.1 Introduction

In main sequence stars the periods of gravity modes are sensitive probes of stellar cores and, in particular, of the chemical composition gradient that develops near the outer edge of the convective core. In this Chapter we investigate how the frequencies of g modes depend on the detailed properties of the chemical composition gradient that develops near the core of main-sequence stars and, therefore, on the transport processes that are able to modify the μ profile in the central regions.

We shall first analyze, by means of analytical approximations, the properties of high-order gravity modes; in a second step we discuss the case of low-order g modes and modes of mixed p and g character, focusing on how various mixing processes acting near the core affect differently the oscillation spectra.

The signatures of chemical stratifications in high-order gravity modes have been extensively investigated theoretically, and then observed, in pulsating white dwarfs (see e.g. Kawaler, 1995, for a review). The influence of chemical composition gradients on g-modes in main sequence stars has been partly addressed and suggested in two farsighted works by Berthomieu & Provost (1988) and Dziembowski et al. (1993). Inspired by these works and following the approach of Berthomieu & Provost (1988) and Brassard et al. (1992), we study the properties of high-order, low-degree gravity modes in main sequence stellar models.

As we described in Sec. 3.8, *high-order gravity modes* are observed in two classes of main-sequence stars: γ Doradus and Slowly Pulsating B stars. The seismic modelling of these classes of pulsators is a formidable task to undertake. The frequencies of high-order g modes are in fact closely spaced and can be severely perturbed by the effects of rotation (see e.g. Dintrans & Rieutord, 2000; Suárez et al., 2005). Nonetheless, the high scientific interest of these classes of pulsators has driven efforts in both the observational and theoretical domain. Besides systematic photometric and spectroscopic ground-based surveys carried out on γ Dor (see Mathias et al., 2004) and SPB stars (see De Cat & Aerts, 2002), the long and uninterrupted photometric observations planned with CoRoT (Baglin et al., 2006; Mathias et al., 2006) will allow to significantly increase the number and accuracy of the observed frequencies. On the theoretical side, as suggested by Suárez et al. (2005) in the case of γ Dor stars, a seismic analysis becomes feasible for slowly rotating targets. In these favorable cases the first-order asymptotic approximation (Tassoul, 1980) can be used as a tool to derive the buoyancy radius of the star (see Moya et al., 2005) from the observed frequencies. Nevertheless, the g-mode spectra of these stars contain much more information on the internal structure of the star. In this chapter we describe in detail the information content carried by the periods of high-order g modes, and show that the effect of chemical composition gradients can be easily included as a refinement of the asymptotic approximation of Tassoul (1980).

As previously mentioned, the second part of this Chapter is dedicated to the properties of *gravity modes of low order and of modes of mixed p and g character*. Among the different classes of main-sequence pulsating stars, low-order gravity modes and mixed-modes are found to be excited in β Cephei and δ Scuti stars (see Sec. 3.8). Moreover, in the case of stars evolving as sub-giants, mixed modes are also expected in the frequency domain typical of solar-like oscillations.

In the literature we find several analyses of the properties of such modes. It has been shown, for instance, that the detection of the frequency of a mixed mode would allow the determination of the overshooting parameter in δ Scuti stars (see e.g. Pamyatnykh, 1999; Michel et al., 1993; Audard et al., 1995). A similar inference is also possible in β Cep stars, where the observed oscillation frequencies are now used to place constraints on extra-mixing at the border of the convective core (see e.g. Aerts et al., 2003; Pamyatnykh et al., 2004; Mazumdar et al., 2006; Briquet et al., 2007a). Finally, as discussed e.g. in Di Mauro et al. (2004) and Miglio et al. (2007), the detection of mixed modes in the spectrum of stars showing solar-like oscillations would allow to determine the evolutionary state of the star and, therefore to discriminate among theoretical models computed with different values of the overshooting parameter (see also Chap. 7). In fact, in stars that are still in the core-hydrogen burning phase, the frequencies of gravity modes are not high enough to enter the domain of solar-like oscillations, whereas this is no longer the case in more evolved models, where mixed modes can severely perturb the solar-like oscillation spectrum.

In our work we discuss if physically different mixing processes acting near the core leave distinguishable signatures in the frequencies of low-order g and mixed modes. In particular, we investigate the effects of rotationally induced turbulent mixing on the chemical composition gradient and then on the oscillation frequencies, and compare it to the effects of overshooting that have been extensively studied in the literature.

After an introduction to the properties of gravity modes in main-sequence stars (Sec.5.2), we present in Sec. 5.3 the analytical approximation of high-order g-mode frequencies that will be used in the subsequent sections. In Sec. 5.4 we describe the properties of numerically computed g-mode frequencies in main-sequence stars in the mass domain 1-10 M_{\odot} . The effect on high-order gravity modes of adding extra-mixing at the edge of the convective core (rotationally induced turbulence, overshooting, diffusion) is investigated in Sec. 5.4.2. In Sec. 5.5 we estimate to what extent the effects of rotation and of current observational limitations affect asteroseismology of main sequence high-order g modes pulsators. Sec. 5.6 is dedicated to the effects of turbulent mixing near the core on low-order gravity modes and modes of mixed p- and g- character. A summary is finally given in Sec. 5.7.

5.2 The properties of trapped g modes

As it is well known, the period spectrum of gravity modes is determined by the spatial distribution of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (N) which is defined as:

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dr} \right). \quad (5.1)$$

N can be approximated, assuming the ideal gas law for a fully-ionized gas, as:

$$N^2 \simeq \frac{g^2 \rho}{p} (\nabla_{\text{ad}} - \nabla + \nabla_{\mu}), \quad (5.2)$$

where

$$\nabla = \frac{d \ln T}{d \ln p}, \quad \nabla_{\text{ad}} = \left(\frac{\partial \ln T}{\partial \ln p} \right)_{\text{ad}} \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla_{\mu} = \frac{d \ln \mu}{d \ln p}. \quad (5.3)$$

The term ∇_{μ} gives the explicit contribution of a change of chemical composition to N . The first order asymptotic approximation developed by Tassoul (1980) shows that, in the case of a model that consists of an inner convective core and an outer radiative envelope (we refer to the work by Tassoul, 1980, for a complete analysis of other possible cases), the periods of low-degree, high-order g modes (where $N^2 \gg \omega^2$) are given by:

$$P_k = \frac{\pi^2}{L \int_{x_0}^1 \frac{|N|}{x} dx} (2k + n_e) \quad (5.4)$$

where $L = [\ell(\ell+1)]^{1/2}$ (with ℓ the mode degree), n_e the effective polytropic index of the surface layer, x the normalized radius and x_0 corresponds to the boundary of the convective core. In order to avoid confusion with n_e , the radial order of g modes is represented by k .

Following Eq. 5.4, the periods are asymptotically equally spaced in k and the spacing decreases with increasing L . It is therefore natural to introduce, in analogy to the large frequency separation of p modes, the *period spacing* of gravity modes, defined as:

$$\Delta P = P_{k+1} - P_k. \quad (5.5)$$

In the following sections we will show that deviations from a constant ΔP contain information on the chemical composition gradient left by a convective core evolving on the main sequence.

We consider as a first example two models of a $6 M_{\odot}$ star evolving on the main-sequence. The behaviour of N and of the chemical composition profile is represented in Fig. 5.1. The convective core is fully mixed and, therefore, the composition is uniform ($\nabla_{\mu} = 0$). However, in stars in this mass range, the convective core shrinks during the evolution, leaving behind a steep gradient in the

Figure 5.1: *Upper panel:* Hydrogen abundance in the core of $6 M_{\odot}$ models on the main sequence. $X_c \simeq 0.5$ (dotted line) and at $X_c \simeq 0.3$ (dashed line). The convective core recedes during the evolution and leaves behind a chemical composition gradient. *Lower panel:* Buoyancy frequency N as a function of the normalized mass.

Figure 5.2: $\langle x \rangle$ for $\ell = 1$ modes in $6 M_{\odot}$ models on the main sequence at two different points in the evolution: $X_c \simeq 0.5$ (dotted lines) and at $X_c \simeq 0.3$ (dashed line). Modes of different radial order are periodically trapped in the region of the chemical composition gradient. Trapped modes are marked with open symbols.

Figure 5.3: We consider a $6 M_{\odot}$ model with $X_c \simeq 0.5$. *Upper panel:* N against fractional radius. *Central panel:* Horizontal component of the displacement for three $\ell = 1$ gravity modes of radial order 18 (dotted line), 20 (continuous line) and 22 (dashed line). The eigenfunction corresponding to $k = 20$ is partly trapped in the region of mean molecular weight where the sharp variation of N is located. *Lower panel:* As in the central panel, this time the radial displacement is shown. The eigenfunctions corresponding to different modes are normalized to have the same total pulsation energy.

Figure 5.4: Period spacing for the same $6 M_{\odot}$ models as in Fig. 5.2. The periods of the components (in terms of k) are approximately 7 and 3. Horizontal dotted lines represent constant period spacing predicted by the asymptotic approximation (Eq. 5.4).

hydrogen abundance X . This causes a sharp peak in ∇_μ and in N : does this feature leave a clear signature in the properties of g-modes?

This question was addressed by Brassard et al. (1991) while studying the seismic effects of compositional layering in white-dwarfs. The authors found that a sharp feature in the buoyancy frequency could lead to a resonance condition that may trap modes in different regions of the model.

A first indicator of such a trapping is the behaviour of $\langle x \rangle$ defined by:

$$\langle x \rangle = \frac{\int_0^1 x |\delta \mathbf{r}|^2 dm}{\int_0^1 |\delta \mathbf{r}|^2 dm} \quad (5.6)$$

where $x = r/R$ and $\delta \mathbf{r}$ is the total displacement vector. As shown in Fig. 5.2 modes of different radial order k are *periodically confined* closer to the center of the star.

In Fig. 5.3 we show the behaviour of the eigenfunctions for modes of radial orders around a trapped mode: the partly trapped mode has, compared to “neighbour” modes, a larger amplitude in the region of mean molecular weight gradient.

In white dwarfs it has been theoretically predicted and observed (see, for instance, the recent work of Metcalfe et al., 2003) that the period spacing $\Delta P(k) = P_{k+1} - P_k$ is not constant, contrary to what is predicted by the first order asymptotic approximation of gravity modes. This has been interpreted as the signature of chemical composition gradients in the envelope and in the core of the star. In analogy with the case of white dwarfs, in models with a convective core, we expect the formation of a *nonuniform period distribution*; this is in fact the case as is presented in Fig. 5.4. The period spacing presents clear deviations from the uniformity that would be expected in a model without sharp variations in N . How these deviations are related to the characteristics of the chemical composition gradients will be studied in the following sections.

5.3 Approximated analytical expression of g-modes period spacing

In this section we derive two approximated expressions that relate deviations from a uniform period distribution to the characteristics of the μ -gradient region. These simplified expressions could also represent a useful tool to give a direct interpretation of an observed period spectrum. Though a first description of these approximated expressions was outlined in Miglio (2006) and Miglio et al. (2006), we here present a more detailed analysis.

5.3.1 Variational principle

A first and simple approach to the problem is to make use of the variational principle for adiabatic stellar oscillations (see e.g. Unno et al., 1989a). The effect of a sharp feature in the model (a chemical composition gradient, for instance) can be estimated from the periodic signature in δP , defined as the difference between the periods of the star showing such a sharp variation and the periods of an otherwise fictitious smooth model.

We consider a model with a radiative envelope and a convective core whose boundary is located at a normalized radius x_0 . N_- and N_+ are the values of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency at the outer and inner border of the μ -gradient region. We define $\alpha = \left(\frac{N_+}{N_-}\right)^{1/2}$ with $N_+ \leq N_-$. Then $\alpha = 1$ describes the smooth model and $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ a sharp discontinuity in N .

To obtain a first estimate of δP , we adopt (following the approach by Montgomery et al., 2003) the Cowling approximation, that reduces the differential equations of stellar adiabatic oscillations to a system of the second order. Furthermore, since we deal with high-order gravity modes, the eigenfunctions are well described by their JWKB approximation (see e.g. Gough, 1993). We can therefore express δP as:

$$\frac{\delta P_k}{P} = 2\Pi_0 \int_0^{\Pi_0^{-1}} \left(\frac{\delta N}{N}\right) \cos(2LP_k\Pi_x^{-1} + \phi) d\Pi_x^{-1} \quad (5.7)$$

where ϕ is a phase constant, $L = [\ell(\ell+1)]^{1/2}$, the local buoyancy radius is defined as:

$$\Pi_x^{-1} = \int_{x_0}^x \frac{|N|}{x'} dx', \quad (5.8)$$

and the total buoyancy radius as

$$\Pi_0^{-1} = \int_{x_0}^1 \frac{|N|}{x'} dx'. \quad (5.9)$$

The buoyancy radius of the discontinuity is then:

$$\Pi_\mu^{-1} = \int_{x_0}^{x_\mu} \frac{|N|}{x'} dx'. \quad (5.10)$$

We model the sharp feature in $\frac{\delta N}{N}$ located at $x = x_\mu$ as:

$$\frac{\delta N}{N} = \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} H(x_\mu - x), \quad (5.11)$$

where $H(x)$ is the step function (see left panel of Fig. 5.5).

Retaining only periodic terms in δP and integrating by parts we obtain:

$$\delta P_k \propto \frac{\Pi_0}{L} \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} \cos\left(2 \frac{L P_k}{\Pi_\mu} + \phi\right). \quad (5.12)$$

Figure 5.5: *Left:* We model the sharp variation of N at $x = x_\mu$ by means of Eq. (5.11) for different values of α : $\alpha_1^2 = 0.5$ (continuous line), $\alpha_2^2 = 0.3$ (dashed line). *Right:* A smoother variation of N is modeled following Eq. (5.15).

For small δP we can substitute the asymptotic approximation for g-modes periods derived by Tassoul (1980) in the expression above:

$$P_k = \pi^2 \frac{\Pi_0}{L} (2k + \phi') ,$$

where ϕ' is a phase constant, and find

$$\delta P_k \propto \frac{\Pi_0}{L} \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} \cos \left(2\pi \frac{\Pi_0}{\Pi_\mu} k + \phi'' \right) . \quad (5.13)$$

From this simple approach we derive that the signature of a sharp feature in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency is a *sinusoidal component in the periods of oscillations*, and therefore in the period spacing, with a periodicity in terms of the radial order k given by

$$\Delta k \simeq \frac{\Pi_\mu}{\Pi_0} . \quad (5.14)$$

The amplitude of this sinusoidal component is proportional to the sharpness of the variation in N and does not depend on the order of the mode k .

Such a simple approach allows us to easily test the effect of having a less sharp “glitch” in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. We model δN (Fig. 5.5, right panel) as a ramp function instead of a step function:

$$\frac{\delta N}{N} = \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} \frac{(x_\mu - x)}{x_\mu - x_0} H(x_\mu - x) . \quad (5.15)$$

In this case integration by parts leads to a sinusoidal component in δP_k whose amplitude is modulated by a factor $1/P_k$ and therefore decreases with increasing k , i.e.

$$\delta P_k \propto \frac{1}{P_k} \frac{\Pi_0}{L} \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2} \frac{1}{\Pi_\mu^{-1}} \cos \left(2\pi \frac{\Pi_0}{\Pi_\mu} k + \phi' \right). \quad (5.16)$$

The information contained in the amplitude of the sinusoidal component, as will be presented in Section 5.4.2, is potentially very interesting. It reflects the different characteristics of the chemical composition gradient resulting, for example, from a different treatment of the mixing process in convective cores, from considering microscopic diffusion or rotationally induced mixing in the models.

Eq. (5.13) was derived by means of a first order perturbation of the periods, neglecting changes in the eigenfunctions. This approximation is valid in the case of small variations relative to a smooth model, therefore it becomes questionable as the change of N at the edge of the convective core becomes large. A more accurate approximation is presented in the following section.

5.3.2 Considering the effects of the μ gradient on the eigenfunctions

We present in this Section a description of mode trapping, considering the change in the eigenfunctions due to a sharp feature in N . As a second step we derive the effects on the periods of g-modes.

Brassard et al. (1992) studied the problem of mode trapping in μ -gradient regions inside white dwarfs. In this section we proceed as Brassard et al. (1992), applying the asymptotic theory as developed in Tassoul (1980) to the typical structure of an intermediate mass star on the main sequence.

Tassoul (1980), assuming the Cowling approximation, provided asymptotic solutions for the propagation of high-order g-modes in convective and radiative regions, located in different parts of the star. In order to generalize the expression for these solutions, she introduced two functions S_1 and S_2 , related to the radial displacement (ξ_r) and pressure perturbation (p') as follows:

$$\sigma^2 \xi_r = \rho^{-1/2} x^{-2} |\phi|^{-1/4} S_1 \quad (5.17)$$

and

$$\sigma \ell(\ell + 1) p' / \rho = \rho^{-1/2} |\phi|^{1/4} S_2, \quad (5.18)$$

where x is the normalized radius and

$$\phi = \frac{\ell(\ell + 1) N^2}{x^2}. \quad (5.19)$$

The expressions for S_1 , S_2 for different propagation regions are given in the equations [T79] to [T97]¹.

¹From now on [Ti] indicates equation number i in the paper by Tassoul (1980).

The only difference from the derivation of Brassard et al. (1992), who assumed an entirely radiative model, is that here we consider a model that consists of a convective core and a radiative envelope. The solutions should then be described by [T80] close to the centre, [T96] in the convective core (x_0), [T97] in the radiative region with [T82] close to the surface (where the structure of the surface layers of the model is described by an effective polytropic index n_e).

Now, as explained in Fig. 5.6, we assume that in the radiative zone at $x = x_\mu$ there is a sharp variation of N due to a μ gradient and, as in the previous section, we model it as a discontinuity weighted by α , where $\alpha = (N_+/N_-)^{1/2}$ (see Eq. 5.11).

We define $\lambda = \sigma^{-1}$,

$$v_0(x) = L \int_x^1 \frac{|N|}{x'} dx' = L (\Pi_0^{-1} - \Pi_x^{-1})$$

$$\text{and } v_1(x) = L \int_{x_0}^x \frac{|N|}{x'} dx' = L \Pi_x^{-1}.$$

For large values of λv_0 and λv_1 , we can write the eigenfunctions in the radiative region above the discontinuity at x_μ as:

$$S_{1a} \propto k_o \sin(A) \quad \text{and} \quad S_{2a} \propto -k_o \cos(A), \quad (5.20)$$

and in the $\nabla\mu$ region below the discontinuity we have:

$$S_{1b} \propto k_1 \cos(B) \quad \text{and} \quad S_{2b} \propto -k_1 \sin(B), \quad (5.21)$$

where

$$A = \lambda v_0(x) - n_e \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{4}, \quad B = \lambda v_1(x) - \frac{\pi}{4}, \quad (5.22)$$

and k_0 and k_1 are arbitrary constants. Note that A and B are functions of x .

The eigenfrequencies are now obtained by matching continuously the individual solutions in their common domain of validity. In particular, imposing the continuity of p' and ξ_r at the location of the discontinuity in N , we obtain the following conditions (as in Brassard et al., 1992):

$$S_1^+ = \alpha S_1^- \quad (5.23)$$

$$S_2^+ \alpha = S_2^- \quad (5.24)$$

where $S_{1,2}$ is evaluated above ($S_{1,2}^+$) and below ($S_{1,2}^-$) $x = x_\mu$.

This finally leads to a condition on the eigenfrequencies $1/\lambda$:

$$\cos(A+B) = \frac{1-\alpha^2}{1+\alpha^2} \cos(A-B), \quad (5.25)$$

Figure 5.6: A schematic view of the simplified model we consider. The radiative region outside the convective core ($x > x_0$) is divided in two zones: one below and the other above the discontinuity in N located at $x = x_\mu$. In each of these regions we consider the asymptotic expressions for the eigenfunctions that are then joined continuously at $x = x_\mu$.

With A and B (Eq. 5.22) evaluated at $x = x_\mu$, this condition can also be explicitly written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos\left(\lambda\frac{L}{\Pi_0} - \frac{n_e\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \\ & = \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{1 + \alpha^2} \cos\left(\lambda L \left[\frac{1}{\Pi_0} - \frac{2}{\Pi_\mu}\right] - \frac{n_e\pi}{2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.26)$$

5.3.2.1 Further approximations

A first extreme case for Eq. (5.26) is that corresponding to $\alpha = 1$, i.e. no discontinuities in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. In this case Eq. (5.25) immediately leads to the condition $\cos(A + B) = 0$ and therefore to the uniformly spaced period spectrum predicted by Tassoul's first order approximation:

$$P_k = \pi^2 \frac{\Pi_0}{L} (2k + n_e) \quad (5.27)$$

Another extreme situation is $\alpha \rightarrow 0$: in this case N is so large in the μ -gradient region that all the modes are trapped there; the periods of “perfectly trapped” modes are then:

$$P_n = \left(n + \frac{1}{4}\right) 2\pi^2 \frac{\Pi_\mu}{L} \quad (5.28)$$

where $n = (1, 2, 3, \dots)$.

The interval (in terms of radial order k) Δk between two consecutive trapped modes ($\Delta n = 1$) can be obtained combining Eq. (5.27) and Eq. (5.28) (see also Brassard et al., 1992), and it is roughly given by:

$$\Delta k \simeq \frac{\Pi_\mu}{\Pi_0}, \quad (5.29)$$

which corresponds with Eq. (5.14) obtained in the previous section.

We choose the $6 M_\odot$ models considered in Sec. 5.2 to compare the g-mode period spacings predicted by the equations (5.14) and (5.26) with the results obtained from the frequencies computed with an adiabatic oscillation code.

Equation (5.14) relates the period of the oscillatory component in the period spacing ΔP to the location of the sharp variation in N . In Fig. 5.4 the periods (in terms of k) of the components are approximately 7 and 3 for models with $X_c = 0.5$ and 0.3. Following Eq. (5.14) these periods should correspond to a location of the discontinuity (expressed as $\Pi_0/\Pi_\mu \simeq k^{-1}$) at 0.14 and 0.3: as shown in Fig. 5.7, these estimates describe very accurately the locations of the sharp variation of N in the models.

Numerical solutions of Eq. (5.26), found using a bracketing-bisection method (see Press et al., 1992), are shown in Fig. 5.8. As it is clearly visible when comparing Fig. 5.8 and Fig. 5.4, we find that the solutions of Eq. (5.26) better represent

Figure 5.7: The Brunt-Väisälä frequency versus Π_0/Π_r for $6 M_\odot$ models with $X_c \simeq 0.5$ (dotted line) and $X_c \simeq 0.3$ (dashed line).

Figure 5.8: Period spacing $\Delta P = P_{k+1} - P_k$ calculated from numerical solutions of Eq. (5.26). All solutions are calculated for $\ell = 1$ modes and $\Pi_0 = 639$ s. *Upper panel:* we fixed the value of Π_0/Π_μ to 0.15 and we vary α : $\alpha = 0.35$ (continuous line), $\alpha = 0.75$ (dashed line) and $\alpha = 1$ (dotted line). *Lower panel:* we fixed the value of α to 0.35 and we vary the value of Π_0/Π_μ : $\Pi_0/\Pi_\mu = 0.15$ (continuous line), 0.225 (dashed line) and 0.1 (dotted line).

the properties of the oscillatory features in the period spacing that are otherwise predicted to be pure sinusoids by Eq. (5.13).

In the following section we extend to a wider range of main-sequence models the analysis that we have presented here for a $6 M_\odot$ model.

5.4 Application to stellar models

The occurrence of a sharp chemical composition gradient in the central region of a star is determined by the appearance of convection in the core and by the displacement of the convective core boundary during the main sequence. For a given chemical composition, and if no non-standard transport process is included in the modeling, the transition from radiative to convective energy transport, as well as the shape of the μ gradients in the central stellar region, are determined by the mass of the model. On the other hand, additional mixing processes may alter the evolution of the convective core and the detailed properties of the chemical composition profile.

As shown in the previous section, the features of periodic signals in the period

spacing of high order g-modes can provide detailed information on the convective core and on the mixing-processes able to change the μ gradients generated during the stellar evolution.

In this section, we present a survey of the properties of adiabatic $\ell = 1$ high order g-modes in main-sequence stars with masses from 1 to 10 M_{\odot} , and for four different evolutionary stages corresponding to a central hydrogen mass fraction X_c of 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 and 0.1. All these model were computed with the same initial chemical composition $(X_0, Z_0) = (0.70, 0.02)$. The adiabatic oscillation frequencies were computed with LOSC (Scuflaire et al., 2007a).

We first study how the properties of high order gravity modes depend on the mass and the evolutionary stage of the model (Sec. 5.4.1). In a second step we evaluate the effects of including extra-mixing such as overshooting, diffusion and turbulent mixing (Sec. 5.4.2). The behaviour of modes with different ℓ will be briefly addressed in Sec. 5.4.3.

5.4.1 Convective core evolution: stellar mass dependence

In our analysis of the signatures of the μ gradients on g-modes, we consider three stellar mass domains: *i*) $M < M_{Lcc}$, with M_{Lcc} being the minimum mass required to keep a convective core during the main sequence; *ii*) $M_{Lcc} \leq M \leq M_{gc}$, for which the mass of the convective core increases during part of the main sequence; and *iii*) $M > M_{gc}$ for which the convective core recedes as the star evolves. The situations described here above are presented in Fig. 5.9, where the size in mass of the convective core is shown as a function of the central hydrogen abundance (and therefore of the age) of the star. The exact values of M_{Lcc} and $M > M_{gc}$ depend on the chemical composition and, as we shall see below, on extra-mixing processes.

5.4.1.1 Models with a radiative core

As a first example we consider the evolution of the period spacing along the main sequence in models without a convective core, e.g. in a 1 M_{\odot} star. The behaviour is substantially different from higher mass models: ΔP , as shown in Fig. 5.10, considerably decreases during the main sequence: this can easily be understood recalling the first order asymptotic expression for the mean period spacing. The increase of N near the centre of the star, due to the mean molecular weight gradient developing in a radiative region (see upper panel of Fig. 5.10), gives a larger and larger contribution to $\int \frac{N}{x'} dx'$, leading to a significant reduction of the mean period spacing. The increase of N near the centre is nonetheless not sufficient to produce any periodic components of appreciable amplitude in the period spacing (see lower panel of Fig. 5.10).

Figure 5.9: Fractional mass of the convective core as a function of the central hydrogen abundance for models computed with (right panel) and without (left panel) overshooting, for masses between 1.0 and $2 M_{\odot}$. α_{OV} is the overshooting parameter as defined in Sect. 5.4.2.1.

5.4.1.2 Models with a growing convective core on the main-sequence.

In models with masses between M_{Lcc} and M_{gc} , the contribution of nuclear burning through CNO cycle becomes more and more important as the star evolves on the main sequence (see e.g. Gabriel & Noels, 1977; Crowe & Mitalas, 1982; Popielski & Dziembowski, 2005). The ratio L/m in the nuclear burning region becomes large enough to alter the behaviour of ∇_{rad} i.e. the latter increases and so does the size of the convective core.

A growing convective core generates a discontinuity in the chemical composition at its boundary (see Fig. 5.11), and may lead to an inconsistency in the way the convective boundary is defined. The situation is illustrated in Fig. 5.12: the discontinuous hydrogen profile forces the radiative gradient to be discontinuous and to increase outside the region that is fully mixed by convection, and therefore this region should be convective as well! If this is the case, then we have a contradictory situation: if we allow this region to have the same chemical composition as the core, then ∇_{rad} decreases and the region becomes radiative again. The question of the semi-convection onset in models with masses in the range 1.1 - 1.6 was already addressed by Gabriel & Noels (1977) and Crowe & Mitalas (1982) quite some time ago. Nevertheless, what happens in this so-called “semi-convective” region is still a matter of debate. Some mixing is likely to take place so that the composition gradients are adapted to obtain $\nabla_{rad} = \nabla_{ad}$ in the semiconvective

Figure 5.10: *Upper left panel:* N as a function of the normalized radius in $1 M_\odot$ models with decreasing central hydrogen abundance. *Upper right panel:* Hydrogen abundance profile versus r/R . *Lower panel:* g-modes period spacing as a function of the radial order k . The asymptotic value of ΔP (predicted by Eq. 5.4) is represented, for each model, by dotted lines.

Figure 5.11: The discontinuous chemical composition profile generated by a growing convective core in $1.3 M_{\odot}$ (see Fig. 5.12) when no extra-mixing outside the core is allowed.

region.

Even if no specific mixing is added in the semi-convective region, the μ gradient at the boundary of the convective core is very sensitive to the details of the numerical algorithm used in describing the core evolution. In fact, a strict discontinuity in chemical composition is only obtained if the border of the convective region is treated with a double mesh point (Fig. 5.11 for instance). This “unphysical” framework leads to a problem when computing the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, nevertheless this numerical difficulty can easily be avoided keeping a quasi-discontinuous chemical composition, with a sharp change of X in extremely narrow region ($\delta_0 = x_{\mu} - x_0$) outside the convective core (x_0). From Eqs. (5.10) and (5.13) it is evident that in this case the signal in the period spacing will have an almost infinite period.

Of course, any treatment of the semi-convective region should destroy this discontinuity leading to a wider μ -gradient region. The chemical composition discontinuity may also be removed by a sort of “numerical diffusion” that appears when the grid of mesh points (necessarily finite) in the modelling does not follow the convection limits. That is the case of the evolution code (CLEM, Scuflaire et al. 2007b) used to compute most of the stellar models presented in this Chapter. In these models, the region where the discontinuity would be located is assumed to have an intermediate chemical composition between the one in the outermost point of the convective core and the one in the innermost point of the radiative region.

Figure 5.12: *Upper panel:* Radiative gradient in the inner regions of $1.3 M_{\odot}$ models at different stages on the main sequence. The adiabatic gradient is represented with a short-dashed line. *Middle panel:* Ratio $L(r)/m(r)$. During the evolution the large increase of L/m at the former border of the convective core dominates the behaviour of ∇_{rad} . The vertical dashed line denotes the border of the convective core in the ZAMS model. *Lower panel:* Behaviour of κ for the same models as in the other panels.

The final effect is to flatten the μ gradient at the edge of the convective core.

Furthermore, in models with a mass $M \simeq M_{\text{LCC}}$, e.g. $M = 1.2 M_{\odot}$, the convective core is so small ($m/M \sim 0.01$) that the behaviour of the period spacing resembles the one for the $1 M_{\odot}$ model. We notice, however, the appearance of oscillatory components in ΔP in the model with $X_c \simeq 0.1$ (see Fig. 5.13). The sharp variation of N located at $\Pi_0/\Pi_r \simeq 0.1$ is large enough to generate components with a periodicity of $10 k$ in ΔP . In more massive models, the μ gradient becomes larger and so does the amplitude of the components in the period spacing (see e.g. Fig. 5.14).

5.4.1.3 Models with a receding convective core.

In models with shrinking convective cores the situation is much simpler. If $M > M_{\text{gc}}$ the term that dominates the behaviour of the radiative gradient is the opacity and, since $\kappa \propto (1 + X)$, ∇_{rad} decreases with time as X decreases: the boundary of the convective core is displaced toward the centre. A receding convective core leaves behind a chemical composition gradient that is responsible for an abrupt change in the N profile (as in Fig. 5.1). Such a sharp feature, which is a direct consequence of the evolution of a convective core, leaves a clear signature in the periods of gravity modes.

This behaviour is shown in Figures 5.15 and 5.16 for models of 1.6 and $6 M_{\odot}$ (for larger masses, the behaviour is almost identical to that of $6 M_{\odot}$). The amplitude and periodicity of the components in ΔP can be easily related to the profile of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency by means of expression (5.14). For instance, the $\Delta k = 7$ in Fig. 5.16 (lower panel, $X_c = 0.50$), corresponds to the sharp signal in N at $\Pi_0/\Pi_r \sim 0.14$. As the star evolves, the sharp feature in N is shifted at higher Π_0/Π_r , and when $\Pi_0/\Pi_r \simeq 0.5$ a kind of beating appears in the period spacing, due to the fact that the sampling frequency is about half the frequency of the periodic component.

It can also be noticed that oscillatory components of small amplitude are already present in zero age main-sequence stars with $M \gtrsim 6 M_{\odot}$ (see e.g. Fig. 5.16, solid lines). Though a chemical composition gradient is not yet present in these models, the bump in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency due to an increase of the opacity² at a temperature of $\sim 3 \times 10^6$ K ($\Pi_0/\Pi_r \simeq 0.8$) is able to produce such a deviation from constant ΔP . It is not surprising that the effects of a sharp feature located near the surface can mimic the effect of a perturbation in the core: as shown by Montgomery et al. (2003) the signature on high order g-modes of a perturbation in N located at a normalized buoyancy radius $r_{\text{BV}} = \Pi_0/\Pi_r$ is aliased to a signal whose source is located at $1 - r_{\text{BV}}$. The signal shown in Fig 5.16 could indicate a source at $0.2 \Pi_0/\Pi_r$ which is in fact approximatively an alias $(1 - 0.2)$ of the

²mainly due to C, O, Ne and Fe transitions (see e.g. Rogers & Iglesias, 1992; Seaton & Badnell, 2004).

source at $0.8 \Pi_0/\Pi_r$. The amplitude of this signal increases with the stellar mass as the contribution of this opacity bump becomes dominant in the behaviour of ∇_{rad} (and therefore of N). In fact for large enough stellar masses, a convective shell can appear at a temperature $\sim 3 \times 10^6$ K. The amplitude of such components is however less than 1000 s and therefore much smaller than the one generated by the chemical composition gradient at the edge of the convective core.

The behaviour of g-mode period spacing is clearly different depending on the mass and age of the models. While in models without a convective core, or with a very small one, the mean value of the period spacing decreases with age (see Sec. 5.4.1.1), for more massive models the period spacing does not significantly change with age. In stars with larger convective cores the chemical composition gradient is located at a larger fractional radius, giving a smaller contribution to $\int \frac{N}{x^2} dx'$, and thus to ΔP , as predicted by the asymptotic expression. In these models the age effect is nonetheless made evident through the appearance of the periodic signal in the period spacing, whose periodicity is directly linked to the chemical gradient left by the evolution of the convective core.

5.4.2 Effects of extra-mixing on high-order g modes

The comparison between theoretical models and observations clearly shows that the standard stellar modelling underestimates the size of the central mixed region (see e.g. Andersen et al., 1990; Ribas et al., 2000). This fact is generally accepted, but there is no consensus about the physical processes responsible for the required extra-mixing that is missing in the standard evolution models: overshooting (e.g. Schaller et al., 1992), microscopic diffusion (Michaud et al., 2004), rotationally induced mixing (see e.g. Maeder & Meynet, 2000; Mathis et al., 2004, and references therein), or mixing generated by propagation of internal waves (e.g. Young & Arnett, 2005). The shape of the composition transition zone is a matter of great importance as far as asteroseismology is concerned. In particular it significantly affects the term ∇_μ appearing in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency and plays a critical role in the phenomenon of mode trapping.

It is therefore evident that the size and evolution of the convective core, as well as the μ gradients that it generates, can be strongly affected by the occurrence of mixing processes. In the following paragraphs we study how these effects are reflected on the high order g-modes. We have computed models with overshooting, microscopic diffusion, turbulent mixing, and we have compared their adiabatic g-modes periods with those derived for models computed without mixing but with the same central hydrogen abundance.

Figure 5.13: Behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (upper left panel), of the hydrogen abundance profile (upper right panel) and of the $\ell = 1$ g-mode period spacing in models of $1.2 M_{\odot}$. We consider, as in all the following figures, several models on the main sequence with decreasing central hydrogen abundance (X_c 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 and 0.1). In the lower panel the uppermost model has $X_c = 0.7$ and the lowermost $X_c = 0.1$.

Figure 5.14: Same as Fig.5.13 for $1.4 M_\odot$ models.

Figure 5.15: Same as Fig.5.13 for $1.6 M_{\odot}$ models.

Figure 5.16: Same as Fig.5.13 for $6.0 M_{\odot}$ models. In the homogeneous ZAMS model ($X_c \simeq 0.7$, full lines) a sharp variation in N located at $\Pi_0/\Pi_r \simeq 0.8$ generates a periodic signal of small amplitude in the period spacing. Note that for this model, to make such a component more visible in ΔP , the y-axis scale has been modified.

5.4.2.1 Overshooting

Penetration of motions beyond the boundary of convective zones defined by the Schwarzschild stability criterion has been the subject of many studies in an astrophysical context (see e.g. Zahn, 1991). Unfortunately, features such as extension, temperature gradient and efficiency of the mixing in the overshooting region cannot be derived from the local model of convection currently used in stellar evolution computations. As a consequence, this region is usually described in a parametric way. In the models considered here the thickness of the overshooting layer ov is parameterized in terms of the local pressure scale height H_p : $ov = \alpha_{OV} \times (\min(r_{cv}, H_p(r_{cv})))$ (where r_{cv} is the radius of the convective core and α_{OV} is a free parameter). We assume instantaneous mixing both in convective and in overshooting regions, and the temperature gradient in the overshooting region is left unchanged (i.e. $\nabla = \nabla_{rad}$). Therefore overshooting simply extends the region assumed to be fully mixed by convection. The larger hydrogen reservoir, due to an increase of the mixed region, translates into a longer core-hydrogen burning phase.

The adopted amount of overshooting also determines the lowest stellar mass at which a convective core appears. For sufficiently large values of α_{OV} , the convective core that develops in the pre-main sequence phase persists during the main sequence in models with $M < M_{Lcc}$ (as in Fig. 5.9). In these models the convective core is maintained thanks to the continuous supply of ${}^3\text{He}$ that sustains the highly temperature-dependent nuclear reaction ${}^3\text{He} + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}^4\text{He} + {}^1\text{H} + {}^1\text{H}$, keeping the pp chain in an out-of-equilibrium regime. The inclusion of overshooting changes the value of the mass corresponding to the transition between models with a convective core that grows/shrinks during the main sequence (Fig. 5.9, right panel). And finally, the effect of overshooting on the μ gradients depends on whether the nuclear reactions occur only inside the convective core or outside also.

In Figures 5.17, 5.18 and 5.19 we present the chemical composition profile, the behaviour of N and of the period spacing, in models computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$). These models have a larger fully mixed region than those computed without overshooting. The chemical composition gradient is then displaced to a higher mass fraction. If we compare models with similar central hydrogen abundance, however, this does not necessarily imply that the sharp feature in N is located at a different normalized buoyancy radius (Π_0/Π_μ).

- In $6 M_\odot$ models (Fig. 5.19), for instance, neither the sharpness of the abrupt variation in N nor its location in terms of Π_μ change when comparing models computed with and without overshooting.
- The situation changes in lower mass models, e.g. in $1.6 M_\odot$ models (Fig. 5.18). Here the periodicity of the components in ΔP differs if we include overshooting or not. A change in the location, but also in the value of the μ

Figure 5.17: behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (upper row), of the hydrogen abundance profile (central row) and of the $\ell = 1$ g-mode period spacing (lower row) in models of $1.2 M_{\odot}$ computed with (thick lines) or without (thin lines) overshooting.

Figure 5.18: As in Fig. 5.17, but for $1.6 M_\odot$ models.

Figure 5.19: As in Fig. 5.17, but for $6 M_{\odot}$ models.

gradient (as nuclear reactions take place outside the core as well), is responsible for a different behaviour of the oscillatory components in ΔP .

- In models with a mass $M \simeq M_{LCC}$, e.g. $M = 1.2 M_{\odot}$, the inclusion of overshooting dramatically increases the size of the fully mixed region. The oscillatory components in ΔP have different periods and much larger amplitudes than the ones in the models without overshooting (see Fig. 5.17).

As we mentioned above, not only the extension of the overshooting region is uncertain, but also its temperature stratification. However, the effect on ΔP of considering convective penetration ($\nabla = \nabla_{ad}$ in the “extended” convective core) instead of simple overshooting is found to be small (see Straka et al., 2005; Godart, 2007).

5.4.2.2 Effects of microscopic diffusion

Other physical processes, different from overshooting, can lead to an increase of the central mixed region or modify the chemical composition profile near the core.

Michaud et al. (2004) and Richard (2005) have shown that microscopic diffusion can induce an increase of the convective core mass for a narrow range of masses, from 1.1 to 1.5 M_{\odot} , and that the effect decreases rapidly with increasing stellar mass. In this mass domain, as previously described, the mass of the convective core increases during the MS evolution instead of decreasing, as it occurs for larger masses. As a consequence, a sharp gradient of chemical composition appears at the convective core border, making the diffusion process much more efficient in that region.

Figure 5.20 shows the effect of including gravitational settling, thermal and chemical diffusion of hydrogen and helium in a 1.6 M_{\odot} model. If only He and H diffusion is considered in the modelling, we find that a smoother chemical composition profile is built at the edge of the convective core (see Fig. 5.20), preventing the presence of a discontinuity of μ caused by a growing convective core. Comparing models calculated with or without diffusion, we see that the location of the convective core boundary has not significantly changed. Nevertheless, a less sharp variation in the Brunt-Väisälä frequency is responsible for a considerable reduction of the amplitude of the components in the period spacing (see Fig. 5.21). It was in fact predicted in Section 5.3.1 that a discontinuity not in N itself, but in its first derivative, would generate a periodic component whose amplitude decreases with the period: this simplified approach is therefore sufficient to account for the behaviour of ΔP in models with a smoother chemical composition gradient (see Eq. 5.16).

When diffusion of Z is also included, the overall effect of diffusion is no longer able to erode the sharp chemical composition gradient and to prevent the formation

Figure 5.20: Behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency in models of $1.6 M_{\odot}$ with $X_c \simeq 0.3$. The different lines correspond to models calculated with no extra-mixing (continuous lines), overshooting (dashed) and helium diffusion (dotted). The different location and sharpness of the chemical composition profile determines the behaviour of N .

Figure 5.21: Period spacing of $\ell = 1$ g modes as a function of the radial order k for the $1.6 M_{\odot}$ models presented in Fig. 5.20.

of a semi-convective zone; on the contrary, diffusion of Z outside the core makes the occurrence of semi-convection easier (see also Richard et al., 2001; Michaud et al., 2004; Montalbán et al., 2007b).

While chemical diffusion leads to a smoother chemical composition profile in intermediate- and low-mass stars, we find that such an effect disappears as higher masses are considered and evolutionary time-scales necessarily decrease. In fact we find that in models with $M \gtrsim 4 M_{\odot}$ diffusion has no effect on the Brunt-Väisälä frequency profile near the hydrogen burning core, nor on the behaviour of the period spacing.

As higher masses are considered, the effect of microscopic diffusion on the stellar structure near the core becomes negligible but other mixing processes can partly erode the chemical composition gradients.

5.4.2.3 Rotationally induced mixing

Rotationally induced mixing can influence the internal distribution of μ near the energy generating core. Different approaches have been proposed to treat the effects of rotation on the transport of angular momentum and chemicals (see e.g. Maeder & Meynet, 2000; Heger & Langer, 2000; Pinsonneault et al., 1989; Mathis et al., 2004, and references therein). Such an additional mixing has an effect on the evolutionary tracks which is quite similar to that of overshooting, but it leads also to a smoother chemical composition profile at the edge of the convective core.

Since our stellar evolution code does not include a consistent treatment of rotational effects, we simply include the chemical turbulent mixing by adding a turbulent diffusion coefficient (D_T) in the diffusion equation. In our parametric approach D_T is assumed to be constant inside the star and independent of age.

The simplified parametric treatment of rotationally induced mixing used in this work has the aim of showing that if an extra-mixing process, different from overshooting, is acting near the core it will produce a different chemical composition profile in the central regions of the star and leave a different signature in the periods of gravity modes. The effects of such a mixing on the evolutionary tracks (see Fig. 5.22) and on the internal structure clearly depend on the value of D_T .

As an example we consider models of a $6 M_{\odot}$ star computed with three different values of the turbulent-diffusion coefficient $D_T = 5 \times 10^2$, 5×10^3 and $5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The lowest D_T value provides an evolutionary track that overlaps the one computed with no mixing, however, its effect on the chemical composition gradient (see Fig. 5.23) is sufficient to affect ΔP at high order modes. In order to significantly change the periods of low-order modes a much more effective mixing is needed. The value $D_T = 5 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ leads to a slightly more luminous evolutionary track, but such a mixing has a substantial effect on the period spacing: the amplitude of the periodic components in ΔP becomes a decreasing function of the radial order k (see Figures 5.23 and 5.24). As in the case of helium dif-

Figure 5.22: HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of $6 M_\odot$ models calculated with different extra-mixing processes. The evolutionary track computed with $D_T = 500 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is superposed to that without extra-mixing (continuous line).

fusion (see Sec. 5.4.2.2) this behaviour can be easily explained by the analytical approximation presented in Sec. 5.3.1 (Eq. 5.16), provided the sharp feature in N is modelled not as a step function but, for instance, as a ramp (Eq. 5.15).

If a significantly more effective mixing is considered (e.g. $D_T = 50000 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, see Fig. 5.22 and 5.25), the corresponding evolutionary track is close to that obtained by including a classical overshooting but the periodic components in ΔP are no longer present.

The effects of such a turbulent mixing on low-order gravity modes and avoided crossings will be addressed in detail in Sec. 5.6.2.

In order to check that our parametric approach is at least in qualitative agreement with the outcome of models where rotationally induced mixing is treated consistently, we present for comparison a sequence of models computed with the Geneva evolutionary code (Meynet & Maeder, 2000; Eggenberger et al., 2007). We considered a $6 M_\odot$ model with an initial surface rotational velocity of 25 km s^{-1} , the typical $v \sin i$ for SPBs stars (Briquet et al., 2007a). As the model evolves on the MS, the effects on the HR diagram (Fig. 5.26) and on the chemical composition gradient in the core (Fig 5.27) are very similar to those of the model computed with a uniform turbulent diffusion coefficient $D_T = 5 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$. This is not surprising since, in the central regions, the total turbulent diffusion coefficient shown in Fig. 5.28 does not change considerably in time and its magnitude is of the order of a few thousands $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

5.4.3 Modes of different degree and low radial order

In the previous sections we analyzed the properties of ΔP for $\ell = 1$, high order g-modes. Does the period spacing computed with modes of different degree ℓ , or with low radial order k , have a similar behaviour? In Fig. 5.29 we consider the period spacing computed with $\ell = 2$ periods ($P_{k,\ell=2}$) scaled by the ℓ -dependent factor suggested by Eq. 5.4, i.e. $P'_{k,\ell=2} = \sqrt{3} P_{k,\ell=2}$. Except for the oscillation modes with the lowest radial orders, we notice in Fig. 5.29 that the period spacing of modes of degree $\ell = 1$ and 2 have the same behaviour, provided that the dependence on ℓ given by Eq. 5.4 is removed.

Though the asymptotic approximation is valid for high order modes, we see in Fig. 5.29 (as well as in the figures presented in the previous sections) that the description of the period spacing as the superposition of the constant term derived from Eq. 5.4 and periodic components related to ∇_μ , is able to accurately describe the periods of gravity modes even for low orders k . This suggest that, at least qualitatively, the description of g-modes presented in this work could represent a useful tool to interpret the behaviour of low order g-modes observed in other classes of pulsators, such as β Cephei and δ Scuti stars (see Sec 5.6).

Figure 5.23: Behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (upper left panel), of the hydrogen abundance profile (upper right panel) and of the $\ell = 1$ g-mode period spacing in models of $6.0 M_\odot$ computed with a turbulent diffusion coefficient $D_T = 500 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 5.24: As in Fig. 5.24 but for models with $D_T = 5000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$

Figure 5.25: As in Fig. 5.24 but for models with $D_T = 50000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The effect of such a mixing on the evolutionary track is shown in Fig. 5.22

Figure 5.26: HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of $6 M_{\odot}$ models calculated with the Geneva evolutionary code. The full line evolutionary track is computed without rotation, whereas in the models evolving on the dotted track, an initial surface velocity of 25 km s^{-1} is assumed.

Figure 5.27: Hydrogen abundance in the core of $6 M_{\odot}$ models with an initial surface velocity of 25 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.28: Total diffusion coefficient D_T as a function of the normalized mass in $6 M_{\odot}$ models evolving on the main sequence. The initial surface velocity assumed is 25 km s^{-1} . D_T includes both the effects of shear (D_{shear}) and meridional circulation (D_{eff}).

Figure 5.29: Period spacing for a $6 M_{\odot}$ models with $X_c = 0.5$. The period spacing computed with $\ell = 2$ modes is multiplied by $\sqrt{3}$, as suggested by Eq. 5.4.

5.5 Challenges for asteroseismology of SPB and γ Dor stars

Asteroseismology of high-order g-mode main-sequence pulsators is not an easy task. The long oscillation periods and the dense frequency spectrum in these stars require long and continuous observations in order to resolve single oscillation frequencies. As clearly stated already in Dziembowski et al. (1993), observations of at least 70 days are needed to resolve the period spacing in a typical SPB star. In addition to large observational efforts that have been made from the ground (see e.g. De Cat & Aerts 2002, De Cat et al. 2007 for SPB stars and Mathias et al. 2004 and Henry et al. 2007 for γ Dor), long uninterrupted space-based photometric time series will soon be provided by CoRoT. In order to estimate if the CoRoT 150 day-long observations have a frequency resolution sufficient to resolve the period spacing of a typical SPB star, we simulated time series of $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ high-order g modes that are expected to be excited in a $6 M_{\odot}$ star with $X_c = 0.2$ computed without overshooting. The excitation of oscillation modes has been computed using the non-adiabatic code MAD (Dupret et al., 2003). Random initial phases have been considered in the sinusoids describing the 25 excited frequencies included in the simulations, and amplitudes of 1 and 0.5 (on an arbitrary scale) have been assumed for $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ modes respectively. The generated time series has been analyzed using the package Period04 (Lenz & Breger, 2005). As it is shown in the resulting power spectrum (see Fig. 5.30), for such long observational runs (150 days), the input frequencies can be accurately recovered even for the largest periods of oscillation. Thanks to the high frequency resolution, the departures from a constant period spacing are also evident in the power spectrum.

We then simulate a time series for an additional $6 M_{\odot}$ model that, despite having the same surface properties ($\log(L/L_{\odot}) = 3.28$, $\log(T_{\text{eff}}) = 4.22$) as the previous one, is computed with turbulent diffusion ($D_T = 5000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). In this case the power spectrum (see Fig. 5.31) shows a regular period spacing that, on the basis of the high frequency resolution, can be easily distinguished from the one described in Fig. 5.30.

Even though frequency resolution may no longer be an issue in the very near future, there is a second well known factor limiting asteroseismology of SPB and γ Dor stars: the effects of rotation on the oscillation frequency can severely complicate the high-order g-mode spectra. Referring once more to the work by Dziembowski et al. (1993), a first requirement in order to treat rotational effects as perturbations on the oscillation frequencies is the angular rotational velocity being sufficiently smaller than the oscillation frequency ($v_{\text{rot}} \ll 2\pi R/P$, where R is the radius of the star and P the oscillation period). In the case of the models of an SPB

Figure 5.30: Power spectrum of simulated time series for a $6 M_{\odot}$ model. The vertical solid and dashed lines represent the input oscillation frequencies of $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ modes respectively.

Figure 5.31: Same as Fig. 5.30 for a $6 M_{\odot}$ model computed with turbulent diffusion in the core.

Figure 5.32: Rotational splittings for $\ell = 1$ modes in the model of an SPB ($M = 4 M_{\odot}$, $R \simeq 3.1 R_{\odot}$) considered in Dziembowski et al. (1993). The $m = -1, 0$ and 1 modes are marked respectively by squares, circles and triangles. Taken from Dziembowski et al. (1993).

star considered previously in this section, this translates into $v_{rot} \ll 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ considering the modes of longest period: this is significantly larger than the average $v \sin i$ ($\sim 25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) measured in SPB stars (see e.g. Briquet et al., 2007a). In the case of γ Dor stars (see e.g. Suárez et al. 2005) a similar estimate limits the validity of the perturbative approach to rotational velocities of $\sim 50 - 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$: for faster rotators non-perturbative approaches are needed (see Dintrans & Rieutord, 2000; Rieutord & Dintrans, 2002).

Even in the case of slow rotators, however, the rotational splittings may become as large as the period spacing itself. Such a large effect of rotation on the frequency spectrum can severely complicate the identification of the azimuthal order m and the degree ℓ of the observed modes. In fact, a simple mode identification based on the regular pattern expected from high-order g-modes becomes inapplicable if the rotational splitting is of the same order as ΔP (see, as an example Fig. 5.32, taken from Dziembowski et al. 1993). The identification of the modes would then need to be provided by photometric and spectroscopic mode identification techniques (see e.g. Balona, 1986; Garrido et al., 1990; Aerts et al., 1992; Mantegazza, 2000; Briquet & Aerts, 2003; Dupret et al., 2003; Zima, 2006).

5.6 The effect of turbulent mixing near the core on low-order g modes and modes of mixed p- and g-character

It has been shown in Sec. 5.4.2.3 that turbulent mixing acting near the edge of the convective core can significantly affect the properties of the μ gradient and thus of gravity modes. As the case of high order gravity modes has been analyzed in Sec. 5.4.2.3, we here address the effects of such mixing on low-order gravity modes and on modes of mixed p- and g-character. From the standpoint of seismic modelling, one of the advantages of these pulsation modes is that the effects of rotation are less severe, at least for low- moderate rotational velocities, than in the case of high-order gravity modes discussed in the previous section.

Low-order gravity modes and mixed-modes are found to be excited in two classes of pulsating stars on the main sequence: β Cephei and δ Scuti stars (see Sec. 3.8). In particular here we shall concentrate on β Cephei stars describing firstly (Sec. 5.6.1) the effects of turbulent mixing on the chemical composition gradient and then on the oscillation frequencies (Sec. 5.6.2.1). We will only briefly discuss in Sec. 5.6.2.2 the effects on the pulsation modes in δ Scuti stars.

Finally, in Sec. 5.6.2.3, we recall the effect of turbulent mixing on the mixed modes that are also expected to affect the frequency spectrum of solar-like oscillations in stars that are leaving the main-sequence and evolving as subgiants.

5.6.1 Effects of turbulent mixing on the μ gradient near the core in $10 M_{\odot}$ models

As we already described in Sec. 5.4.2.3, introducing turbulent mixing near the edge of the convective core results in a smoother μ profile and modifies the properties of the sharp feature in N generated by the μ gradient. We will first describe the properties of models in which we included a simple parametrized turbulent mixing near the core. This parametric implementation is introduced to reproduce the outcome of models computed with the Geneva evolutionary code, where a total turbulent diffusion coefficient is derived taking into account the effects of rotation on the transport of angular momentum and chemicals (see Maeder & Meynet, 2000; Eggenberger et al., 2007).

We consider models for a typical β Cep star, i.e. $10 M_{\odot}$ models on the main-sequence. We compute them assuming different values of the turbulent diffusion coefficient (as described in Sec. 5.4.2.3) and including or not overshooting. The effect on the HR diagram of considering such extra mixing in the core is shown in Fig. 5.33. Though the effect of turbulent mixing on the evolutionary tracks is similar to that of overshooting (longer and more luminous evolutionary track), a milder chemical composition gradient near the core changes the properties of the

Figure 5.33: HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of $10 M_{\odot}$ models calculated with no extra-mixing processes (dashed-dotted line), with overshooting (thin full line) and turbulent mixing near the core with different values of D_{T} (short-dashed, long-dashed, dotted and thick full lines).

Brunt-Väisälä frequency. This is shown in Figs. 5.34-5.37 for models computed with four values of D_{T} (respectively 3.5×10^4 , 7×10^4 , 1.4×10^5 and $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). As we consider larger values of D_{T} , while the extension of the fully-mixed region is not affected (differently than when we increase the overshooting parameter), the chemical composition gradient becomes milder and it extends towards larger values of the fractional radius.

We compare the results of our simple parametric implementation of turbulent mixing with the outcome of models computed with the Geneva code (courtesy of P. Eggenberger) that takes into the effects of rotation on the stellar structure. We consider a set of evolutionary tracks of $10 M_{\odot}$ models computed assuming low/moderate surface rotation rates that are typical of β Cephei stars (20, 50 and 100 km s^{-1} , see e.g. Stankov & Handler 2005). The effects of rotationally induced mixing on the HR diagram and on the chemical composition gradient are shown in Fig 5.38 and Fig. 5.39. The comparison of these figures with Fig. 5.33 and 5.35 shows, similarly to the case of the $6 M_{\odot}$ model in Sec. 5.4.2.3, that these effects are qualitatively well reproduced by the parametric approach adopted in the models computed with CLES. In the latter, the assumption of a uniform and time-independent D_{T} in the central region, qualitatively describes the behaviour of

Figure 5.34: Behaviour of the hydrogen abundance profile (upper panel) and of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (lower panel) in $10 M_{\odot}$ models with $X_c \simeq 0.3$. The different lines correspond to models calculated with no extra mixing (dotted lines), overshooting (dashed) and turbulent mixing with $D_T = 3.5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (continuous).

Figure 5.35: As in Fig. 5.34 but for models with $D_T = 7 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 5.36: As in Fig. 5.34 but for models with $D_T = 1.4 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 5.37: As in Fig. 5.34 but for models with $D_T = 2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 5.38: HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of $10 M_{\odot}$ models calculated with the Geneva stellar evolution code, with different values of the initial surface velocity (v_{rot}). Long-dashed lines refer to the model computed without rotation, whereas dotted, short-dashed and continuous lines refer to models with, respectively, $v_{\text{rot}} = 20, 50$ and 100 km s^{-1} .

the total turbulent diffusion coefficient obtained from Geneva models, as presented in Figures 5.40 and 5.41.

In Fig.5.41 we also notice that the order of magnitude of the total turbulent diffusion coefficient is $\sim 10^4 - 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for initial surface rotational velocities in the range $20\text{-}100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

5.6.2 Effects of turbulent mixing on low-order g modes and mixed modes

In Sec. 5.4.2.3, when considering the case of high-order gravity modes, we have shown that the properties of g-mode spectra can be easily related by means of an analytical approximation to the detailed characteristics of the “glitch” of N located in the μ gradient region. This approximation, however, becomes invalid when considering modes of low-order, and cannot therefore be used to give an accurate description of the properties of such modes. Moreover, a further complication to an analytical description of low-order non-radial modes is given by the interaction between pressure and gravity modes that give rise to modes of mixed character (see e.g. Shibahashi 1979). Nonetheless, as shown in Sec. 5.4.3, the analytical

Figure 5.39: Evolution of the hydrogen abundance profile in the central regions of $10 M_{\odot}$ main-sequence models computed with an initial surface velocity of 50 km s^{-1}

Figure 5.40: Total diffusion coefficient D_T as a function of the fractional mass in $10 M_{\odot}$ models evolving on the main sequence. The initial surface velocity assumed is 50 km s^{-1} . D_T includes both the effects of shear (D_{shear}) and meridional circulation (D_{eff})

Figure 5.41: Total diffusion coefficient D_T as a function the fractional mass in $10 M_{\odot}$ models with $X_c \simeq 0.3$. Dotted, short-dashed and continuous lines refer to models with initial surface velocities of, respectively, 20, 50 and 100 km s^{-1} . The value of the total diffusion coefficient $D_T = 7 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is also shown for comparison (long-dashed line).

description of gravity modes presented there is still able to qualitatively describe the properties of g-mode spectra for modes of low-order (see Fig. 5.29).

In Fig. 5.42 we show that in the typical β Cep frequency domain (vertical lines) the difference between the frequencies of a $10 M_{\odot}$ model computed with and without turbulent mixing can still be qualitatively related to the different behaviour of the sharp variation in N . As shown in the previous sections, turbulent mixing leads to a reduction in the amplitude of the periodic components in the period spacing and such a reduction increases with the order of the mode and with the effectiveness of such extra-mixing (see Figures 5.23, 5.24 and 5.25).

In Fig. 5.42 we compare the period spacing for $\ell = 1, 2$ and 3 modes of a $10 M_{\odot}$ model computed with turbulent mixing or with overshooting. The decrease of the amplitude of the periodic components in ΔP , due to the effect of turbulent mixing, significantly affects the periods of low-order gravity modes and of mixed modes as well. We also show in Fig. 5.42 that the period spacing of low-order modes and of mixed modes has an intermediate behaviour between the expression of ΔP valid in the two asymptotic regimes: for high-order gravity modes ($\Delta P \propto \text{const}$) and for high-order pressure modes ($\Delta P \propto P^2$).

5.6.2.1 β Cephei stars

In this section we analyze the effect of turbulent mixing on the oscillation frequencies of β Cep stars. For this purpose we compare the frequencies of $10 M_{\odot}$ main-sequence models computed with different values of the parametric turbulent diffusion coefficient D_T , with those of models computed with overshooting. The values of the overshooting parameter chosen in the comparisons are such as to lead to an evolutionary track close to the one of the model with turbulent mixing (see Fig. 5.33). Such a comparison allows us to remove the differences in the frequencies due only to a different radius, and therefore to a different position in the HR diagram. These comparisons are presented in Figures 5.43-5.46. As a general result we notice that as expected, pressure modes are not sensitive to a different mixing process near the core. On the other hand, significant differences appear for mixed modes and become larger as we consider gravity modes of increasing order (as suggested by the analytical approximation in Sec. 5.3). The asymptotic expression also explains a larger effect on modes of increasing degree, since the radial order of gravity modes of a given frequency is higher for modes of higher ℓ (see Eq. 5.4).

The relevance of these differences clearly depends on the effectiveness of the turbulent mixing considered in the models. While a small value of D_T affects only slightly the oscillation frequencies in the β Cep domain (up to 0.25 c/d for g modes in $\ell = 3$ modes, see Fig. 5.43), the oscillation spectrum of gravity and mixed modes can be severely modified, even for $\ell = 1$ modes, as the value of D_T increases. As shown in Figs. 5.44-5.46 the main effect of turbulent mixing is

Figure 5.42: Period spacing for $l = 1, 2$ and 3 low order modes (upper, central and lower panel) as a function of the period for $10 M_{\odot}$ models with $X_c \simeq 0.3$ computed with overshooting $\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$ (triangles connected with solid lines) and with turbulent mixing $D_T = 2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (squares connected with dashed-dotted lines). Horizontal short-dashed lines represent the asymptotic value of the period spacing for gravity modes, whereas the long dashed line shows the asymptotic value of ΔP valid for high order pressure modes. The frequency range typical of a β Cep star is delimited by vertical dotted lines.

Figure 5.43: Frequencies of pulsation modes as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ for main-sequence models of a $10 M_{\odot}$ star. Gray dots represent the frequencies of models computed without extra-mixing, whereas black circles are the frequencies of models computed with $D_{\text{T}} = 3.5 \times 10^4$. Excited modes are represented by thicker symbols.

to change the distance between consecutive frequencies of g modes or modes of mixed p-g character. We recall that, from the comparisons with models computed with the Geneva code, $D_{\text{T}} = 7 \times 10^4$ mimics the mixing induced by a rotational velocity $v_{\text{rot}} \simeq 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

We shall further discuss how turbulent mixing and overshooting differently affect the frequencies of low-order g modes and mixed p-g modes. The effects of overshooting on the oscillation frequencies of δ Scuti stars have been studied, e.g. in Dziembowski & Pamyatnykh (1991), Michel et al. (1993) and Audard et al. (1995), where it was shown that only the frequencies of modes undergoing an avoided crossing are slightly modified. The largest differences appear at the lower T_{eff} when the standard model has already left the main sequence, whereas the model with overshooting is still burning hydrogen in the centre.

The difference between the effect of turbulent mixing and of overshooting on

Figure 5.44: As in Fig. 5.43 but comparing the frequencies of main-sequence models computed with $\alpha_{OV} = 0.1$ and $D_T = 7 \times 10^4$.

Figure 5.45: As in Fig. 5.43 but comparing the frequencies of main-sequence models computed with $\alpha_{\text{OV}} = 0.1$ and $D_T = 1.4 \times 10^5$.

Figure 5.46: As in Fig. 5.43 but comparing the frequencies of main-sequence models computed with $\alpha_{\text{OV}} = 0.2$ and $D_T = 2.8 \times 10^5$.

Figure 5.47: Dimensionless frequencies of pulsation modes as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ for main-sequence models of a $10 M_{\odot}$ star. Open circles represent the frequencies of models computed without extra-mixing, whereas crosses and dots are the frequencies of models computed with $\alpha_{\text{OV}} = 0.1$ and $D_{\text{T}} = 1.4 \times 10^5$ respectively.

the oscillation frequencies is clearly shown in Fig. 5.47. To cancel the discrepancy due to a different stellar radius, we plot the dimensionless frequencies as a function of T_{eff} , and we see that while the frequencies of overshooting and standard models on the main sequence are close, those of low-order and mixed modes in models with turbulent mixing are considerably different.

5.6.2.2 δ Scuti stars

Though we concentrated our investigation primarily on the effects of turbulent mixing on models of β Cephei stars, we here recall that a similar effect is also expected in the case of pulsation modes of δ Scuti stars. In Goupil & Talon (2002) it was in fact already suggested that “[...] extra mixing due to rotation modifies the shape of the inner maximum of N . Signatures of these fine structure in frequencies of mixed and g modes should be detectable.”. As an example of this effect we

Figure 5.48: HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of $2 M_{\odot}$ models calculated without extra-mixing processes (dotted line), with overshooting ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$, dashed line) and with turbulent mixing ($D_T = 800 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, full line)

compare models of $2 M_{\odot}$ stars computed with turbulent mixing ($D_T = 800 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and with overshooting ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$). The corresponding evolutionary tracks in the HR diagram are shown in Fig. 5.48, whereas the behaviour of the oscillation frequencies as a function of T_{eff} is presented in Fig. 5.49. As in the case of β Cep models we notice that turbulent mixing, despite having an effect on the evolutionary tracks similar to that of overshooting, affects differently the properties of pulsation modes. For a quantitative investigation of this effect however, we still need comparisons with models where turbulent mixing results from a consistent treatment of rotation.

5.6.2.3 Avoided crossings in solar-like oscillations

As recalled in Sec. 3.5.1.3, in stars that have already left the main sequence and are evolving as subgiants, modes of mixed pressure and gravity character appear in the frequency domain of solar-like oscillations. As in the case of more massive stars presented above, we expect that the frequency of a mixed mode depends on the detailed properties of the chemical composition gradient near the core. An extensive investigation of the properties of such modes is given in Chap. 7, and it is applied to the specific case of 12 Böötis A.

We here consider, as an example, two models of $1.4 M_{\odot}$ subgiant stars with

Figure 5.49: Frequencies of $\ell = 2$ pulsation modes as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ for main-sequence models of a $2 M_{\odot}$ star. Gray dots represent the frequencies of models computed without extra-mixing, whereas black circles are the frequencies of models computed with $D_T = 800 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Excited modes are represented by thicker symbols.

Figure 5.50: Hydrogen profile (*upper panel*) and Brunt-Väisälä frequency (*lower panel*) in models computed of $1.4 M_{\odot}$ with overshooting (continuous line) and with turbulent mixing (long-dashed line)

the same surface properties (L, T_{eff}) but computed including different extra mixing processes in the core: overshooting ($\alpha_{\text{OV}}=0.15$) and turbulent mixing ($D_{\text{T}} = 40 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Even if the models have already left the main sequence, we see in Fig.5.50 that their chemical composition profile (*upper panel*) still bears the signature of a different mixing process in the core, which also affects the Brunt-Väisälä frequency (*lower panel*). In analogy to Fig. 5.42, we show in Fig. 5.51, that the differences in the frequencies of gravity modes, due to a different behaviour of N , can also affect the spectrum in the domain of solar-like oscillations (vertical dotted lines). A more detailed discussion on this effect and, in particular, on its magnitude and detectability will be given in Chap. 7.

Figure 5.51: Period spacing for $\ell = 1$ modes as a function of the period for a $1.4 M_{\odot}$ model computed with overshooting ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$, solid lines) and with turbulent mixing ($D_T = 40 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, dashed-dotted lines). The long-dashed line represents the asymptotic value of ΔP valid for high order pressure modes. The frequency range of solar-like oscillations is delimited by vertical dotted lines.

5.7 Summary

In this chapter we investigated the properties of gravity modes in main-sequence stars with masses from 1 to $10 M_{\odot}$. In the corresponding region of the HR diagram several types of variable stars are found that present g-mode pulsations with distinct properties. While γ Dor stars ($M \simeq 1.4 - 1.8 M_{\odot}$) and SPB ($M \simeq 3 - 8 M_{\odot}$) show high-order gravity modes, δ Scuti ($M \simeq 1.5 - 2.5 M_{\odot}$) and β Cep ($M \simeq 7 - 20 M_{\odot}$) oscillations are low-order p and g modes as well as mixed p-g modes. Finally, solar-like oscillations in subgiant stars can also present a p-mode spectrum perturbed by the interaction between p and g modes.

The frequencies of gravity modes are very sensitive probes of the μ gradient in the central region of the star, that on its turn is determined by the combined action of nuclear burning and mixing processes. We started our investigation with the properties of high-order gravity modes, with the aim of finding the relation between the frequencies of these modes and the properties of the μ gradient.

High-order g modes

The chemical composition gradient that develops near the outer edge of the convective core leads to a sharp variation of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. As we presented in Sec. 5.2, the latter is responsible for a periodic trapping of gravity modes in the region of chemical composition gradient, and it directly affects the period spacing of g modes. In analogy with the works on white dwarfs by Brassard et al. (1992) and Montgomery et al. (2003), we show that in the case of main sequence stars analytical approximations can be used to directly relate the deviations from a uniform period spacing to the detailed properties of the μ -gradient region that develops near the energy generating core. We find that a simple approximation of g-modes periods, based on the variational principle of stellar oscillations, is sufficient to explain the appearance of sinusoidal components in the period spacing. This approximation (see Sec. 5.3.1) relates the periodicity of the components to the normalized buoyancy radius (Eq. 5.10) of the glitch in N , and the amplitude of the components to the sharpness of the feature in N . In particular, if the sharp variation in N is modelled as a step function, the amplitude of such components is expected to be independent of the order of the mode k whereas, if the glitch in N is described with a ramp, the amplitude of the components decreases with k . A more accurate semi-analytical approximation of the period spacing, which considers the effects of the sharp feature in N on the eigenfunctions, is given in Sec. 5.3.2.

As a general result we found that, in models with a convective core, the period spacing of high-order g modes is accurately described by oscillatory components of constant amplitude, superposed to the mean period spacing predicted by the asymptotic theory of Tassoul (1980). In Sec. 5.4.1 we showed that the period spacing depends primarily on the extension and behaviour of the convective core

during the main sequence and, therefore, on the mass of the star.

- In models without a convective core (see Sec. 5.4.1.1) the mean ΔP considerably decreases during the MS, whereas no significant deviation from a constant period spacing is present.
- For an intermediate range of masses (see Sec. 5.4.1.2), the convective core grows during most of the MS, generating an “unphysical” discontinuity in μ if no mixing is added in the small semiconvective region that develops. We find that the behaviour of ΔP , and in particular the appearance of periodic components, depends on the treatment of this region. It is interesting to notice that γ Doradus stars are in the mass domain where models undergo a transition between having a convective core that grows and a convective core that shrinks during the main sequence. Gravity modes could therefore represent a valuable observational test to discriminate between the different prescriptions used in stellar models (see e.g. Popielski & Dziembowski, 2005) to introduce the required mixing at the boundary of the convective core.
- In models with higher masses, the convective core recedes during the main sequence (see Sec. 5.4.1.3), leaving behind a μ gradient that generates clear periodic components in ΔP . We found that the analytical expression derived in Sec. 5.3.1 allows to accurately recover the location and sharpness of the μ gradient from the amplitude and periodicity of the components in ΔP . In this mass domain, though the average period spacing does not change substantially with the age, the periodicity of the components does change, and it therefore represents an indicator of the evolutionary state of the star.
- In Sec. 5.4.2 we showed that also extra-mixing processes can alter the behaviour of ΔP , since they affect the size and evolution of the convective core, as well as the sharpness of the μ gradient. We compared models with the same X_c , but computed with and without overshooting (see Sec. 5.4.2.1) and found that in models with small convective cores, or where nuclear reactions take place also in the radiative region, the different size of the fully-mixed region changes the periodicity of the components in ΔP .
- In Sec. 5.4.2.3 we described how chemical mixing can severely affect the amplitude of the periodic components in ΔP . In models where turbulent mixing induced by rotation is considered, the smoother μ profile near the core leads to a discontinuity not in N itself, but in its first derivative: as suggested by the analytical approximation in Sec. 5.3.1, this leads to periodic components in ΔP whose amplitude decreases with the order of the mode. In the case of SPB stars, in particular, we find that the mixing induced by

the typical rotation rates observed (i.e. $\simeq 25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, see e.g. Briquet et al. 2007a), is sufficient to alter significantly the properties of the g-modes spectrum.

- In Sec.5.5 we discussed the difficulties encountered in the asteroseismology of γ Doradus and SPB stars. Even though a frequency resolution sufficient to resolve closely spaced periods will be provided by the forthcoming space-based observations, an asteroseismic inference on the internal structure will only be possible for stars with very slow rotation rates, and with reliably identified pulsation modes. Once these conditions are reached, we will be able to access the wealth of information on internal mixing which, as shown in this work, is carried by the periods of high-order gravity modes in main-sequence objects.

Low-order g modes and modes of mixed p and g character

In Sec. 5.6 we extended our analysis of the effects of extra-mixing processes to low-order gravity modes and mixed modes. We found that turbulent mixing leaves a signature in the oscillation spectrum which differs from that of overshooting, and that can be related to the detailed properties of the sharp variation in N , due to the different mixing processes considered. In the case of β Cephei stars, we found that the turbulent mixing induced by the typical rotation rates observed in these stars is able to significantly change (by a few tenth of a c/d) the oscillation frequencies and, in particular, the frequency difference between non-radial modes of consecutive frequency. A detectability study of this effect, given the current observational uncertainties on the position on HR diagram and chemical composition of the star, remains however to be addressed.

6

α Centauri AB

The results presented in this chapter are published in the following papers:

Miglio, A., Montalbán, J.: *Constraining fundamental stellar parameters using seismology. Application to α Centauri AB*, (2005), A&A, 441, 615,

Montalbán, J., Miglio, A.: *Evolution and seismology of α Centauri*, (2006), Mem SAIT, 77, 472,

where the seismic observational data adopted in the modelling are those by Bouchy & Carrier (2002) and Carrier & Bourban (2003). Since new observations of solar-like oscillations in α Cen A and B have in the meanwhile been published (Bedding et al., 2004; Kjeldsen et al., 2005; Bazot et al., 2007), we describe in Section 6.6 how the models compare with these recent observational data.

6.1 Introduction

α Cen AB is the binary system closest to the Earth ($d=1.34\text{pc}$). It shows an eccentric orbit ($e=0.519$) with a period of almost 80 years (Pourbaix et al., 2002). α Cen A is a G2V star and α Cen B a K1V one, slightly hotter and cooler respectively than the Sun. Thanks to the high apparent brightness ($V_A = -0.01$ and $V_B = 1.33$) and to the large parallax of the components, their stellar parameters are among the best known of any star except the Sun. The binarity, their well determined characteristics and the solar-like oscillations detected in both stars, provide a unique opportunity to test our knowledge on stellar evolution in conditions slightly different from the solar one.

As a consequence, a great number of theoretical studies dealing with α Cen has been published since the one by Flannery & Ayres (1978). In this first study the authors, assuming a solar chemical composition for α Cen AB, were not able to reproduce the observational constraints. They concluded that, to fit the observations, models with twice the solar heavy element abundance were needed: this prediction was later confirmed by detailed abundance analyses. Demarque et al. (1986) analyzed ground-based parallax and orbital measurements and derived the masses of the components ($M_A = 1.09 \pm 0.01 M_\odot$ and $M_B = 0.90 \pm 0.01 M_\odot$). They also computed seismic properties of their models with the aim of comparing them with the report by Fossat et al. (1984) of possible detection of solar-like oscillations in α Cen A, and found no agreement between the observed and model-predicted frequencies.

A successive series of papers addressed whether fitting models of α Cen to the available observational constraints could represent a test of the universality of the mixing-length parameter (α) describing the stellar convection. Noels et al. (1991) introduced a calibration procedure to determine four free parameters in the modelling (X, Z, age and α) by reproducing four observables (the luminosity

and effective temperatures of component A and B). The calibration procedure proposed by the authors is a generalisation of the calibration of solar models, i.e. it is based on the computation of partial derivatives of the observables with respect to the free parameters in the model. The parameters determined by this calibration were $Z = 0.04$, $X = 0.32$, $\alpha = 1.6$ and an age of 5 Gyr. The assumption taken in Noels et al. (1991) of a unique mixing-length parameter α for both components, was relaxed in the study by Edmonds et al. (1992). The authors, considering the observed metallicity as a further constraint, found that the mixing-length parameter in component A is slightly larger than in B, but did not include an uncertainty analysis to determine if the difference is significant. The study by Edmonds et al. (1992) was also the first to consider the effect of helium diffusion in the models. A solution that favours a unique convection parameter for both components was found in Neuforge (1993). Fernandes & Neuforge (1995) modelled α Cen AB with both the mixing-length and the FST theory for convection by Canuto & Mazzitelli (1991, 1992, hereafter CM91,CM92) and concluded that the mixing-length parameter for component B is larger than in component A if the heavy-element mass fraction Z is lower than 0.038. The authors however noticed that the uncertainties in the observational constraints were too large to establish a significant difference between the convection parameters of α Cen A and B.

A revision of the observational constraints adopted in the modelling was provided by Pourbaix et al. (1999). By combining visual and spectroscopic constraints of the orbit they derived new values of the masses of α Cen A and B (respectively $1.16 \pm 0.031 M_{\odot}$ and $0.97 \pm 0.032 M_{\odot}$) which were significantly higher than those previously determined by Demarque et al. (1986) and adopted as constraints in the models until that time ($M_A = 1.09 \pm 0.01 M_{\odot}$ and $M_B = 0.90 \pm 0.01 M_{\odot}$). The revised values of the masses led to a substantially lower age estimate of the system (2.7 Gyr). The main reason for the different masses derived by Demarque et al. (1986) and Pourbaix et al. (1999) resides in the lower parallax derived by the latter (737.0 ± 2.6 mas instead of 750.6 ± 4.6 mas).

In order to estimate the impact on the modelling of the uncertainties on the parallax, Guenther & Demarque (2000) presented a thorough modelling of the α Cen binary system assuming three different values of the parallax: the one determined in Demarque et al. (1986), the Hipparcos parallax (742.12 ± 4.6 mas) and the one determined by Söderhjelm (1999) obtained combining Hipparcos and ground-based observations (747.1 ± 1.2 mas). The authors found that the theoretical estimate of the age of α Cen A depends strongly on the presence of a convective core. If the primary component does not have a convective core (this is the case for models with $Z < \sim 0.03$ on the ZAMS) the age of α Cen AB is 6.8 ± 0.8 Gyr whereas for models with larger Z the age estimate is ~ 1 Gyr larger. They also concluded that the major uncertainty in the age determination is primarily related to the uncertainties in the composition, rather than to the values of the parallax

considered in their study. A further result of Guenther & Demarque (2000) was to show that the mixing-length parameter in α Cen A models is $\sim 10\%$ smaller than in α Cen B models but that the uncertainties in the composition and in the effective temperature needed to be reduced to consider such a difference significant. The authors also discussed in detail the potential usefulness of solar-like oscillations to further constrain the models. They showed that the detection of the large separation of p modes would provide a precise estimate of the radius of the star, whereas the small separation could be used as an age indicator thanks to the additional constraints due to the binarity (α Cen A and B are coeval and have the same initial chemical composition).

Models of α Cen adopting the revised mass determination of Pourbaix et al. (1999) were presented in Morel et al. (2000). In this work the models were calibrated through a χ^2 minimisation that allowed to constrain the model parameters (initial chemical composition, age and two distinct convection parameters for component A and B). The authors have shown that the results of the calibration depend on the convection theory adopted: using the mixing-length theory they derived an age of ~ 2.7 Gyr (in agreement with the findings of Pourbaix et al. 1999), whereas adopting the FST they obtained an age of ~ 4.1 Gyr. They also found that the mixing-length convection parameter in α Cen A is not significantly different than in α Cen B.

In more recent years, in addition to the detection of p modes in α Cen A by Bouchy & Carrier (2002) (see Sec. 6.3.2 for a more detailed description), Pourbaix et al. (2002) reduced the uncertainty on the orbital parameters by adding to the analysis precise radial velocity measurements obtained in the framework of the Anglo-Australian (Butler et al., 2001) and CORALIE (Queloz, 2001) planet search projects. Adopting the parallax derived by Söderhjelm (1999), they provided very precise masses for α Cen A and B ($M_A = 1.105 \pm 0.007 M_\odot$, $M_B = 0.934 \pm 0.006 M_\odot$). These high quality data stimulated new calibrations of the system by Thévenin et al. (2002) and Thoul et al. (2003). The two teams reached different results. While Thévenin et al. (2002) could not fit the seismic data without changing the masses more than 4σ with respect to Pourbaix's data, the second group fitted the α Cen A p-mode spectrum and the spectroscopic constraints using a single value of the mixing length parameter, and with the new values for the masses.

Interferometric measurements with VINCI/VLTI by Kervella et al. (2003) have provided high precision values of the angular diameter of α Cen A and B, and new observations by Carrier & Bourban (2003) have allowed to identify p-mode frequencies also in the B component. These new constraints have been used by Eggenberger et al. (2004). Their calibration, based on a grid of models obtained by varying the mixing-length parameters, the chemical composition, and the age, leads to a stellar model in good agreement with the astrometric, photometric, spec-

troscopic and asteroseismic data, and they assert that “*the global parameters of the α Cen system are now firmly constrained to an age of $t = 6.52 \pm 0.30$ Gyr, an initial helium mass fraction $Y_i = 0.275 \pm 0.010$ and an initial metallicity $(Z/X)_i = 0.0434 \pm 0.0020$ ” and that “*the mixing length parameter α of the B component is larger than the one of the A component*”. These results are quantitatively consistent with those obtained by Thoul et al. (2003), nevertheless, both groups have performed the calibration assuming a given, but different, “physics”.*

The aim of this work is to study, following the theoretical analysis of the utility of seismology to constrain fundamental parameters made by Brown et al. (1994), the dependence of the set of parameters obtained by fitting the observables, on the details of the fitting procedure. That is: *i*) the kind of constraints included in the χ^2 functional that drives the fitting procedure, as well as other effects of their uncertainties, and *ii*) the physics included in the stellar evolution theory. Only in this way we will be able to provide an estimation of the uncertainty in the obtained set of stellar parameters, and to evaluate the degree at which the present data precision can constrain the physics in stellar evolution models.

To do that, and also with the prospect of dealing with a great quantity of seismic data from spatial missions such as COROT (Baglin & The COROT Team, 1998) and KEPLER (e.g. Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 2007) and from new generation spectrograph such as HARPS (Bouchy, 2002) and SOPHIE (Bouchy & The Sophie Team, 2006), we have implemented a non-linear fitting algorithm that performs a simultaneous least-square adjustment of all the observable characteristics, the classical and the seismic features.

The fitting method is described in Sec. 6.2. In Sec. 6.3 we discuss the different sets of classical and seismic observables that will be included in our χ^2 quality function. The physics included in the stellar evolutionary code is summarized in Sec. 6.4. The results of these different combinations of observables and of different physics are presented and discussed in Sec. 6.5. A special effort has been devoted to the problem of stellar convection (Sect 6.5.2). We will try to answer to the question about the universality of the mixing-length parameter, and to study the effect of different convection treatments. We performed different calibrations changing the convection treatment (FST or MLT), as well as different MLT calibrations either with a unique or different α values for each component. The effects of using different equation of state, including or not gravitational settling, and adopting a different solar mixture are discussed in Sec. 6.5.3. In Sec. 6.6 we describe how the most recent observational seismic data (Bedding et al., 2004; Kjeldsen et al., 2005; Bazot et al., 2007) compare with the models presented in the previous sections. Finally, a discussion and a summary of the results are given in Sec. 6.7.

6.2 Calibration method

Usually the approach to analyze stellar oscillation data is rather conventional: *i*) several stellar models that bracket the known observational constraints (typically composition, mass, luminosity, and effective temperature) are computed ; *ii*) p-mode oscillation frequencies are calculated for the models; and *iii*) the model oscillation spectra are compared with the observed one. We believe that a different approach is needed, so that asteroseismology is directly included in the calibration procedure and the results are not biased by a limited/subjective exploration of the parameter space or strongly dependent on an initial guess of the model parameters.

The development and use of objective and efficient procedures to fit stellar models to observations has become of evident utility in particular since seismic constraints are included in the modelling (see e.g. Brown et al., 1994).

Guenther & Brown (2004) have proposed a method that quantifies at which degree the oscillation spectra as obtained from a grid of models parametrised in mass, age and composition reproduce the observations. Models providing a minimum in the χ^2 , defined by the differences between the theoretical and observational frequencies, are selected for an additional inspection in a finer grid. As noted by Guenther & Brown (2004) the first problem in this kind of approach is its computational cost. Moreover the direct fit of the oscillation spectra implies a good knowledge of the surface layers of the star, as that strongly affects the exact frequency values. Guenther & Brown (2004) quantify the uncertainty in the theoretical frequencies due to our poor modelling of the external layers by using the discrepancies between observed and theoretical solar frequencies. But, how good is this estimation for stars with different superficial gravity, chemical composition and age? On the other hand, Eggenberger et al. (2004) use the aforementioned conventional approach, and only in a second and a third phase take into account the asteroseismic data, first the large and small frequency separations ($\Delta\nu$, $\delta\nu$), and then the frequencies.

Here we propose a calibration method that finds the parameters of the system by the minimization of a χ^2 functional including at the same time classical and asteroseismic observables. The parameters of the models are, as usual, the mass, initial chemical composition, age, parameter(s) of convection α . The observables could be chosen among the masses, T_{eff} , L , R , $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, $\Delta\nu$, $\delta\nu$ (or combinations of these frequency differences). Of course, being α Cen a binary system, the same initial chemical composition and age have to be assumed when calibrating components A and B.

We define a quality function measuring the distance between models and observations, that is, a goodness-of-fit measurement by:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{N_o} \frac{(O_i^{\text{obs}} - O_i^{\text{theo}})^2}{(\sigma_i^{\text{obs}})^2} \quad (6.1)$$

where O_i^{obs} , σ_i^{obs} and O_i^{theo} are respectively the observed value, observational uncertainty and theoretical prediction of each of the N_o (A+B components) observables considered.

The choice of the observables included in the objective function is thoroughly described in Section 6.3.

In the general case of a binary system the model that generates the observables and their derivatives has seven free parameters (or six if $\alpha_A = \alpha_B$). The most substantial part of the model consists of a stellar evolution code (CLES, see Sec. 6.4) which takes as inputs the masses of each component (M_A , M_B), the initial chemical composition of the system (Y , Z), the age and the convection mixing-length parameters (α_A , α_B), that in general are assumed to be different for the two stars.

We compute oscillation frequencies for the models by solving the equations of adiabatic oscillations (OSC), and determine $\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$ and $\langle \delta\nu \rangle$ for the degrees $\ell = 0, 1, 2, 3$. This is not done by a least square fit to the computed frequencies, based on the asymptotic properties of low degree modes, but by making the average of the theoretical separations in the domain of observed radial order n ($n = 15 - 25$, for α Cen A, and $n = 17 - 27$ for α Cen B). The observed average separations have been determined from observed frequencies in the same way.

For each component the evolution code provides the stellar luminosity, the radius and the effective temperature, as well as the model quantities required in the subsequent calculations of the oscillation frequencies. In the calibration process, the derivatives of the observable quantities are obtained varying each of the parameters ($M_A, M_B, Z, Y, \alpha_A, \alpha_B$, and the age). We do not derive colors or visual magnitudes, and we do not include orbital elements such as apparent semi-major axis (a'), orbital period (P_{orb}) or parallax. We assume the parallax as determined by Söderhjelm (1999) and the values of observables based on it. The masses, however, are considered as parameters and also as observable quantities in our calibrations.

In the calibration of a binary system the large number of variables involved, both in terms of model parameters and observables, suggests the use of a least-squares based fitting procedure. This is particularly useful in this kind of calibration as we fit at the same time classical and seismological observables without making first a selection based on the HR location of the system.

As shown in Brown et al. (1994) the observable quantities depend on the parameters in a complex way: stellar evolution is not a linear problem. Most of the observables are influenced by several parameters, and hence the connection between observables and parameters that could conceptually seem to us the simplest

one will not always provide the correct results.

6.2.1 Optimization algorithm

We use the gradient-expansion algorithm known as Levenberg-Marquardt method. This algorithm combines the advantages of an expansion method, i.e. rapid convergence close to the minima, with those of the gradient-search, that is, a rapid approach to a far away minimum. This method has as well the strong advantage of being reasonably insensitive to the starting values of the parameters.

At each step the fitting function is linearized calculating numerical derivatives (centered differences) of the observables with respect to each model parameter. The displacement in the parameter space, leading to a lower value of χ^2 , is calculated following the prescription of Bevington & Robinson (2003), p. 161-164 and the iterative procedure is ended when χ^2 no longer changes more than 2%. In calibrations with $M_A, M_B, Z, Y, \alpha_A, \alpha_B$, and the age as model parameters, convergence is typically achieved in 3-4 iterations and at each of them the computation of 16 evolutionary tracks is needed to evaluate centered derivatives. The result of such a local minimization could be sensitive to the initial guess of the parameters; therefore, in order to get a more reliable final solution we perform several runs starting from different points in the parameter space. The effect we find is limited to a variation of the number of iterations needed to reach the minimum χ^2 , whereas the final parameters of the system differ much less than their uncertainty. On the other hand, building a 6-dimensional dense grid of models seems impractical considering the aim of evaluating the effects of using different physical prescriptions in our models (e.g. different equation of state, different metal mixture etc).

It is sometimes nonetheless possible to make fairly direct connections between the observables and the parameters, particularly when one observable is much better determined than the rest. The solution is determined by the parameter that is known with very small uncertainty. The uncertainties in the parameters for these fits are calculated from the diagonal terms in the error matrix (inverse of curvature matrix in the parameter space) and are, in general considerably larger than the uncertainties obtained in the grid- and gradient-search methods. The latter are obtained by finding the change in each parameter to produce as change of χ^2 of 1 from the minimum values, without re-optimizing the fit, while there is a strong suggestion that correlations among the parameters play an important role in fitting (see e.g. Bevington & Robinson, 2003).

6.3 The choice of the observational constraints

6.3.1 Non-asteroseismic constraints

Due to the proximity of the α Cen binary system, the precision on the measurement of its trigonometric parallax is potentially very high. Unfortunately, some discrepancies have appeared among the most recent published values (see Table 10 in Kervella et al., 2003). Guenther & Demarque (2000) studied the uncertainty in the stellar parameters due to the different parallax values. This, indeed affects the determination of mass, luminosity and radius. Following Eggenberger et al. (2004) we adopt $\pi = 747.1 \pm 1.2$ mas (Söderhjelm, 1999) and, therefore, the corresponding mass values determined by Pourbaix et al. (2002): ($M_A = 1.105 \pm 0.007 M_\odot$, $M_B = 0.934 \pm 0.006 M_\odot$) and the radii : ($R_A = 1.224 \pm 0.003 R_\odot$; $R_B = 0.863 \pm 0.005 R_\odot$) (Kervella et al., 2003).

As in the case of the parallax, there is a large scatter in the published values of other quantities, such as T_{eff} , luminosity, and metallicity. We decided to use the same values adopted by Eggenberger et al. (2004) in order to have a reference model. Eggenberger et al. (2004) took as T_{eff} for the component A a value to encompass those given by two spectroscopic determinations, the one from Neuforge-Verheecke & Magain (1997) ($T_{\text{effA}}=5830\pm 30$ K, $T_{\text{effB}}=5255\pm 50$ K), and the one by Morel et al. (2000) based on a re-analysis of Chmielewski et al. (1992) spectra ($T_{\text{effA}}=5790\pm 30$ K, $T_{\text{effB}}=5260\pm 50$ K), used respectively in the α Cen calibrations by Thoul et al. (2003) and Thévenin et al. (2002). We will use the effective temperature as constraint in our minimization method only in one of the calibrations (A1t,B1t, in Table 6.2), since the precise determination of the radius provides a narrower domain in the space of observable quantities. The luminosity values adopted by Eggenberger et al. (2004) come from a new and weighted calibration of previous Geneva photometric data, where they have also coherently taken into account the effective temperatures and the parallax. These values cover the domain considered by Thévenin et al. (2002) that considered an error bar twice smaller, and a lower luminosity for the component B. The luminosity values, directly determined from the adopted radius and effective temperature, are in very good agreement with the those determined by Eggenberger et al. (2004): $L_A/L_\odot = 1.518 \pm 0.06$, $L_B/L_\odot = 0.507 \pm 0.025$. On the other hand, the values determined by Pijpers (2003) for L_A are much larger and only marginally overlap the values considered here.

The precise values of masses and radii provide also precise values of the surface gravity for both stars: $\log g_A=4.305 \pm 0.005$ and $\log g_B=4.536 \pm 0.008$, while the spectroscopic values determined by Neuforge-Verheecke & Magain (1997) are $\log g_A = 4.34 \pm 0.05$ and $\log g_B = 4.51 \pm 0.08$. These values were used by Thoul et al. (2003) to fix the luminosity domain, leading to higher central values and to larger error bars with respect to those determined by Eggenberger et al. (2004) and

	A	B	Ref
M/M_{\odot}	1.105 ± 0.007	0.934 ± 0.006	(1)
T_{eff}	5810 ± 50	5260 ± 50	(1)
R/R_{\odot}	1.224 ± 0.003	0.863 ± 0.005	(1)
L/L_{\odot}	1.522 ± 0.030	0.503 ± 0.020	(1)
Z/X	0.039 ± 0.006	0.039 ± 0.006	(2)

Table 6.1: Non-asteroseismic constraints. References(1): Eggenberger et al. (2004); (2): Thoul et al. (2003).

Thévenin et al. (2002).

Also for the metallicity of both components there is no complete agreement in the literature: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{A}} = 0.20 \pm 0.02$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{B}} = 0.23 \pm 0.03$ from Morel et al. (2000), and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{A}} = 0.25 \pm 0.02$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{B}} = 0.24 \pm 0.03$ from Neuforge-Verheecke & Magain (1997). The uncertainty in the observable Z/X is quite large, if we take into account also the 10% in the $(Z/X)_{\odot}$. We have taken the value adopted by Thoul et al. (2003), that is $Z/X = 0.039 \pm 0.006$, the same for both stars. The detailed abundance analysis of α Cen A and B carried out in Neuforge-Verheecke & Magain (1997) suggested no evidence for a different metal mixture relative to the sun, therefore all our models were computed assuming the solar mixture by Grevesse & Noels (1993), except for the calibration (A5,B5) in which we have considered the recently determined solar metal abundances (Asplund et al., 2004, 2005) that implies $(Z/X)_{\odot} = 0.0177$.

The non-asteroseismic constraints used in this work are summarized in Table 6.1.

6.3.2 Seismic constraints

Several groups had made thorough attempts to detect the signature of p-mode oscillations in α Cen A, but their results were not confirmed. Only recently Bouchy & Carrier (2002), from high precision radial velocity measurements with the CORALIE echelle spectrograph have yielded a clear detection of p-mode oscillation, and identified several modes between 1800 and 2900 μHz , and with an envelope amplitude of about 31 cm s^{-1} . Assuming that frequency modes $\nu_{n\ell}$ satisfy the simplified asymptotic relation (Tassoul, 1980):

$$\nu_{\ell n} \approx \Delta\nu_0 \left(n + \frac{\ell}{2} + \epsilon \right) - \ell(\ell + 1) \frac{\delta\nu_{02}}{6} \quad (6.2)$$

and assuming the parameter ϵ near the solar one (1.5) they estimated: $\Delta\nu_0 = 105.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$, $\delta\nu_{02} = 5.6 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{Hz}$, $\epsilon = 1.40 \pm 0.02$ and identified 28 p-modes with degree $\ell = 0, 1, 2$ and order between $n = 15$ and $n = 25$.

Notice that the given errors come from the autocorrelation algorithm, but we must keep in mind that their frequency resolution is only $0.93 \mu\text{Hz}$, and that they derive an uncertainty in the frequency determination equal to $0.46 \mu\text{Hz}$. They also point out that an error of $\pm 1.3 \mu\text{Hz}$ could have been introduced at some identified mode frequency, that could explain the dispersion of mode frequency around the asymptotic relation. In particular higher observational uncertainty could affect mainly the $\ell = 2$ modes that determine the value of $\delta\nu_{02}$ for the lower and higher frequency $\delta\nu_{02}(n=16 \text{ and } 25)$.

Carrier & Bourban (2003) have also detected solar-like oscillations in the fainter component, α Cen B. Only twelve frequencies, between 3000 and 4600 μHz have been kept in the final list of identified p-modes, four of them with a detection level lower than 3σ , and it is recommended to take them with caution. As for component A the frequency resolution is $0.93 \mu\text{Hz}$. The large and small separations, determined by autocorrelation of the asymptotic relation, are respectively $\Delta\nu_0 = 161.1 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $\delta\nu_{02} = 8.7 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{Hz}$. We must note here that the value derived for $\delta\nu_{02}$ comes from only few p-modes. In fact, from their frequency table is only possible to obtain two values: $\delta\nu_{02}(n = 21) = 10.0 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $\delta\nu_{02}(n = 23) = 7.0 \mu\text{Hz}$. Carrier & Bourban (2003) expect a rotational splitting $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{Hz}$ that, given the frequency resolution, could imply an increase of the uncertainty of frequencies for modes of degree $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$.

Recently, the result of new observations of solar-like oscillations in both component of the system have been published (Bedding et al., 2004; Kjeldsen et al., 2005; Fletcher et al., 2006; Bazot et al., 2007). Our computations have been done before these values were available, therefore we will not take them into account in our calibration. We will nonetheless describe in Sec. 6.6 how these new observations compare with our models.

How should these seismological observations be used to constrain our stellar models? The classical way is to use the large and small separations to characterize the power spectrum of solar-like oscillations. The standard asymptotic theory of stellar oscillations (Tassoul, 1980) relates the averages values of high-radial order / low-degree small and large separations to conditions in the stellar core ($\delta\nu$) and to the mean density of the star ($\Delta\nu$). Recently Guenther & Brown (2004) and Metcalfe (2005) have proposed to use directly the p-mode frequencies as observables to constrain the stellar models.

Brown et al. (1994) theoretically analyzed the case in which the individual frequencies are included as observables. Their purpose was to illustrate the potential loss of information resulting from representing the spectra in terms of the large and small separations derived from the expected asymptotic behavior. The dominant source of frequency changes is very close to the stellar surface. It could be difficult to disentangle these effects from the uncertainties in the treatment of the physics of the outer layers, where non-adiabaticity and dynamics effects of convection have

to be taken into account.

The oscillation frequencies, the large and small separations depend on the structure of both the inner and the outer layers of a star, so model fitting and testing techniques to probe the interior structure of the stars are dependent on our having a good understanding of the structure of the outer layers. But these are just the layers where our ignorance is greatest; non-adiabatic convection is important but not understood, the oscillations are non-adiabatic in the surface layers and the structure of real stellar atmosphere is poorly understood. For example the oscillation frequencies predicted by the reference solar models (S96)(Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1996) differ from the observed values up to $10\mu\text{Hz}$ at the higher end of the observed frequency range.

In a first step, we will include as seismic constraints in our fitting algorithm the combinations of frequencies: the large

$$\Delta\nu_{n,\ell} = \nu_{n,\ell} - \nu_{n-1,\ell}$$

and small

$$\delta\nu_{n,\ell} = \nu_{n,\ell} - \nu_{n-1,\ell+2}$$

frequency separations defined from the identified p-mode frequencies for both components.

As discussed in Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1995a) and Di Mauro et al. (2003), care has to be taken when considering as a constraint in the modelling the large separation, as its averaged value at high frequencies could be influenced by near-surface effects as well. This is in fact the case when comparing the observed and the predicted low-degree large separations of the Sun (see Fig. 6.1), where the disagreement of the order of a μHz is related to a simplified treatment of the model outer layers.

With the aim of checking whether the calibration we perform considering $\langle\Delta\nu\rangle$ and $\langle\delta\nu\rangle$ is not biased by a simplified treatment of the outer structure in our models, we considered the effect on the calibration of choosing as seismic constraint r_{02} , the ratio between the small and large frequency separations defined by:

$$r_{02}(n) = \frac{\delta\nu_{n,0}}{\Delta\nu_{n,1}} = \frac{\nu_{n,0} - \nu_{n-1,2}}{\nu_{n,1} - \nu_{n-1,1}} \quad (6.3)$$

for 6 different orders n of the component A. This combination of frequencies, as presented in Roxburgh & Vorontsov (2003b), is to a great accuracy independent of the outer layers of the star, and therefore represents a reliable indicator of the conditions in the deep stellar interior.

Figure 6.1: Solar large frequency difference $\Delta\nu_{n,1}$ (upper panel) from standard seismic solar model S96 (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1996) (solid line), compared to the observational solar large separation (dots) (Basu et al., 1997). Lower panel: as upper panel but for the ratio r_{02} .

6.4 Stellar models

All stellar model sequences are calculated using the CLES code (Code Liégeois d'Evolution Stellaire). The opacity tables are those of OPAL96 (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) complemented at $T < 6000$ K with Alexander & Ferguson (1994) opacities. The relative mixture of heavier than helium elements, used in the opacity and equation of state tables, is the solar one according to Grevesse & Noels (1993). The nuclear energy generation routines are based on the cross sections by Caughlan & Fowler (1988) and screening factors from Salpeter (1954). CLES allows the choice between two equations of state: CEFF (Christensen-Dalsgaard & Däppen, 1992) and OPAL01 (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002). Most of the models have been computed using OPAL01, but we have also made a calibration using CEFF to study the capability of seismology to constrain the EoS.

All our stellar models were obtained from evolutionary tracks including the pre-main sequence (PMS) phase, and ending at ~ 9 Gyr. The stellar models have approximately 1200 shells, the last one corresponding to $T=T_{\text{eff}}$ as determined using as boundary conditions those given by the Kurucz (1998) atmosphere models. Furthermore, for the computation of oscillations we have added atmospheric layers from $T = T_{\text{eff}}$ up to $\tau = 10^{-4}$.

We have computed models where the convection is treated both using the Mixing Length Theory (MLT Böhm-Vitense, 1958) with the formalism described in Cox & Giuli (1968), and the Full Spectrum of Turbulence (FST Canuto et al., 1996) with a formalism similar to the one used by Morel et al. (2000) or Bernkopf (1998). That means convective fluxes as given by Canuto et al. (1996), but another prescription of the scale length. The parameter α of the MLT and the corresponding in the FST are considered as free parameters of the model calibration, and the values obtained are compared with the values required in the solar calibration for the same physics.

Finally we have computed stellar models with and without gravitational settling of helium and metals. The microscopic diffusion formulation is that given by Thoul et al. (1994), solving the Burgers (1969) equations for H, He and Z and thus considering diffusion due both to thermal and concentration gradients. We also assume complete ionization and the effect of radiative acceleration is ignored. This assumption is completely justified for the precision of the models and for the masses considered (Turcotte et al., 1998).

6.5 Results

In Table 6.2 we list all the fits of the binary system α Cen. The calibrations differ in the choice of the observables included in the objective function (χ^2) and in the used physics. The first column in Table 6.2 identifies the models, the second, third and

fourth columns describe the physics; the fifth one resumes the characteristic of the seismic and non-seismic constraints used in the calibration process, while all the following columns give the values of the parameters (and the uncertainty in each of them) providing in each case the minimum χ^2 . The values of the observable quantities derived for each set of parameters is listed in Table 6.3. There, the last column χ_R^2 is the the value of the “reduced” χ^2 , defined as:

$$\chi_R^2 = \frac{\chi^2}{N_o - N_p} \quad (6.4)$$

were N_o is the number of observables and N_p the number of model parameters.

In the three following subsections we shall analyze the effect of changing the non-seismic constraints, the seismic constraints and finally the physics used in the models, that is, a different treatment of convection, different equation of state, different solar mixture, models including or not gravitational settling, and the effect of considering overshooting in our models.

Fig. 6.2 shows the HR location of each of these fitted models. We have indicated the error boxes in T_{eff} , $\log L/L_\odot$, and radius, corresponding to 1σ (solid line), and 2σ (dashed-line).

Figure 6.2: HR diagram location of models with stellar parameters from differing fits. Labels corresponds to those in Tables 6.2, and 6.3. Upper and lower panel correspond respectively to components A and B. The error boxes for T_{eff} , $\log L/L_{\odot}$, and radii correspond to 1σ (solid line) and 2σ (dashed-line)

Figure 6.3: Large (upper panels) and small (lower panels) separations for the A (left) and B (right) components of α Cen system. Points represent the observational values with their error bars assuming an error in frequencies equal to 2σ . All these curves correspond to calibrations performed including in the χ^2 functional the average of the observational large and small separations, but different classical observational constraints: masses fixed to the value given by Pourbaix et al. (2002) and T_{eff} (solid lines); radii (dotted-lines); and masses variable as parameter and radii (dashed-lines). All the curves were computed from stellar models including gravitational settling, and MLT treatment of convection with two mixing length adjustable parameters. For clarity only $\ell = 1$ theoretical large separations are shown in the upper panels.

Model	Conv	Diff	EoS	fitting	M/M _⊙	ϵ	α	ϵ	Age	ϵ	Y ₀	ϵ	Z ₀	ϵ
A1t	MLT	Y	OPAL	$T_{\text{eff}}, M_{\text{fix}}$	1.105		1.99	0.11	7.0	0.5	0.273	0.016	0.0316	0.003
B1t	MLT	Y	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.934		2.22	0.07	7.0	0.5	0.273	0.016	0.0316	0.003
A1r	MLT	Y	OPAL	M_{fix}	1.105		2.00	0.11	6.8	0.5	0.276	0.015	0.0325	0.003
B1r	MLT	Y	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.934		2.24	0.07	6.8	0.5	0.276	0.015	0.0325	0.003
A1nd	MLT	N	OPAL	M_{fix}	1.105		1.84	0.10	7.1	0.6	0.265	0.015	0.0284	0.003
B1nd	MLT	N	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.934		1.99	0.05	7.1	0.6	0.265	0.015	0.0284	0.003
A1e	MLT	Y	CEFF	M_{fix}	1.105		1.93	0.10	6.7	0.6	0.281	0.015	0.0324	0.003
B1e	MLT	Y	CEFF	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.934		2.08	0.06	6.7	0.6	0.281	0.015	0.0324	0.003
A1-3	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{fix}},$	1.105		1.86	0.06	6.0	0.4	0.277	0.017	0.0302	0.003
B1-3	MLT	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.934		2.18	0.05	6.0	0.4	0.277	0.017	0.0302	0.003
A2	MLT	Y	OPAL	M_{var}	1.104	0.006	1.96	0.11	6.4	0.6	0.282	0.016	0.0326	0.003
B2	MLT	Y	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.926	0.005	2.11	0.10	6.4	0.6	0.282	0.016	0.0326	0.003
A2c	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{var}}, \alpha_A = \alpha_B$	1.107	0.005	1.78	0.08	5.4	0.5	0.284	0.016	0.0305	0.003
B2c	MLT	Y	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.919	0.004	"	"	5.4	0.5	0.284	0.016	0.0305	0.003
A2f	FST	Y	OPAL	M_{var}	1.105	0.006	0.77	0.05	6.4	0.6	0.282	0.016	0.0325	0.003
B2f	FST	Y	OPAL	$\langle \Delta\nu \rangle, \langle \delta\nu \rangle$	0.927	0.005	0.89	0.05	6.4	0.6	0.282	0.016	0.0325	0.003
A3	MLT	Y	OPAL	M_{var}	1.110	0.006	1.90	0.07	5.8	0.2	0.284	0.014	0.0322	0.003
B3	MLT	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.927	0.005	2.05	0.08	5.8	0.2	0.284	0.014	0.0322	0.003
A3c	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{var}}, \alpha_A = \alpha_B$	1.113	0.006	1.95	0.05	5.8	0.5	0.276	0.017	0.0317	0.003
B3c	MLT	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.922	0.004	"	"	5.8	0.5	0.276	0.017	0.0317	0.003
A3α _⊙	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{var}}, \alpha = \alpha_{\odot}$	1.114	0.006	1.91		5.7	0.2	0.283	0.010	0.0314	0.002
B3α _⊙	MLT	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.921	0.004	"		5.7	0.2	0.283	0.010	0.0314	0.002
A3f	FST	Y	OPAL	M_{var}	1.110	0.006	0.74	0.03	5.8	0.2	0.285	0.015	0.0323	0.003
B3f	FST	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.927	0.005	0.86	0.03	5.8	0.2	0.285	0.015	0.0323	0.003
A3nd	MLT	N	OPAL	M_{var}	1.108	0.006	1.84	0.07	6.3	0.4	0.270	0.015	0.0281	0.003
B3nd	MLT	N	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.929	0.005	1.99	0.07	6.3	0.4	0.270	0.015	0.0281	0.003
A3e	MLT	Y	CEFF	M_{var}	1.109	0.006	1.85	0.07	5.7	0.3	0.288	0.015	0.0322	0.003
B3e	MLT	Y	CEFF	$r_{02}(n)$	0.927	0.005	1.93	0.07	5.7	0.3	0.288	0.015	0.0322	0.003
A4	OV	Y	OPAL	M_{var}	1.112	0.006	1.77	0.05	5.2	0.2	0.285	0.015	0.0299	0.003
B4	OV	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.925	0.005	1.98	0.07	5.2	0.2	0.285	0.015	0.0299	0.003
A5	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{var}}, A04 \text{ mix}$	1.109	0.006	1.74	0.06	5.9	0.3	0.280	0.013	0.0239	0.002
B5	MLT	Y	OPAL	$r_{02}(n)$	0.927	0.005	1.84	0.07	5.9	0.3	0.280	0.013	0.0239	0.002
Ans	MLT	Y	OPAL	$M_{\text{var}},$	1.105	0.007	2.40	0.33	8.9	1.8	0.259	0.021	0.0340	0.003
Bns	MLT	Y	OPAL	No Seismo	0.934	0.006	2.61	0.31	8.9	1.8	0.259	0.021	0.0340	0.003

Table 6.2: Sets of parameters of fitted models. Meaning of numeric labels: 1 (fixed masses and $\Delta\nu$, $\delta\nu$ as seismic constraints); 2 (as 1 but with variable masses); 3 (as 2 but using $r_{02}(n)$ as seismic constraint); 4 (as 3 but including convective overshooting) and 5 (as 3 but using Asplund et al. (2005) instead of Grevese & Noels (1993)). Meaning of alphabetic labels: nd (non diffusion models); f (FST convection treatment); e (CEFF EoS instead of OPAL01 one); c (a unique mixing-length parameter); ns (fit without seismic constraints); for case 1, t refers to T_{eff} as constraint, and r to radius as constraint.

Model	M/M_{\odot}	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	$(Z/X)_s$	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	R/R_{\odot}	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	T_{eff}	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	L/L_{\odot}	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	$\Delta\nu$	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	$\delta\nu$	$\chi^2_{R_i}$	χ^2_R
A1t	1.105		0.037	0.06	1.234		5764	0.17	1.508	0.04	105.7	0.01	4.95	0.66	1.52
B1t	0.934		0.039	0.00	0.874		5280	0.03	0.534	0.44	161.1	0.	9.22	0.1	
A1r	1.105		0.038	0.02	1.227	0.20	5770		1.498	0.13	106.5	0.52	5.07	0.53	2.80
B1r	0.934		0.041	0.00	0.872	0.67	5289		0.533	0.48	161.6	0.11	9.33	0.14	
A1nd	1.105		0.040	0.00	1.227	0.17	5780		1.508	0.05	106.6	0.56	5.34	0.27	2.27
B1nd	0.934		0.040	0.00	0.872	0.66	5258		0.521	0.17	161.7	0.13	9.60	0.24	
A1e	1.105		0.038	0.02	1.228	0.24	5772		1.500	0.10	106.5	0.46	5.16	0.43	2.64
B1e	0.934		0.041	0.01	0.872	0.66	5286		0.533	0.44	161.6	0.44	9.42	0.17	
A1-3	1.105		0.035	0.07	1.224	0.00	5767		1.488	0.16	106.5		5.77	0.99	2.08
B1-3	0.934		0.038	0.01	0.871	0.29	5315		0.543	0.51	161.6	0.04	9.85		
A2	1.104	0.00	0.039	0.01	1.226	0.13	5782		1.509	0.04	106.6	0.55	5.35	0.26	2.20
B2	0.926	0.32	0.042	0.01	0.870	0.38	5259		0.520	0.12	161.6	0.09	9.72	0.30	
A2c	1.107	0.01	0.036	0.07	1.227	0.22	5778		1.508	0.04	106.6	0.45	6.28	0.03	2.89
B2c	0.919	0.99	0.040	0.00	0.870	0.37	5210		0.501	0.00	161.0	0.00	10.54	0.69	
A2f	1.105	0.00	0.039	0.01	1.226	0.12	5784		1.510	0.03	106.4	0.32	5.35	0.27	1.80
B2f	0.927	0.28	0.041	0.01	0.869	0.28	5261		0.519	0.13	161.6	0.07	9.72	0.29	
A3	1.110	0.06	0.038	0.01	1.224	0.00	5791		1.512	0.01	106.6		5.87	0.94	1.46
B3	0.927	0.18	0.042	0.02	0.869	0.16	5259		0.518	0.07	161.4	0.03	10.16		
A3c	1.113	0.17	0.038	0.02	1.223	0.01	5819		1.540	0.04	106.8		5.77	0.87	1.67
B3c	0.922	0.40	0.041	0.00	0.870	0.16	5206		0.497	0.01	161.1	0.00	10.22		
A3 α_{\odot}	1.114	0.15	0.038	0.02	1.224	0.00	5807		1.529	0.00	106.8		5.94	0.75	1.60
B3 α_{\odot}	0.921	0.47	0.041	0.01	0.869	0.15	5190		0.491	0.04	160.7	0.02	10.35		
A3f	1.110	0.06	0.038	0.01	1.224	0.00	5790		1.511	0.02	106.5		5.85	0.92	1.40
B3f	0.927	0.16	0.042	0.01	0.868	0.12	5260		0.518	0.07	161.4	0.02	10.14		
A3nd	1.108	0.02	0.040	0.00	1.224	0.00	5795		1.516	0.01	106.5		5.90	0.95	1.31
B3nd	0.929	0.10	0.040	0.00	0.869	0.19	5240		0.511	0.02	161.6	0.04	10.16		
A3e	1.109	0.05	0.038	0.01	1.224	0.00	5792		1.514	0.01	106.6		5.89	0.95	1.45
B3e	0.927	0.16	0.042	0.01	0.869	0.17	5256		0.517	0.06	161.5	0.03	10.17		
A4	1.112	0.13	0.036	0.05	1.224	0.00	5782		1.503	0.05	106.7		5.99	1.16	1.96
B4	0.925	0.27	0.039	0.0	0.869	0.15	5275		0.524	0.13	161.5	0.02	10.56		
A5	1.109	0.04	0.028	0.02	1.224	0.00	5791		1.513	0.01	106.7		5.86	0.95	1.51
B5	0.927	0.17	0.030	0.01	0.869	0.20	5251		0.516	0.05	161.6	0.05	10.12		
Ans	1.105		0.039		1.224		5800		1.521		107.0		3.57		0.06
Bns	0.934		0.041		0.863		5238		0.502		164.3		8.27		

Table 6.3: Observable quantities predicted from the sets of parameters in Table 6.2

6.5.1 Effect of classic and seismic observable quantities

A first calibration (A1r,B1r) was performed including in the χ^2 function the luminosity, the radii and the actual $(Z/X)_s$, as well as the average large and small frequency separations (computed as described in Sec. 6.2) for each component. The model parameters are the initial chemical composition (Y_0, Z_0) , the mixing length parameters (α_A, α_B) and the age (τ) . In this calibration we consider, following Eggenberger et al. (2004), that the masses are perfectly determined, and we assume the mass of each component to be fixed to its observational central value, as given Pourbaix et al. (2002). The parameters providing the minimum χ^2 are: $\tau = 6.8 \pm 0.5$ Gyr, $\alpha_A=2.00$, $\alpha_B=2.24$, $Y_0=0.276$ and $Z_0=0.0325$. We note that these results are in complete agreement with those obtained by Eggenberger et al. (2004): $\tau = 6.5 \pm 0.2$ Gyr, $Z_0 = 0.0302$, $Y_0 = 0.275$, and also their value for the mixing-length parameter of α Cen B is $\sim 10\%$ larger than α_A .

This agreement is not surprising, as similar observational constraints were considered. It strengthens the results obtained, since a different calibration procedure and different stellar evolution codes (with different equation of state, treatment of diffusion and treatment of sub-photospheric boundary conditions) were used, and it provides us with a good reference model to study the dependence of the calibrated stellar parameters on the choice of observable quantities and of the physics.

The observational values of the masses given by Pourbaix et al. (2002), though precisely determined, should be treated as observables and therefore introduced, with their error bars, in the definition of the χ^2 and allowed to be changed during the calibration. M_A and M_B are considered both as parameters and observables in a second set of fittings (A2,B2; A2f,B2f). The readjustment of parameters leads to a decrease of M_B which is 1.5σ smaller than the value determined by Pourbaix et al. (2002), and to a decrease of age ($\tau = 6.4 \pm 0.6$ Gyr instead of 6.8 ± 0.5 Gyr). The location of α Cen B in the HR diagram has significantly improved compared with (A1r,B1r) (Fig. 6.2) and $\langle \Delta\nu_A \rangle$ is also better reproduced (Fig. 6.3), leading to an overall lower χ_R^2 compared with the equivalent fitting with fixed masses.

Even including the stellar masses among the parameters, we are not able to improve significantly the fit of radii and large separations. Actually the large separation is strongly dependent on radius ($\Delta\nu \propto (M/R^3)^{1/2}$), and, given the high precision of radius data, the procedure privileges sets of parameters providing the radii within 1σ (for A), and 1.5σ (for B) to detriment of a too high large separation: $\Delta\nu_A$ is always around $106.6 \mu\text{Hz}$ instead of $105.5 \mu\text{Hz}$. In order to relax the constraints, we have performed a fitting including T_{eff} 's among the observables instead of the radii (A1t,B1t). This fitting provided a small χ_R^2 thanks to the good match of large separation values. However, the radii (not included in the χ^2 function) are systematically larger (by more than 2σ) than Kervella et al. (2003) ones. The large separation is very much affected by the external layers properties, such as either the description of the super-adiabatic region in the upper boundary

of the convective zone, or the non-adiabatic processes (not taken into account either in the stellar models or in the oscillation code). An inspection of frequencies predicted for these models (Fig. 6.7) shows that even if the fit of $\Delta\nu_A$ is almost perfect, the frequencies show a shift of $25 \mu\text{Hz}$ with respect to the values determined by Bouchy & Carrier (2002). On the other hand, sets of parameters with a better fit of the radii reduce significantly the shift of frequencies.

The small separation for the A component (Fig. 6.3) suggest that seismic observables would privilege younger models, whereas one of the two values of $\delta\nu_B$ ($n = 23$) and the classical observables tend to a high value of the age. In fact, in our calibration (Ans,Bns) where only classical observable have been taken into account for the fit, we obtain a very good agreement for masses, radii, luminosity and effective temperature (not taken as observable) for both components, and the age is $\tau = 8.9 \pm 1.8 \text{ Gyr}$.

Though the small separation averaged value of component A is well reproduced by our models, the slope of $\delta\nu$ as a function of ν differs from the theoretical prediction. One could argue that this could be a consequence of taking as observable the average value of $\delta\nu$. Roxburgh & Vorontsov (2003b, and references therein), show that the Tassoul asymptotic result gives a poor fit both to the small separations of stellar models and to the observed values for the Sun, and that a better fit is obtained by using the ratios of small and the large separations ($r_{02}(n)$). This ratio depends only on the inner phase shifts which are determined solely by the interior structure of the star and are uninfluenced by the unknown structure of the outer layers.

We have performed a similar fitting using six observational values of the ratio r_{02} as seismic constraints for the A component. Unfortunately, the p-modes identified for B component do not allow us to define any value of r_{02} , we decided, therefore, to take as seismic constraint the average large separation. The first thing to be noticed, when comparing the new set of parameters (A3,B3) with the one based on average large and small separation for both components (A2,B2), is a difference in the resulting age of about 1 Gyr. We also see that, by fitting r_{02} , we get a good fit of $\delta\nu_{02}$ for both stars (Fig. 6.4). The large separation is slightly higher than the observational one, as we obtained in (A2,B2) and (A1r,B1r).

In Fig. 6.7 we can see also the effect on the p-mode frequencies, the model (A3,B3) providing better fit to the observational ones, than the model (A2,B2).

Notice that the parameter set (A3,B3) was determined without taking into account the small separation for the B component. Theoretical $\langle\delta\nu\rangle$ is $\sim 10.15 \mu\text{Hz}$, that is close to the new observational value ($10.1 \mu\text{Hz}$) by Kjeldsen & Bedding (2004). We wonder whether the high age obtained by taking $\langle\delta\nu_B\rangle$ as given by the average of two points (Carrier & Bourban, 2003) is only a consequence of the low value imposed to $\langle\delta\nu_B\rangle$. In fact, a different calibration performed using the small and large separations as observables, but taking only $\delta\nu_B$ ($n = 21$) instead of the

Figure 6.4: As Fig. 6.3 but for models computed using different approach for convection: MLT with two mixing length parameters (solid line); FST (dashed lines); MLT with $\alpha_A = \alpha_B$ (dotted lines); and MLT with $\alpha_A = \alpha_B = \alpha_\odot$ (dash-dotted lines) Large and small separations are derived from stellar models, but the fitting is performed using the ratios r_{02} for component A and $\Delta\nu$ for component B.

average of two available values, provides an age of 6.0 Gyr, in good agreement with r_{02} (A3,B3) fittings, and quite younger than (A2,B2) models.

Finally, we have also used r_{02} but without varying the masses. Again, the age is of the order of 6.0 Gyr, but now, the mixing-length parameters needed for both stars are quite different (by 17%).

The fits reported in Table 6.3 could indicate an inconsistency between the seismic and classical observables. Actually for component B the resulting radii are larger than the observed ones by more than $\sim 1\sigma$ or $\sim 2\sigma$ and the masses are smaller by more than $\sim 1\sigma$ or $\sim 2\sigma$ with respect to the values observationally derived. These results could be interpreted as a systematic error in the radii and/or in the mass determination. A calibration performed with a free M_B parameter/observable, leads to $M_B = 0.911 M_\odot$ and $R_B = 0.863 R_\odot$. The other parameters do not significantly change. This mass value would imply a systematic error of $\sim 4\sigma$ that, given the available high precision data, does not seem reliable. On the other hand, if R_B is let free, the fit of the other observables provides $R_B = 0.871 R_\odot$ instead of $0.863 R_\odot$, and a M_B value within 1σ from the observed

one. It must be notice, however, that these fits have included $\Delta\nu_B$ in the χ^2 functional. To check if the large radius is only a consequence of $\Delta\nu_B$, we calibrate the system adopting as seismic constraints $r_{02}(n)$ for component A, and $\delta\nu(n = 21)$ for component B. In this case we are able to fit the radii and masses of both components within 1σ , but $\langle\Delta\nu_B\rangle$ is more than $+3\text{-}\sigma$ far away from the observational value, and the predicted frequencies are $\sim 40 \mu\text{Hz}$ larger than observed ones. A priori, we cannot rule out a larger uncertainty in the observed radius. Actually in the observational radius determination there are implicit a definition of stellar radius (that is not necessarily the same than that used in stellar modelling) and an assumption about the limb darkening law and the atmosphere models. How much the stellar radius is affected by these assumptions? Kervella (2005, private communication) claims that these effects are much smaller than other errors intrinsic to the measurement method and already taken into account.

6.5.2 Effect of the treatment of convection

It is well known that one of the weak points of stellar evolution models is the treatment of convection. The “standard model” of convection adopted in stellar evolution is the mixing length theory (MLT) where turbulence is described by a relatively simple model that contains essentially one adjustable parameter: the mixing length $\Lambda = \alpha H_p$ (H_p being the local pressure scale height and α an unconstrained parameter). The value of this parameter determines the radius of the star and the behavior of the super-adiabatic region in the outer boundary of the stellar convective zone. The calibration of a stellar code using the solar radius and solar luminosity provides the value of the mixing-length parameter (α_\odot) which in turn is usually used to model other stars with the same physics. A question arises: can stars of different masses, initial chemical composition and evolutionary status be modeled with a unique α ? If the answer is negative, how reliable is the shape of the isochrones determined with a unique α ?

α Cen offers a unique opportunity of testing our assumption about α and, therefore, our simplified way of overcoming the complex problem of convection in stars. The question of the universality of the mixing-length parameter has been approached many times in the past (Noels et al., 1991; Edmonds et al., 1992; Lydon et al., 1993; Neuforge, 1993; Morel et al., 2000; Fernandes & Neuforge, 1995; Guenther & Demarque, 2000). Some attempts of calibrating α Cen A&B in luminosity and radii using MLT theory suggest different values of α for each component and different from the α_\odot , while others favor similar values for both components, or conclude that the uncertainties in masses and radii as well as the chemical composition should be reduced significantly before being able to draw firm a conclusion on whether the MLT parameter is unique or not (Lydon et al., 1993; Andersen, 1991; Guenther & Demarque, 2000). Nowadays, the high preci-

sion with which we know masses and radii for α Cen A&B allows to analyze again this problem. The frequencies are very sensitive to R and therefore to α , and the difference between the observed frequencies (ν_{obs}) and the theoretical ones (ν_{theo}) is highly affected by how the super-adiabatic zone is described (see e.g. Schlattl et al., 1997).

In order to analyze these questions we have made several fits of the α Cen observable quantities by using MLT with *i)* $\alpha_A \neq \alpha_B$ as free parameters; *ii)* $\alpha_A = \alpha_B$ free parameter; and *iii)* $\alpha_A = \alpha_B = \alpha_{\odot}$ fixed; and *iv)* since Morel et al. (2000) presented also controversial results when comparing calibrations for α Cen using MLT or FST, we shall analyze as well the effect of using the FST treatment of convection.

6.5.2.1 MLT versus FST

Mimicking the spectral distribution of eddies by one “average” eddy, such as MLT theory does, has critical consequences on the computation of MLT fluxes. Canuto (1996) shows that in the limit of highly efficient convection MLT underestimates the convective flux, and on the contrary, in the low efficiency limit, MLT overestimates the convective flux. FST models attempt to overcome the one-eddy approximation by using a turbulence model to compute the full spectrum of a turbulent convective flow. As consequence, the convective flux is ~ 10 times larger than the MLT one in the limit of high efficiency, and ~ 0.3 in the limit of low efficiency. This behavior yields, in the super-adiabatic region at the top of a convective zone, steeper temperature gradients for FST than for solar-tuned MLT. The mixing length used in FST treatment is in general defined as the distance from a given point to the boundary of the convective zone. However, the FST fluxes have also been used combined with other definitions of mixing length. For instance, Bernkopf (1998), use the FST fluxes with a mixing length $\Lambda = \alpha^* H_p$ with $\alpha^* < 1$. Morel et al. (2000) use also this kind of description of FST convection with CM91 for the fluxes. Here we will use this prescription of FST treatment of convection, with the fluxes by Canuto et al. (1996) instead of CM(91,92). The main difference is in the temperature gradient, steeper in CM than in CGM96, but both, in any case, much steeper than the MLT one. Morel et al. (2000) found significant differences in the fitted parameters (in particular a 1.5 Gyr difference in the age) when investigating the effect of using a different theory of convection in the modelling of α Centauri. This is rather surprising since the treatment of convection affects only the very external layers of the star, and such an important effect on the age of the star is not expected.

The convection parameters that result from our fits are, as in the case of the calibration with MLT, close to the parameter needed to calibrate the Sun (0.753). Furthermore, in comparing the models (A3,B3) with (A3f,B3f) ones, we do not observe any difference in the parameters of the models fitting the system α Cen

using MLT or FST. In principle this is a logic behavior since we considered as seismological observable the $r_{02}(n)$ (Roxburgh & Vorontsov, 2003b) ratio, and this quantity is independent of surface properties of the model. However, also the sets of parameters (A2,B2) and (A2f,B2f) determined by using large and small frequency separations as constraints, are in fact the same, independently of the convection description used.

We would expect, like in the Sun, a decrease of the difference between theoretical and observational frequencies in the high frequency domain when FST is used. However, for our binary system, the improvement provided by FST treatment with respect to MLT is quite small.

For α Cen A the improvement is of the order of 4 μHz at 3000 μHz , while for the B component, this effect does not appear clearly (Fig.6.7). In fact, the difference between MLT and FST frequencies is due to a different radius and mass. If we adopt for M_B and R_B the values determined in the calibration B3 as the real ones, and compute a new FST calibration, we find that the difference between the MLT and FST frequencies in the observational domain (3000-4600 μHz) goes from 0 to 3 μHz , while the difference in frequencies between B3 and B3f introduced by the different mass and radius is of the order of 8 μHz (see Fig. 6.5).

6.5.2.2 One or two different values for the mixing length parameter?

Several times in the literature it has been addressed the question if convection in the two components of α Centauri should be described with distinct mixing-length parameters and, if, given the observational uncertainties, the inferred difference between mixing length parameters is significant (see e.g Eggenberger et al. (2004), where an exhaustive review on previous calibrations is also presented). It was, in fact, already suggested in Guenther & Demarque (2000) that a reduction in the observational uncertainties and the inclusion of seismic constraints in the modelling would allow a more robust inference on the mixing-length parameters of α Cen A and B. This is now the case, thanks to the detection of solar-like oscillations and to the precise determination of radii. These are compatible with effective temperatures spectroscopically determined and significantly reduce the error box in the HR diagram. As a general result of the calibrations presented in the previous sections we find that the mixing-length parameter of calibrated model A (α_A) is approximatively 5–10% smaller than α_B .

Numerical simulations of convection has recently permitted to carry out a calibration of mixing-length parameter through the HR diagram. A function $\alpha(T_{\text{eff}}, \log g)$ is determined in order to reproduce the step of the specific entropy provided by the atmosphere hydrodynamic models. Both calibrations, the one by Ludwig et al. (1999) (based on 2-D simulations) and the one by Trampedach (2004) (based on 3-D simulations) show slight variations of α with the position in the HR diagram, and suggest that the mixing parameter should be represented as a function of $\log T_{\text{eff}}$,

Figure 6.5: Frequency differences between a reference MLT model (B3) and FST models of α Cen B with the same mass and initial chemical composition as B3, but calibrated with slightly different radii. If the models have the same radius (open squares) we see that the $\nu_{\text{MLT}} - \nu_{\text{FST}}$ increases with the frequency as in solar models. If the radii of the models differ (as is the case for the calibrated models B3 and B3f, full squares) $\nu_{\text{MLT}} - \nu_{\text{FST}}$ is determined by difference in radius and is a nearly constant shift of about $5 \mu\text{Hz}$ in the observed range of frequencies (delimited by dashed lines). This is the reason why, as shown in Fig. 6.8, there is a constant shift of $\sim 5 \mu\text{Hz}$ between the frequencies of model B3 and B3f.

$\log g$, and chemical composition.

Actually, comparing our results with these theoretical predictions, we see that the difference between the value determined for α_B and α_A is in good agreement with the predictions by numerical simulations of convection. Moreover, our α values for the two components bracket that obtained by calibrating the Sun ($\alpha_\odot = 1.91$) with same physics (see for instance the model A3,B3). This is what one expects from their HR location and from the calibrations by Ludwig et al. (1999) and Trampedach (2004). We note, however, that in the fits obtained by using $\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$ and $\langle \delta\nu \rangle$ we find $\alpha_B > \alpha_A$, but also α_A larger than the solar one. The difference with respect to the solar value is even larger when the masses of the components are assumed to be fixed. The same effect is present in Eggenberger et al. (2004): they find $\alpha_B > \alpha_A$, but their values are far from their solar one.

In order to determine whether the addition of an extra free parameter leads to a significant improvement of the fit, we performed a calibration assuming a single mixing-length parameter for both components, and including the $r_{02}(n)$ ratios in the quality function (A3c,B3c). The value of α for this calibration is $\alpha = 1.95$ (quite close to the solar one), but the masses now are slightly larger for the component A, and slightly smaller for the component B. The same happens if we decide to fix $\alpha_A = \alpha_B = \alpha_\odot$. The masses are anyway within 2σ of the observed value, and the age is the same $\tau = 5.7 - 5.8$ Gyr.

A different result is obtained if the small and large differences are considered in the quality function (A2c,B2c), and the mixing-length parameter is assumed to be the same for both stars. In this case, the value reached ($\alpha = 1.78$) is not so close to the solar one, M_B must decrease to $0.919M_\odot$, and the age of the system decreases with respect to the value obtained allowing two different mixing-length parameters. This result recalls that obtained by Thévenin et al. (2002), who using a unique α had to decrease the M_B to $0.907M_\odot$.

Since adding a free parameter would naturally lead to a better fit (a lower χ^2 as defined in Eq.(6.1)), for a quantitative comparison between the quality of the fit obtained with a different number of model parameters, it is more meaningful to compare the so-called “reduced” χ_R^2 (Eq. 6.4). As can be seen in Table 6.3 the value of χ_R^2 is lower if two distinct mixing length parameters are used in the modelling (both comparing A3,B3 with A3c,B3c and A2,B2 with A2c,B2c): this suggests that, with the adopted observational constraints, the addition of another free mixing-length parameter is justified. In fact, comparing the fits obtained with one or two mixing-length parameters, the F-test gives a confidence of 85-90% that the inclusion of two different parameters for convection is significant. We should however recall that such a statistical test, and generally a χ^2 statistics, assumes that the observational errors are distributed about the mean following a Gaussian distribution. This is not necessarily true as systematic shifts in the observed quantities and inaccuracies in the models cannot be excluded. As could also be expected, the

Figure 6.6: As Fig. 6.4 but with different curves corresponding to different physics included in the stellar computation: convective overshooting (dashed lines); solar mixture from Asplund et al. (2004) instead of Grevesse & Noels (1993)(dash-dotted lines); no gravitational settling (solid lines); CEFF equation of state instead of OPAL01 (dotted lines).

uncertainties adopted with the observational constraints are crucial. For instance, we find that if the observational error in the mass of the component B is doubled, the addition of a second free parameter for convection is no longer justified.

6.5.3 Disentangling the physics

One of the principal motivations for pursuing the study of pulsations in other stars is to test the assumptions concerning the physics underlying the stellar structure theory. To practically investigate this idea, we compute four models of α Cen that use the same observational constraints and model parameters as the reference calibrations (A3,B3) and (A1r,B1r), but incorporate changes in the physical assumptions. These are : CEFF EoS (A1e,B1e; A3e,B3e), Asplund et al. (2004) chemical composition (A5,B5). To test the effects of gravitational settling we have calibrated the models (A1nd,B1nd) and (A3nd,B3nd) without microscopic diffusion.

The central question is whether the residual errors are observationally significant. If the residuals are all small compared to the observational errors, it is not

Figure 6.7: Difference between theoretical and observed frequencies for the sets of parameters whose separations have been plotted in Fig. 6.3 (upper panel); in Fig. 6.4 (middle panel); and Fig. 6.6 (lower panel). Left side corresponding to α Cen A, and right side to α Cen B. The labels correspond to the identification of the model used in Table 6.2.

Figure 6.8: Difference of frequencies between a reference calibration (A3,B3), and both, that with a different EoS (A3e,B3e) (solid lines), and without microscopic diffusion (A3nd,B3nd) (dashed lines). Upper panel corresponds to component A, and lower panel to component B. To avoid changing the figure scale, the curve of residuals (A3-A3nd) in the upper panel has been shifted down by $2.5 \mu\text{Hz}$

possible to distinguish parameter changes from changes in physical assumptions. In general, we find that stars obeying different physics succeed remarkably well in masquerading as stars that merely have different parameters (Brown et al., 1994).

6.5.3.1 Equation of state

Concerning the equation of state, the calibration assuming CEFF (A3e,B3e) leads to a result in agreement with the fit (A3,B3) computed adopting OPAL01, both in terms of χ_R^2 (either the total one or that corresponding at each observable quantity), and of the fitted parameters. This is expected for stars with an internal structure similar to the sun: as shown by Miglio (2004) the differences between the sound speed and the first adiabatic exponent (Γ_1), due solely to the use of a different EOS (CEFF and OPAL01), are smaller than 1% except in outer regions with radii larger than $0.95 R_*$, that is of the same order of those predicted in solar models (see e.g. Basu & Christensen-Dalsgaard, 1997). The differences appear to be larger in the lower-mass model B than in model A, and are mainly located in the hydrogen and helium ionization regions. In that study, the differences in Γ_1 came from the application of CEFF or OPAL01 to a given stellar structure ($\log \rho$ vs. $\log T$) and chemical composition. In the calibration procedure, such small differences in the internal structure of a model propagate in a variation of the observables of each model that could be easily compensated by a re-adjustment of the free parameters.

The models calibrated by using different equations of state are very similar. There is, nevertheless, a difference in the frequencies. In Fig. 6.8 (solid lines) we plot the difference between (A3,B3) and (A3e,B3e) frequencies. The upper panel corresponds to the A component, and the lower panel to the B one. This difference in frequencies shows a behavior depending on ν with an oscillatory signature. This is expected for instance, when the models have either different locations of the convective region boundaries, or a different behaviour of Γ_1 . The bottom of the convective zone in α Cen A is located at $x_{zc} = R_{cz}/R_* = 0.707$ for A3 calibration, and $x_{zc} = 0.711$ for A3e model. Therefore, the oscillatory signature is probably related to the changes in the second helium ionization zone. The amplitude of this oscillation is linked to the difference in depth of the Γ_1 bump, and the period contains information about the location of the difference in stellar structure. For star A, the amplitude of the oscillation between the order $n = 10$ and 15 is around $0.7 \mu\text{Hz}$, while for the B component that is almost $2 \mu\text{Hz}$.

6.5.3.2 Microscopic diffusion

The calibrations without diffusion (A1nd,B1nd) and (A3nd,B3nd) provide fits of similar quality with respect to the corresponding calibrations including gravitational settling, respectively (A1r,B1r) and (A3,B3). As reported in Table 6.2 the parameters resulting from the calibrations differ, as expected, in the initial chemi-

cal composition. The smaller mass fraction of He required in these calibrations implies also a slight increase in the age of the system: 6.3 ± 0.4 Gyr for (A3nd,B3nd) versus 5.8 ± 0.2 Gyr for (A3,B3) (and 7.1 ± 0.6 Gyr for (A1nd,B1nd) versus 6.8 ± 0.5 Gyr for (A1r,B1r)). The (A3nd,B3nd) calibration is consistent with the one obtained by Thoul et al. (2003). Since they use only α Cen A frequencies, their age estimation is not affected by the low $\delta\nu(B)$ value.

The mixing-length parameters are also re-adjusted to fit the stellar radius, and also in this case α_B is almost 8% larger than α_A , and both bracket the mixing length parameter obtained for a Sun calibrated without microscopic diffusion ($\alpha_\odot = 1.84$).

In Fig. 6.8 (dashed-line) we show how diffusion affects the frequencies. We plot the residuals defined as $\nu_{n0}(A3) - \nu_{n0}(A3nd)$ (upper panel) and $\nu_{n0}(B3) - \nu_{n0}(B3nd)$ (lower panel). For component A the residuals as function of the order n show an oscillatory behavior, reflecting the changes in envelope He abundance (Y_s). Actually the calibrated model including diffusion has a superficial He abundance $Y_s(A3) = 0.245$, while model A3nd, without gravitational settling has $Y_s = 0.270$. This difference implies as well a different opacity and, therefore, a different location of the boundary of the convective zone ($X_{cz}(A3nd) = 0.725$). To avoid changing the figure scale, the curve of residuals in the upper panel has been shifted down by $2.5 \mu\text{Hz}$; we see that the amplitude of the oscillatory signal is around $0.5 \mu\text{Hz}$ between $n = 10$ and $n = 20$.

For component B the curve of residuals shows a completely different behavior. Since α Cen B is less massive than its companion, the mass contained in its convective zone is much larger and, therefore, the effect of microscopic diffusion is much smaller. The value of Y_s for B3 is less than 4% smaller than that for B3nd, while for the component A, the difference in Y_s between both calibrations (A3 and A3nd) is around 10%.

6.5.3.3 Solar mixture

Asplund et al. (2004) have recently proposed a substantial revision of the abundance of C N and O in the solar photosphere. Since the value of the surface metallicity of α Cen is observationally determined relative to the solar heavy element abundance, the solar $(Z/X)_s = 0.0177$ resulting from the new solar calibration would lower $(Z/X)_s$ in α Cen by $\sim 30\%$. We thus calibrate our models assuming as observational constraint $(Z/X)_s = 0.029$ (instead of 0.039) and using in the computations OPAL opacity tables calculated with the solar mixture proposed by Asplund et al. (2004). The results of this calibration, models (A5,B5), present a different initial chemical composition, but no other significant deviation from the global parameters of models (A3,B3) is noticed. As it happens for the Sun, the α CenA model calibrated with Grevesse & Noels (1993) has a deeper convective region compared with the model A5. The uncertainty in the observational data,

Figure 6.9: HR diagram showing the evolutionary tracks of model A3 (thick solid line) and A4 (thick dashed line). A4 is computed including overshooting and presents a convective core. The error boxes for T_{eff} , $\log L/L_{\odot}$, and radii correspond to 1σ (thin solid lines) and 2σ (thin dashed-lines)

however, is much larger than in the Sun, preventing us to make any inference on the depth of the convective envelope.

6.5.3.4 Overshooting

An additional consequence of our simple way of describing convection in stellar models, is the need to parameterize convective overshooting. In general (see e.g. Schaller et al., 1992) convective core overshooting is necessary to fit isochrones of open clusters for masses larger than a given critical mass. The problem is to determine this critical mass and to describe the transition between no-overshooting mass domain and overshooting mass domain. On the one hand, the mass and effective temperature of α Cen A are quite close to solar values, and one could think that no overshooting should be introduced. Nevertheless the chemical composition of α Cen A is different from the solar one and the evolution of a convective core does not necessarily show the same behaviour. The mass of α Cen places

Figure 6.10: $r_{02}(n)$ ratios for A component. Points represent the observational values with their error bars assuming an error in frequencies equal to 2σ . Dashed-dotted line corresponds to the model (A1t) calibrated using large and small separation in the χ^2 functional, as well as the effective temperatures instead of the radii. The other two curves correspond to modes calibrated using $r_{02}(n)$ in χ^2 : model including overshooting and presenting a convective core (A4, dashed line); the same calibration without overshooting (A3, continuous line).

it in the boundary region between models with and without a convective core. We have made several calibrations varying the thickness of the overshooting layer $ov = \alpha_{OV} \times (\min(r_{cv}, H_p(r_{cv})))$ (where r_{cv} is the radius of the convective core) with α_{OV} from 0.0, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2. In fact, for values of $\alpha_{OV} \leq 0.15$ no convective core remains after the PMS, therefore the parameters resulting from the fitting are not changed. For sufficiently large values of α_{OV} , as described in Sec. 5.4.2.1, the convective core that develops in the pre-main sequence phase persists during the main sequence thanks to the continuous supply of ${}^3\text{He}$ that sustains the highly temperature-dependent nuclear reaction ${}^3\text{He} + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}^4\text{He} + {}^1\text{H} + {}^1\text{H}$, keeping the pp chain in an out-of-equilibrium regime.

In Tables 6.2 and 6.3 we report the set of parameters and observables corresponding to models (A4,B4) calibrated with $\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$. In Fig. 6.9 we show the evolutionary tracks of models A3 and A4. As should be expected, including overshooting reduces the age of the system. Fig. 6.6 shows the large and small separations. We find a possible direct indicator of a convective core in the behavior of the small separation of component A at high frequencies ($\nu > 2500 \mu\text{Hz}$). That is even more evident in the signature left in r_{02} (see Fig. 6.10). However, given

Figure 6.11: $r_{10}(n)$ ratios for A component. Points represent the observational values with their error bars assuming an error in frequencies equal to 2σ . Short-dashed line corresponds to the model calibrated using large and small separation in the χ^2 functional, as well as the effective temperatures instead of the radii. The other three curves correspond to modes calibrated using $r_{02}(n)$ in χ^2 : model including overshooting (solid line) and presenting a convective core; the same calibration without overshooting (dot-dashed line), and calibration without overshooting and without microscopic diffusion (long-dashed line).

the uncertainty ($1.3\mu\text{Hz}$) affecting the p-modes involved in the highest frequency $r_{02}(n)$ (or $\delta\nu(n)$), it is not possible, based only on $r_{02}(n)$ or $\delta\nu_{02}$, to rule out a convective core in α Cen A. The ratio $r_{10}(n) = (\nu_{n0} - 2\nu_{n1} + \nu_{n+1,0}) / (2\Delta\nu_0(n+1))$, however, is much more eloquent, as shown in Fig. 6.11, and allows to discriminate between model A3 and A4: current observational constraints seem not to be in favour of a convective core in α Cen A. As will be described in the following section this conclusion is also supported by recent observations of oscillations in α Cen A.

6.6 Comparison with the latest observational data

Since we addressed the modelling of α Cen AB, new observations of solar-like oscillations in both component of the system have been performed and the results recently published (Bedding et al., 2004; Kjeldsen et al., 2005; Fletcher et al., 2006; Bazot et al., 2007).

6.6.1 α Cen A

The outcome of a two-site observational run on α Cen A was reported in Bedding et al. (2004). In this work the authors were able to identify 42 oscillation frequencies including $\ell = 3$ modes. However, due to bad weather conditions, the overall duration of the observations (~ 5 days), as well as the gaps in the time-series, did not allow an accurate determination of the oscillation frequencies which present a large scatter about the asymptotic relation. The latter also prevents a precise determination of the large and small separations (see Fig. 6.12 and 6.13), though their averaged values are in good agreement with those published by Bouchy & Carrier (2002).

Thanks to the detection of $\ell = 3$ modes in the Bedding et al. (2004) data, we can now compare a few points of the observed and theoretical small separation $\delta\nu_{13}$. As shown in Fig. 6.14 this frequency separation could help discriminating between models with and without a convective core, however, a significant comparison between the theoretical and observed values is prevented by the severe scatter and large uncertainty of the frequencies determined by Bedding et al. (2004).

Such a large observed scatter was used by the authors to infer valuable information about the lifetime of the modes, which was estimated to be 1-2 days, i.e. significantly lower than in the Sun (3-4 days). In a successive revised analysis of the same data set presented in Kjeldsen et al. (2005), the estimate of the mode lifetime was revised upwards to $2.3^{+1.0}_{-0.6}$ d at $2100 \mu\text{Hz}$, closer to the lifetime of the modes observed in the Sun.

A further upwards revision of the mode lifetime in α Cen A was obtained by

Figure 6.12: Large frequency separation of model A3 (full line) compared to the values observed in α Cen A by Bouchy & Carrier (2002) (full triangles), Bedding et al. (2004) (crosses) and Bazot et al. (2007) (open squares). $1-\sigma$ error bars on $\Delta\nu$ for the data sets of Bouchy & Carrier (2002) and Bazot et al. (2007) are shown in the legend. In the case of Bedding et al. (2004) data, in addition to an error bar representing approximately half of the frequency resolution of their time-series, we show the fit (dotted line) that the authors suggest to use in the comparison with theoretical models instead of the actual frequencies. The authors estimate an uncertainty in the fit of about $0.4 \mu\text{Hz}$ between 1900 and $2800 \mu\text{Hz}$.

Fletcher et al. (2006). In this work a first evidence for rotational splitting was observed and the latter was considered as an additional source of the observed frequency scatter. By analyzing space-based photometric time series obtained with the WIRE satellite (Buzasi, 2003), the authors were able to infer a mode lifetime of about 3.9 ± 1.4 d in the frequency range 1700 - $2650 \mu\text{Hz}$. Such an upwards revision of the mode lifetime is good news for the observation of solar-like oscillations, since short lifetimes would degrade the precision with which oscillation frequencies can be measured.

Recently Bazot et al. (2007) observed α Cen A during a five-night observational run with the HARPS (Pepe et al., 2002) spectrograph at the 3.6 m ESO telescope in Chile. These observations allowed to identify 36 oscillation modes of degree $\ell = 0 - 3$ and to find evidence of rotational splitting based on the detection of a larger scatter (about the expected asymptotic relation) in frequencies of higher degree. The authors have also shown that the contribution of unresolved rotational splitting to the frequency scatter can affect both the estimation of the mode lifetime as well as the accuracy of the frequency determination of non-radial

Figure 6.13: As in Fig. 6.12 but showing the comparison of the small frequency separation $\delta\nu_{02}$.

Figure 6.14: As in Fig. 6.13 but for the small separation $\delta\nu_{13}$.

modes (as already pointed out in Bouchy & Carrier 2002). Bazot et al. (2007), in agreement with Fletcher et al. (2006), suggest that consequently the mode lifetimes for α Cen A should be revised to a higher value compared to the results in Bedding et al. (2004) and Kjeldsen et al. (2005), where the lifetime was inferred from the scatter itself but neglecting the effect of rotational splitting. Moreover the authors suggest that the scatter due to rotational splittings has probably led to a misidentification of three $\ell = 2$ modes in Bouchy & Carrier (2002).

As a consequence the correct identification of $\ell = 2$ modes at 2573.1, 2679.8 and 2786.2 μHz affects the estimated value of the small spacing $\delta\nu_{02}$ (see Fig. 6.13). The authors suggest that in the Bouchy & Carrier (2002) data set the two points of $\delta\nu_{02}$ at the highest frequencies (which were already considered as uncertain in Bouchy & Carrier 2002) should be removed due to an erroneous mode identification. If this on the one hand removes the discrepancy between the theoretical and the observed slope of $\delta\nu_{02}$ as a function of ν (see Sec. 6.5.1), on the other hand it implies a slightly larger observed value for the average small separation, that could lead to a decrease of the theoretical age estimate of the system.

We notice that this misidentification has a further interesting consequence: two of the modes that were erroneously identified as $\ell = 0$ (at 2573.1 and 2679.8 μHz) were combined with $\ell = 1$ modes to compute the separation r_{10} . If we exclude in Fig. 6.11 the two points at the highest frequencies, we see that the comparison with the theoretical values shows a *significantly better agreement for models that do not present a convective core*. A similar conclusion is also suggested by the comparison between theoretical and observed values of the small separation $\delta\nu_{13}$ (see Fig. 6.14), though the uncertainty on $\ell = 3$ frequencies used in the computation of $\delta\nu_{13}$ is probably underestimated since rotational splittings of $\ell = 3$ modes are not resolved in Bazot et al. (2007) data.

6.6.2 α Cen B

After the first detection of oscillations by Carrier & Bourban (2003), α Cen B was observed by Kjeldsen et al. (2005) during about 5 days in a two-site campaign from Chile (with the UVES spectrograph at the VLT) and Australia (with UCLES at the Anglo-Australian Telescope). This observational campaign led to the detection of 37 oscillation modes with degree $\ell = 0 - 3$ and therefore to the determination of the large separation and both the small separations $\delta\nu_{02}$ and $\delta\nu_{13}$. This multi-site campaign had the clear advantage of reducing the gaps in the time-series and thus the aliases in the frequency analysis: this allowed the authors to firmly state that the oscillation frequencies are ~ 1 c/d (i.e. ~ 11.57 μHz) higher than those identified by Carrier & Bourban (2003). This conclusion is particularly interesting since these higher frequencies reduce the discrepancy between observed and theoretical frequencies noticed in Sec. 6.5.1 for models that reproduce within $1-\sigma$ the radius

Figure 6.15: As in Fig. 6.12 but comparing models and observational data of α Cen B. The error bar representative of Kjeldsen et al. (2005) data is an average of the error bars given for each frequency in their Table 1. As in the case of Bedding et al. (2004) data for α Cen A, we also show (dotted line) the fit that the authors propose to use in the comparison with theoretical frequency separations.

of α Cen B.

In Kjeldsen et al. (2005) the total length of the observations, and therefore the frequency resolution of the time-series, was however quite low and this, coupled to the finite life-time of the modes and to the unresolved rotational splittings, is likely to be the main reason for the large scatter of the observed frequencies about the asymptotic relations. This scatter is also clearly visible on the observed points of the large and small separation, as presented in Fig. 6.15, 6.16 and 6.17, where the comparison with Carrier & Bourban (2003) observations and with the predictions of our models is presented. Even though the theoretical values of the large and small separation agree with the new observations, the large scatter in the observed frequencies prevents us, however, from putting any tighter constraints on the modelling. As already discussed in Sec. 6.5.1, the averaged value of the theoretical $\delta\nu_{02}$ is in better agreement with the average value ($10.1 \mu\text{Hz}$) observed by Kjeldsen et al. (2005) than the one ($8.5 \mu\text{Hz}$) determined by Carrier & Bourban (2003), which was based on only 2 observed points. The latest observations also allow to determine a few points of the small separation $\delta\nu_{13}$ (computed with modes of degree $\ell = 1$ and 3) that, as shown in Fig. 6.17, is in good agreement with the values predicted by the models.

Figure 6.16: As in Fig. 6.13 but in the case of α Cen B.

Figure 6.17: As in Fig. 6.14 but in the case of α Cen B.

6.7 Summary

We propose a calibration of the binary system α Cen by means of Levenberg-Marquardt minimization algorithm applying it simultaneously to classical (photometric, spectroscopic and astrometric) and seismic observables. The main features of this sort of algorithm make it an ideal tool for the aim of this work: to analyze the effectiveness of oscillation frequencies in constraining stellar model parameters and stellar evolution physics, by using the p-modes identified by Bouchy & Carrier (2002) (α Cen A) and by Carrier & Bourban (2003) (α Cen B). Actually thanks to its low computational cost, this algorithm allows to search for the best model in the full 7-dimensional parameter space describing the binary system, varying both the set of stellar observables, and the physics included in stellar modelling.

As starting point we assumed the same observables as Eggenberger et al. (2004). In spite of the different EoS (MHD), diffusion treatment (Richard et al., 1996, for five elements separately), cross section of nuclear reactions (NACRE) and atmospheric boundary conditions, we derive a set of stellar parameters (A1r,B1r) in complete agreement with theirs.

By comparison between calibrations with different observables we make clear that care has to be taken when using $\Delta\nu_0$ to constrain fundamental stellar parameters. Given the strong dependence of $\Delta\nu_0$ on surface layers, and our poor understanding of the physics describing outer stellar regions, seeking a perfect agreement between observed and predicted $\Delta\nu_0$ may bias our results toward, for instance, inaccurate radii. This is clear when comparing the models A1t and A1r; in the former a perfect agreement with the observed $\Delta\nu$ is reached but the radii (and therefore the frequencies, see Fig. 6.7) deviate significantly from their observational values.

An additional source of systematic error in the calibrations concerns the value of the small frequency separation of component B. Since the observational data are still rather poor one of the two measured values, $\delta\nu_B(n = 23)$ leads to a higher age than suggested by $\delta\nu_A$.

The value of $\delta\nu_B$ predicted in our calibration (A3,B3) (where $\delta\nu_B$ is not included in the χ^2) is in agreement with $\delta\nu_B(n = 21)$ and with the recent value of the average $\delta\nu_B$ published by Kjeldsen & Bedding (2004) and Kjeldsen et al. (2005). This also suggests that sufficiently precise seismic data of one star are sufficient to determine fundamental parameters of the system. In fact additional calibrations, not shown in Table 6.2, where no seismic constraints of component B are included, lead to fitted parameters compatible with e.g. (A3,B3) even though a large discrepancy between predicted and observed frequencies of α Cen B is observed.

We therefore propose to use r_{02} as a reliable seismic constraint to determine

fundamental parameters of a star. The large frequency separation could, nonetheless, provide a first estimate of the mean density and, as shown e.g. in Gough (1990), useful information on localized features in stellar interior once more accurate determinations of solar-like oscillations will be available.

Section 6.5.2 was devoted to the study of the effects on the calibration of our uncertainties concerning stellar convection. If the calibrations, e.g. (A3,B3), are performed considering a free parameter describing convection in each component (α_A , α_B) we find, as Eggenberger et al. (2004), α_B 5-11% higher than α_A . Differently from Eggenberger et al. (2004) we find that $\alpha_A < \alpha_\odot < \alpha_B$. We notice also that our inferred values of α follow the same trend predicted by MLT parameter calibration based on 2D (Ludwig et al., 1999) and 3D (Trampedach, 2004) hydrodynamic atmosphere models.

In order to draw firm conclusions on the significance of considering α_A and α_B as free parameters we repeated our calibrations (A3,B3) and (A2,B2) assuming a single parameter for both components ((A3c,B3c) and (A2c,B2c)). The fit necessarily improves when an additional free parameter is introduced in the calibration, nevertheless we find, with the observational constraints we adopted, the difference between α_A and α_B significant. We note also that the value of α obtained in (A3c,B3c) and (A2c,B2c) calibrations is quite close to the corresponding α_\odot .

We also find that, contrary to what was obtained by Morel et al. (2000), the use of a different theory of convection (MLT or FST) in our models does not change the set of parameters derived from the fitting. The only effect of convection model is a slight improvement in the fit of high frequencies when using FST (in particular for A component).

The available seismic data are not in favour of a convective core in α Cen A, moreover, the overshooting parameter needed for a convective core to persist after the PMS ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$) appears to be too large for a model of the mass and chemical composition of α Cen A (see e.g. Demarque et al., 2004). This conclusion is also strengthened by the comparison with the latest seismic observational data presented in Sec. 6.6.

We find that stars obeying different physics provide similar fits to those obtained with stars that merely have different parameters. As a consequence, we are not able from present data to discriminate neither between different EoS, neither between diffusion or not diffusion models. Fig. 6.8 shows, however, that expected precision from space missions or continuous ground based observations would allow to apply inversion techniques to frequency data.

Adding seismic observables has significantly improved the determination of the system fundamental parameters, but more and more precise observations are needed to be able to extract information about the internal structure of the stars.

As recent observations of oscillations in α Cen A have shown (Fletcher et al.,

2006; Bazot et al., 2007), in order to get an accurate measurement of the frequencies (and also an estimate of the lifetime of the oscillation modes), the effects of rotational splittings of non-radial modes need to be considered. This conclusion further shows the need for data sets of longer duration that may also be obtained combining the already available data. It is encouraging that, in the case of α Cen A, the combination of Bouchy & Carrier (2002) and Bedding et al. (2004) observational data is currently being done (Bedding, private communication).

7

12 Böötis: a test bed for extra-mixing
processes in stars

The results presented in this chapter are published in the following paper:

Miglio, A., Montalbán, J., Maceroni, C. : *12 Boötis: a test bed for extra-mixing processes in stars*, (2007), MNRAS, 377, 373

7.1 Introduction

In standard stellar modelling convection is described by means of a local theory such as the Mixing Length Theory (Böhm-Vitense, 1958), and the extension of the convective regions is determined by the classical Schwarzschild criterion ($\nabla_{\text{rad}} = \nabla_{\text{ad}}$). This is one of the well known shortcomings of stellar structure and evolution theory. For intermediate and high mass stars, where a convective core is developed, the mass of this central mixed region plays a fundamental role in determining the lifetime and the luminosity of the main sequence phase, and affects other relevant aspects such as the s-process nucleosynthesis on the asymptotic giant branch (Ventura & D’Antona, 2005), the chemical evolution of the interstellar medium, and the size and composition of white dwarfs (see, e.g. Chiosi, 1998).

We mean here by overshooting or extra-mixed region the mixing of material beyond the formal boundary of convection region set by the Schwarzschild criterion. There is quite a large number of observational evidences indicating that this phenomenon of overshooting exists. For instance, comparisons between observations (binaries and open clusters, Andersen et al., 1990; Ribas et al., 2000) and theoretical models indicate that stars have larger convective cores than predicted by theory. Moreover, numerical simulations and laboratory experiments suggest the overshoot of convective elements in the adjacent stable regions. A great effort has been done during the last 30 years to describe turbulent convection in stellar interiors, however, given the difficulty in estimating the rate of dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy, it is still not possible to predict the thickness of the extra-mixed region from first principles. Therefore, the thickness of the overshooted region (Λ_{OV}) is usually parameterized in terms of the local pressure scale height H_p ($\Lambda_{\text{OV}} = \alpha_{\text{OV}} H_p$). The value of this parameter has been estimated by fitting theoretical isochrones to the observed color-magnitude diagrams of open clusters, and by modelling double-lined eclipsing binaries with well determined masses and radii (see e.g. Ribas et al., 2000). These calibrations also indicate that the exact value of the overshoot parameter might depend on the stellar mass: values of the order of 0-0.1 are required for masses between 1.1 and 1.5 M_{\odot} , and values from 0.2 to 0.5 are needed in the 1.6 to 9 M_{\odot} interval (see Ribas et al., 2000). Moreover, as noticed in VandenBerg & Stetson (2004) and VandenBerg et al. (2006), the overshooting parameter has probably a steep dependence on mass in the range $1.3 \lesssim M/M_{\odot} \lesssim 1.55$.

Not only the exact amount of overshooting and its dependence on the stellar

mass, but also the physical process responsible for extra-mixing, are still matter of a lively debate (Maeder & Zahn, 1998; Young & Arnett, 2005; Popielski & Dziembowski, 2005).

In this context the binary system 12 Boötis represents a valuable observational test of stellar modelling. Recent interferometric measurements allowed Boden et al. (2005) to determine the masses of the components of this double-lined spectroscopic binary with a precision of about 0.3%. The masses of the components are very similar (mass ratio $q \sim 0.97$), but their luminosities are quite different. A preliminary determination of stellar parameters by comparison with theoretical isochrones (see Boden et al., 2005), suggested that secondary component is still in the central-hydrogen burning phase, while the primary is more evolved and burning hydrogen in a shell. Given the lifetime of the sub-giant phase derived from theoretical models, this solution is quite unlikely (Andersen et al., 1990). Furthermore, as shown by Boden et al. (2005), the evolutionary state of the fitted models is highly dependent on the model details (and in particular on the amount of core overshooting) and needs further investigation. The masses of 12 Boo components (1.416 and 1.372 M_{\odot}) are in fact in the transition region, where the thickness of the “overshooting” layer seems to depend on the stellar mass, metallicity and evolutionary stage (VandenBerg et al., 2006).

Even if the masses are very precisely known, and both the components have the same age and initial chemical composition, there is a large number of possible parameter sets able to fit the “classical” observables. In this work we present different scenarios based on different theoretical prescriptions for extra-mixing processes, which provide stellar parameters compatibles with observational constraints, but with different evolutionary state and internal structure. The classical observables do not allow to distinguish between different solutions, and hence additional and independent observational constraints are needed. In this work we propose solar-like oscillations as additional observational constraints. Fortunately, the components of 12 Boo are located in a region where solar-like oscillations are expected to be excited (see e.g. Kjeldsen & Bedding 1995, Houdek et al. 1999 and Samadi et al. 2005).

Solar-like oscillations have been observed in several single stars (e.g. η Boötis, and μ Arae, Kjeldsen & Bedding, 1995; Bouchy et al., 2005, respectively) and binary systems (Procyon, Martić et al., 2004) as well as in both components of the visual binary system α Centauri (Bouchy & Carrier, 2002; Carrier & Bourban, 2003; Bedding et al., 2004; Kjeldsen et al., 2005). In the latter, as shown in the previous chapter, the combination of asteroseismic and precise “classical” constraints (masses, radii, luminosities ...) significantly improves the determination of the system fundamental parameters. While the study of α Centauri provides a test of our knowledge of stellar structure in conditions that are slightly different from the Sun, a detailed investigation of 12 Boötis will be a relevant step in

understanding the structure of the central regions for this particular area in the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram (HRD) where the “transition” from radiative to convective core models takes place.

In Sect. 7.2 we summarize the observational knowledge about 12 Boo, and we describe the constraints that will be used in the calibration process. The latter is described in Sec. 7.3. Among the free parameters, the most important is the extension of the overshooting region. We will also analyse possible solutions by taking into account different physical processes able to change the thickness and features of the extra mixed region. In Sec. 7.4 we study how the differences in the stellar structure for the models fitted in different scenarios are reflected on the oscillation frequencies, and we suggest which kind of observational data could give us enough information to constraint the evolutionary state of 12 Boo, and, possibly, also the properties of the transport processes (if any) in the stellar central region. Finally, in Sec. 7.5 we present our conclusions.

7.2 12 Boötis: observational constraints

With the rapid development of optical interferometry in the last years, closer and closer binary systems have become resolvable. Thanks to interferometric orbits an increasing sample of double-lined spectroscopic binaries (SB2), including non-eclipsing systems, can be used for accurate stellar parameter determination. Interferometry essentially yields the orbital inclination that, combined with accurate radial velocity measurements, can provide mass determination at a level better than 1%, i.e. suitable for strict stellar modelling tests (see e.g. Andersen, 1991).

A good example of an ideal target for this technique is 12 Boo, a bright ($V=4.83$) non-eclipsing SB2 with an orbital period of about ten days ($P = 9.6$) and a (composite) spectral type F8 IV -F9 IVw (Barry, 1970) (where “w” stays for weak metallic lines). Boden et al. (2005) obtained long baseline interferometry of 12 Boo with the Palomar Testbed Interferometer (PTI) and the Navy Prototype Optical Interferometer (NPOI). They secured, as well, new high resolution (echelle) spectra, as the previous spectroscopic observations (Abt & Levy, 1976; De Medeiros & Udry, 1999), were the major limit to the precision of derived parameters. The interferometric visibility data and the radial velocity curves were simultaneously solved to derive the orbital parameters. The components could not be resolved (the apparent orbital semiaxis is only 3.45 mas), so that the individual radii had to be derived by indirect means, namely by the Infrared Flux Method by Blackwell and collaborators (Blackwell et al., 1990; Blackwell & Lynas-Gray, 1994). The information about the total and the individual bolometric fluxes (needed for radius determination) was derived by a fit of multi-wavelength archival data and from the in-band intensity ratio of the interferometric measurements. Furthermore, the analysis of the observed spectra provided an estimation

Parameter	value	reference ^a
P (d)	$9.6045529 \pm 4.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1
e	0.19268 ± 0.00042	1
i	$107^{\circ}99 \pm 0.077$	2
a (mas)	3.451 ± 0.018	2
ΔK_{CIT} (mag)	0.589 ± 0.005	2
ΔH_{CIT} (mag)	0.560 ± 0.020	2
ΔV (mag)	0.560 ± 0.020	2
K_{A} (Km s^{-1})	67.286 ± 0.037	1
K_{B} (Km s^{-1})	69.30 ± 0.050	1

^aReferences: 1) Tomkin & Fekel (2006), 2) Boden et al. (2005)

Table 7.1: Orbital parameters and magnitude differences for 12 Boo

of the component effective temperatures and of the luminosity ratio. A further improvement in the determination of the spectroscopic orbit by Tomkin & Fekel (2006), combined with the same interferometric data, confirms the values of the masses derived by Boden et al. (2005) and reduces the associated error bars. The relevant values and their uncertainties are reported, for the reader's sake, in Table 7.1.

Other relevant information on the system are its near-solar chemical composition, with a mean value of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.01 \pm 0.08$, derived from Strömgren photometry and detailed spectroscopic analysis (Duncan, 1981; Balachandran, 1990; Lèbre et al., 1999; Nordström et al., 2004) and the component rotational velocities of 14.0 and 12.0 km s^{-1} (Boden et al., 2005). The latter are slightly faster than the expected corotation rate of, respectively, 12.4 and 9.3 km s^{-1} .

The resulting global picture of 12 Boo is that of a binary with very similar components (masses, effective temperatures, rotation) except an unexpected magnitude difference: both spectroscopic and interferometric measurements indicate a difference of ~ 0.48 - 0.58 mag, depending on the band. That is quite hard to explain in a system with coeval and non-interacting components (both of them are well inside the critical Roche lobe).

The high precision of the radial velocity measurements (the typical error is 0.5 km s^{-1} in Boden et al., 2005; Tomkin & Fekel, 2006) and the short orbital period rules out the possibility of making the masses unequal by "hiding" a small fraction of a component mass in a third unseen object. Unless rather improbable configuration of the third object orbit are assumed (i.e. orbit almost normal to the line of sight), even an object of a few hundredth solar masses orbiting one component would easily be detected from the reflex motion of the more massive companion. Besides, such a planetary orbit can be excluded on the ground of stability consideration, see e.g Holman & Wiegert (1999) and references therein.

	A	B
M/M_{\odot}	1.4160 ± 0.0049	1.3740 ± 0.0045
$T_{\text{eff}} \text{ (K)}$	6130 ± 100	6230 ± 150
L/L_{\odot}	7.76 ± 0.35	4.69 ± 0.74
Z/X	0.0245 ± 0.01	0.0245 ± 0.01

Table 7.2: Observational constraints as adopted in the modelling.

The observational constraints we assume in our modelling are taken from Table 5 of Boden et al. (2005) that, for the sake of convenience, we repeat here in Table 7.2. As the above mentioned spectroscopic and photometric studies of 12 Boötis indicate a metallicity within 0.1 dex of the solar value, given this uncertainty and a further uncertainty on the value of the solar metallicity, we adopted the solar Z/X of Grevesse & Noels (1993) considering a conservative error bar, as reported in Table 7.2.

7.3 Modelling 12 Boötis

In the following we will use the term “calibration” to denote the process of determining the stellar model parameters, such as initial composition and age (the same for A and B components), satisfying - within $1-\sigma$ - the observational constraints: M_A , M_B , Z/X , L_A , L_B , $T_{\text{eff},A}$ and $T_{\text{eff},B}$.

As both system components are massive enough to develop a convective core during the main-sequence and no a-priori assumption on their evolutionary state can be made, the dependence of T_{eff} and luminosity on the stellar parameters (e.g. age and overshooting) is highly non-linear. As Boden et al. (2005) already pointed out, the result of system fitting strongly depends on the model details, and, in particular, on the amount of convective overshooting in the core.

The aim of this work is to study the possible solutions (not just to find a single solution) and to verify the ability of discriminating among different scenarios. We apply, therefore, the minimization technique adopted and described in Chap. 6 with the purpose of determining the chemical composition and age for each value of the overshooting parameter (assumed to vary from 0.0 to 0.50 in steps of 0.01). The parameters left free are: the initial chemical composition (described by the hydrogen and heavy-elements mass fraction, X and Z respectively), the age and the component masses. These are adjusted in order to fulfill the observational constraints in Table 7.2. A standard χ^2 is used as goodness-of-fit estimate, so that each observable is taken into account with its uncertainty. We did not allow α_{MLT} to be adjusted and fixed its value to $\alpha_{\text{MLT}} = 1.84$, i.e. the value provided by the Solar calibration. This choice is justified by the fact that both stars are quite close in the HRD and that different values of α_{MLT} are not expected. Besides, a

variation of α_{MLT} implies a change of T_{eff} that can be easily balanced by a change of the chemical composition.

The search for a solution fulfilling the observational constraints on the HR diagram is usually biased by an additional criterion, though this is not included in the χ^2 : a preference towards long lasting evolutionary phases, as the probability of finding a star in a given evolutionary phase depends on how “rapid” that phase is. Evidently, it is less likely to observe a star in its second gravitational contraction than on the main sequence. This is however a statistical argument, that can be verified on large samples of stars (e.g. in clusters), but cannot be applied to a single case. In addition to that, the duration of each evolutionary stage depends on whether overshooting is considered in the models or not. As pointed out e.g. by Maeder (1975) and Noels et al. (2004), the duration of the thick-shell-hydrogen burning phase depends on the amount of overshooting as the latter increases the mass of the isothermal helium core built during the core hydrogen-burning phase. As an example, a $1.4 M_{\odot}$ star without overshooting spends in that phase $\sim 20\%$ of the main-sequence lifetime (see Iben, 1991, for instance). An overshooting parameter $\alpha_{\text{OV}} \simeq 0.1$ implies a decrease of the duration of this evolutionary phase down to 4% of the main-sequence lifetime, i.e. lasting as long as the overall contraction phase. In our modelling we do not make, therefore, any a-priori assumption on the particular evolutionary phase of the solution.

Stellar Models

The stellar model sequences are computed with the code CLES (Code Liégeois d’Evolution Stellaire). The opacity tables are those of OPAL96 (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) complemented at $T < 10000$ K with Alexander & Ferguson (1994) opacities. The metal mixture used in the opacity tables, is the solar one according to Grevesse & Noels (1993). The nuclear energy generation routines are based on the cross sections by Caughlan & Fowler (1988) and updated with the recent measurement of the $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate (Formicola et al., 2004). The weak screening factors come from Salpeter (1954), and the equation of state used in the computations is OPAL01 (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002). Convection transport is treated with the classical mixing length theory by Böhm-Vitense (1958) in the formulation by Cox & Giuli (1968); and atmospheric boundary conditions given by Kurucz (1998) are applied at $T = T_{\text{eff}}$.

Chemical mixing in the formal convective region and in the overshooting layer is treated as instantaneous. Besides, the thickness of the overshooting layer, Λ_{OV} , is expressed in terms of a parameter α_{OV} , so that $\Lambda_{\text{OV}} = \alpha_{\text{OV}} \times \min(r_{\text{cv}}, H_{\text{p}}(r_{\text{cc}}))$, where r_{cc} is the radius of the convective core. The temperature stratification in this overshooting layer could be radiative or adiabatic (e.g. Zahn 1991). At any rate the effect of this thin layer on the evolutionary track is very small, in our models a

	α_{OV}	Y_0	Z_0	Age (Gyr)
a	0.06	0.268	0.0195	3.08
b	0.15	0.267	0.0198	3.31
c	0.23	0.267	0.0200	3.58
d	0.37, 0.15	0.281	0.0186	3.24

Table 7.3: Parameters of the models.

radiative stratification has been assumed.

We have computed as well models that, in contrast with the assumed instantaneous chemical mixing, include a diffusive treatment of mixing in the formal convective region and in the extra-mixed layer. These computations were done with the ATON3.0 code (D’Antona et al., 2005) for the same physics: MLT, OPAL1996 and Alexander & Ferguson opacities, as well as OPAL equation of state.

We have also studied (see Sect. 7.3.2) the effect of other chemical mixing processes, such as diffusion and gravitational settling of helium and heavy elements. Microscopic diffusion has been implemented in CLES code following the formulation by Thoul et al. (1994).

Finally, the effect of an additional turbulent mixing, such as the one expected to be induced by rotation, is addressed in Sec. 7.3.3.

7.3.1 Overshooting

We performed several calibrations for different values of the overshooting parameter and we found solutions only for models computed with $\alpha_{OV} \geq 0.06$ (see. Table 7.3). By changing α_{OV} the evolutionary state of the system changes. In detail: for the lowest values of overshooting the situation is that represented in Fig. 7.1.a: the primary component is close to the maximum luminosity in the shell–hydrogen burning phase, whereas the secondary, with a $X_c=0.03$, is at the end of its central hydrogen-burning phase. As α_{OV} increases, the evolutionary state of component A approaches the TAMS. With $\alpha_{OV} \simeq 0.15$ (Fig. 7.1.b) the primary is burning hydrogen in a thick shell while component B is well on the main sequence. A further increase of the overshooting parameter $\alpha_{OV} \geq 0.2$ places the primary in the rapid overall contraction phase (Fig. 7.1.c). Still larger values of α_{OV} make L_B increase out of $1-\sigma$ and therefore worsen the fit.

The observed luminosity ratio, $L_A/L_B \sim 1.65$ is the main obstacle for a solution with both components on the Main-Sequence. In fact, given that both components have the same age and initial chemical composition, if the same kind of mixing processes are considered in the center, the luminosity ratio in the main-sequence is determined by the mass ratio ($q \sim 0.97$), and does not significantly depend on the choice of the other common model parameters (X, Z, α_{OV}).

Regardless of the set (X, Z, α_{OV}) chosen, all the models computed with $\alpha_{OV,A} =$

$\alpha_{OV,B}$ provided $(L_A/L_B)_{MS} \simeq 1.15$. A higher value of the luminosity ratio can be reached if $\alpha_{OV,A} > \alpha_{OV,B}$. Therefore, the only way we found to place both components in their MS phase is to assume a different efficiency of mixing processes in each component. In Fig. 7.1.d we show a calibration solution obtained by assuming $\alpha_{OV,A} \simeq 0.37$ and $\alpha_{OV,B} \simeq 0.15$. In this case both 12 Boo A and B are well in the MS.

The values of stellar parameters collected in Table 7.3 are those used in the figures and comparisons in this work. It has to be noticed, however, that the uncertainty on Z/X reflects on an uncertainty of 0.02 in the initial helium mass fraction (Y_0) and of 0.2 Gyr in the age of the models. Besides, the calibrations with $\alpha_{OV,A} = \alpha_{OV,B}$ and similar initial chemical composition provide an age difference of the order of 15%, and the calibration with $\alpha_{OV,A} > \alpha_{OV,B}$ implies an age in the range bracketed by the $\alpha_{OV,A} = \alpha_{OV,B}$ models. Unfortunately, the uncertainty in Z/X is too large to constrain the models.

All the different scenarios presented here cannot be clearly discriminated by means of the available observational constraints, nevertheless, the internal structure of these models are significantly different, and these differences shall show up in their asteroseismic properties (see. Sec. 7.4).

Diffusive overshooting

The classical treatment of overshooting is an extension of the instantaneously mixed convective core by a distance Λ_{OV} . In the diffusive approach of convection, chemical mixing is described by the diffusion equation with diffusion coefficient $D = 1/3 v_{conv} \Lambda$, where v_{conv} is the average turbulent velocity and Λ the convective scale length. In a MLT treatment $v_{conv} \propto (\nabla - \nabla_{ad})$ and $\Lambda \propto H_p$, which imply $v_{conv} = 0$ at the formal boundary of the convective region ($\nabla = \nabla_{ad}$). In order to define a continuous diffusion coefficient, also in the overshooting region, ATON code extrapolates the $\log v_{conv}$ vs. $\log P$ relation, to get the turbulent velocity at the boundary, starting from a point inside the convective region where the pressure is 5% larger than at the boundary. Furthermore, following Xiong (1985), turbulent velocity is assumed to exponentially vanish outside the convective region, and the thickness of the mixed region is determined by the parameter β (see Ventura et al., 1998, for more details) which describes the exponential vanishing of turbulent velocity. As shown by Ventura et al. (1998), a β value ten times smaller than the α_{OV} in classical instantaneous mixing produces the same effect on the HR diagram.

With this formulation of overshooting we find the same set of solutions as with instantaneous mixing, this time for a parameter β in the range 0.004-0.035. This is of course reassuring as a completely independent stellar evolution code, and a different description of overshooting have been used. The chemical composition profiles at the border of the convective core are, however, smoother with the

Figure 7.1: HR diagram showing solutions found with different values of the overshooting parameter: *a*) $\alpha_{OV} = 0.06$, *b*) $\alpha_{OV} = 0.15$, *c*) $\alpha_{OV} = 0.23$, and *d*) $\alpha_{OV,A} = 0.37$ and $\alpha_{OV,B} = 0.15$. Model parameters are described in Table 7.3. Error boxes corresponding to 1- and 2- σ error bars in L and T_{eff} are represented by continuous and dotted lines.

diffusive overshooting than with the classical treatment.

7.3.2 Effects of diffusion

Richard et al. (2001), Michaud et al. (2004) and Richard (2005) showed that microscopic diffusion can affect the size and evolution of a convective core. In those papers, thermal diffusion, gravitational settling and radiative accelerations were included in the models to derive the evolution of chemical distribution. CLES code does not take radiative accelerations into account. Nevertheless, there is no observational evidence in 12 Boo of surface chemical peculiarities that could be produced by gravitational-settling and radiative-acceleration, and the latter is not expected to play a mayor role in the central region (see e.g. Richard et al., 2001).

We do not expect a large effect of radiative acceleration in the 12 Boo mass domain, since the thickness of their convective envelopes is quite large. Even if at the beginning of the MS component A has a shallow convective envelope, and therefore the role of radiative accelerations could be non-negligible, as the star evolves its convective region becomes deeper. As a consequence, the effect of radiative acceleration is reduced, and the chemical composition of the convective region re-homogenized. We decided, therefore, to consider and compare models accounting for diffusion of H and He, and of H, He and Z.

Michaud et al. (2004) showed that microscopic diffusion can induce an increase of the convective core for a narrow range of masses, from 1.1 to 1.5 M_{\odot} , and that the effect decreases rapidly with increasing stellar mass. We also note that in this mass domain, the convective core mass increases during the MS evolution instead of decreasing, as it occurs for larger masses. As a consequence, a sharp gradient of chemical composition appears at the convective core border, making the diffusion process much more efficient in that region.

As shown in Fig. 7.2, for a 1.4 M_{\odot} star, the increase of the core mass fraction when diffusion of H, He and Z is considered is of only $\simeq 5\%$, and the age of the turnoff is only slightly increased (Fig. 7.3). This is in agreement with the findings of Michaud et al. (2004) and Richard (2005) who consistently included radiative accelerations in their computations while considering Z -diffusion. An obvious consequence is that, in presence of diffusion, the amount of overshooting needed to find 12 Boo A and B in a given evolutionary state is reduced with respect to the values obtained in the previous section. In fact, the minimum amount of overshooting required is slightly smaller, i.e. $\alpha_{OV} \simeq 0.04$ instead of 0.06. The evolutionary state of the calibrated system changes, with increasing α_{OV} , in a way similar to that described Sec. 7.3.1.

On the other hand, the increase of the opacity in the envelope due to the settling of He and Z provides evolutionary tracks cooler than those without diffusion (this effect is even more important if only H and He diffusion is considered, see Fig.

Figure 7.2: Fractional mass of the convective core as a function of the age in no diffusion models: without overshooting (solid line) and with $\alpha_{ov} = 0.1$ (long-dashed line); and in no overshooting models including microscopic diffusion of He and H (dashed-dotted line) and of He,H and Z (dashed line).

7.3). At the end of the main sequence the surface Z/X is $\sim 10\%$ (diffusion of H and He) or $\sim 25\%$ (diffusion of H, He and Z) smaller than the initial value, nevertheless, given the uncertainties in the observed Z/X , this implies only a slight change in the Z and X initial values in the calibrated models.

In addition to a slight enlargement of the convective core, diffusion leads to a smoother chemical composition profile at the edge of the convective core (see Fig. 7.10). Whether this property affects the oscillation modes of the components will be addressed in see Sec. 7.4.

7.3.3 Other sources of extra-mixing in the core

The shear instability induced by stellar rotation is considered as one of the first causes of chemical mixing in the radiative interior of the stars. Different approaches have been proposed to treat the effects of rotation on transport of angular momentum and chemicals (see Maeder & Meynet, 2000; Mathis et al., 2004, for

Figure 7.3: Evolutionary tracks of the models described in Fig. 7.2 in a $\log T_{\text{eff}}$ -Age diagram.

a review). Since our stellar evolution code does not include a consistent treatment of rotational effects, we simply include the chemical turbulent mixing by adding a turbulent diffusion coefficient (D_T) in the diffusion equation. In our parametric approach D_T is assumed to be constant inside the star and independent of age. These simple prescriptions are inspired by the results obtained by Mathis et al. (2004) from a consistent study of rotational effects in a $1.5 M_\odot$ star (see their Fig. 2).

We have then calibrated our models with different values of D_T . We find, similarly to the case of including overshooting (see Sec. 7.3.1), that we are able to fit the system at different evolutionary stages depending on the value of D_T ; the values needed to fit the system are in the range $30 - 170 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. We note that these values are of the same order of the total diffusion coefficient resulting from the calculations for a $1.5 M_\odot$ model as presented in Mathis et al. (2004). As already seen for overshooting, in order to fit the system with 12 Boo A and B in their main-sequence, a different efficiency of mixing must be assumed in each component: $D_{T,A} = 330 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $D_{T,B} = 120 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The simplified parametric treatment of rotationally induced mixing used in this work has the aim of showing that if an extra-mixing process, different from overshooting, is acting near the core it will produce a different chemical composition profile in the central regions of the star. Whether these different profiles are reflected or not on the solar-like oscillations features will be analysed in Sec.7.4.2.

7.4 Asteroseismic properties

Stellar models predict the presence of a convective envelope for the range of masses of 12 Boo A and B and, therefore, solar-like oscillations are expected to be excited in both components of the system. By means of the scaling relations of Kjeldsen & Bedding (1995), Kjeldsen & Bedding (2001) and the theoretical predictions of Houdek et al. (1999), and using the precisely determined values of the mass and the luminosity, we estimate that the modes with the largest amplitudes should be around $\nu_{\text{max}} = 700 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$ and $\nu_{\text{max}} = 1200 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$ in 12 Boo A and B, respectively. The peak amplitude in the power-spectrum is expected to be 3-4.5 times larger than the solar-one for the A component, and 2.5-3.5 times larger than the solar one for the B component.

The components of 12 Boötis are massive enough to develop a convective core during main sequence. The combined action of nuclear burning and convective mixing is responsible for the development of a steep chemical composition gradient at the boundary of the convective core. As a star leaves the main-sequence, the increasing central condensation, together with the steep chemical composition gradient in the central regions, leads to a large increase of the buoyancy frequency (N) and, therefore, of the frequencies of gravity modes. The latter interact with

pressure modes and affect the properties of non-radial solar-like oscillations by the so-called *avoided crossing* phenomenon (see e.g. Osaki, 1975; Aizenman et al., 1977). The frequency of the modes undergoing an *avoided crossing* (also called mixed-modes) are therefore sensitive probes of the core structure of the star.

As a first example let us consider the evolution of the frequencies of the model of component A corresponding the scenario *b* of Table 7.3 (hereafter *Ab*). In Fig. 7.4 we plot the evolution of frequencies for $\ell = 0$ (dotted lines) and $\ell = 1$ (solid lines) modes, and show how *g*-modes, whose frequency strongly increases after the overall contraction (~ 3.27 Gyr), interact with pressure modes of same degree. This interaction results in non-radial modes with a mixed *p*- and *g*-character and frequencies that significantly deviate from a regular spacing between consecutive overtones.

Since the thickness of the mode evanescent region (where $N < \omega < S_\ell$, with S_ℓ being the so-called Lamb frequency) increases with the degree ℓ (see propagation diagram in Fig. 7.5), the interaction between *p* and *g* modes decreases. As a consequence, in modes of degree $\ell > 1$, the behaviour of gravity and pressure mode is generally better separated (see e.g. Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1995b; Morel et al., 2001): *g*-modes tend to remain concentrated in the core and would hardly be detectable due to their significantly larger inertia. This is in fact the case for the our models *Aa* and *Ab* where only $\ell = 1$ modes present a mixed character. Nevertheless, for the less evolved models (*Ac* for instance) also $\ell = 2$ mixed modes appear in the solar-like frequency domain. In the following discussion we will address mainly the properties of mixed modes.

Given the MS status of 12 Boo B, we will first discuss the seismic properties of component A, and only in Sec. 7.4.1.1 consider the additional information that the observation of solar-like oscillations of component B would add to the modelling.

7.4.1 Probing the evolutionary status

As already investigated in the case of η Boötis (see e.g. Di Mauro et al., 2004), the frequencies of modes undergoing an *avoided-crossing* are direct probes of the evolutionary status of intermediate mass stars.

In Fig. 7.6 we compare the large frequency separation¹ $\Delta\nu$ for radial and $\ell = 1$ modes corresponding to the models of component A presented in Fig. 7.1. Though radial modes do not give information on the evolutionary status, $\ell = 1$ modes allow a clear discrimination among the scenarios. Modes of mixed *p* and *g* character are not present in the model on the main sequence (Fig. 7.6.d) and $\Delta\nu$ is almost constant, indicating therefore a regular spacing between modes of consecutive radial order (both radial and $\ell = 1$). On the other hand, as more evolved models (*Aa*, *Ab* and *Ac*) are considered, the *avoided crossings* effects become more ev-

¹Computed as the difference between modes of same degree and consecutive frequencies.

Figure 7.4: Evolution in time of the frequencies of model *Ab*. Dotted and solid lines represent radial and $\ell = 1$ modes with radial order n from 11 to 23. The frequencies of model *Ab* are highlighted by a thick vertical line. Vertical dashed lines represent $\pm 1\sigma$ interval in the observed T_{eff} .

Figure 7.5: Propagation diagram for model *Ab* (see Table 7.3, Fig. 7.1). The solid line represents the Brunt-Väisälä frequency N , the short- and long-dashed line the Lamb frequency S_ℓ for, respectively $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$. The domain of solar-like oscillations falls within the horizontal dotted lines.

Figure 7.6: Large frequency separation as a function of the frequency for the models described in Fig. 7.1. Solid and dashed lines connect, respectively, $\Delta\nu$ for radial and $\ell = 1$ modes.

ident. Therefore, for the model in the second overall contraction (A_c , Fig. 7.6.c) the interaction between p and g modes changes by up to 10 μHz the modes with frequencies lower than 600 μHz (corresponding mode order, n , lower than 12). That can also be seen in Fig. 7.4 for models at 3.265 Gyr and the lowest n modes. For more evolved models (A_a and A_b) the avoided crossing phenomenon clearly breaks the regular frequency spacing in the domain of expected solar-like oscillation (Figs. 7.6.a and 7.6.b).

The radical variation of the properties of $\ell = 1$ modes derives from a considerable change of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency near the center of the star (see Fig. 7.7) as hydrogen is exhausted throughout the convective core and the star undergoes an

Figure 7.7: Propagation diagram in the core of the models for which large frequency separation has been plotted in Fig. 7.6. Solid line represents the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, and the dashed line the Lamb frequency for $\ell = 1$.

overall contraction. As models of component A at different evolutionary stages are obtained for different amounts of core overshooting, the detection of mixed modes and their frequencies would allow to constraint the value of the overshooting parameter or the extension of the mixed central region. While model *Aa* (computed with $\alpha_{OV} = 0.06$) presents *avoided crossings* at $\nu = 780 \mu\text{Hz}$ ($n = 15$) and $\nu = 1100 \mu\text{Hz}$ ($n = 24$) model *Ab* ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.15$) does it at $\nu = 700 \mu\text{Hz}$ ($n = 13$) and $\nu = 950 \mu\text{Hz}$ ($n = 20$). These differences between the frequencies of the modes presenting mixed p-g character ($\sim 100 \mu\text{Hz}$), as well as the differences of the frequency spacing between two consecutive avoided crossings ($\sim 20 \mu\text{Hz}$), are large enough to be detected with the current observational techniques. Furthermore, 12 Boo A has a rotational velocity 14 km s^{-1} (Boden et al., 2005) that, assuming an inclination of the rotational axis equal to the orbital one (108°), implies a rotational splitting between ($\ell = 1, m = -1$) and ($\ell = 1, m = 1$) modes of only $2.5 \mu\text{Hz}$.

Distinguishing between scenarios *Ac* ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.23$) and *Ad* ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.37$ for 12 Boo A and $\alpha_{OV} = 0.15$ for 12 Boo B) on the base of $\ell = 1$ mixed modes might be less straightforward since the effect of avoided crossing occurs at lowest frequencies, where the amplitudes of the modes are predicted to be small. Therefore, no detection of avoided crossing could imply, either that 12 Boo A is well in MS, and has therefore a large central mixed region, or that it is close to the TAMS. Luckily, for models in the second overall contraction (SOC), the changes in stellar structure are such that $\ell = 2$ mixed modes appear in the predicted solar-like spectrum, while for MS models (*Ad*) they would have very low frequencies.

7.4.1.1 Seismology of component B

Though in all calibrations we considered component B as a main-sequence object and, therefore, avoided crossings are not expected, the detection of solar-like oscillations in the secondary would, nonetheless, add constraints to the modelling of the binary system. A first additional constraint comes from the average value of the large frequency separation ($\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$) that, for main-sequence stars, is well known to represent an estimate of the mean density and, hence, of the stellar radius, if the mass is known. The available estimate of component radii in 12 Boo (Boden et al., 2005) is based on the Infrared Flux method and yields: $R_A = 2.474 \pm 0.096 R_\odot$ and $R_B = 1.86 \pm 0.15 R_\odot$. However, a more precise and independent determination of the stellar radii could be obtained, thanks to the small uncertainty on the masses (0.3%), from the knowledge of $\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$. In particular for component B, the measurement of $\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$, would result in a significantly smaller uncertainty on its location in the HR diagram and, therefore, in tighter constraints on the modelling. In Fig. 7.8 we show the uncertainty on the radii deriving from $\langle \Delta\nu \rangle$ values supposed to be known with an accuracy of 1 and 2 μHz .

Information on the central structure of component B could be provided by

Figure 7.8: Position in the HR diagram of 12 Boo A and B with 1 and 2- σ error boxes in $\log L$ and $\log T_{\text{eff}}$. Also shown are lines of constant radius deduced from the (known) masses of the components and the large frequency separation. The large separation is assumed to be known with an uncertainty of 1 (continuous lines) and 2 μHz (dotted lines).

the small frequency separations $\delta\nu_{02}$. In Fig. 7.9 we show $\delta\nu_{02}$ as a function of the frequency, as expected for the models of 12 Boo B corresponding to the four scenarios of Fig. 7.1. We notice that the dependence of $\delta\nu_{02}$ on ν is mainly determined by the location of the discontinuity in sound speed derivative at the border of convective core, while the age of the model changes the mean value of $\delta\nu_{02}$. The spread of $\delta\nu_{02}$ for the four considered scenarios increases with the frequency and is of the order of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$ at $1500 \mu\text{Hz}$ and of $1.5 \mu\text{Hz}$ at ν_{max} . The age difference between scenarios *b* and *d* (note that both have $\alpha_{OV} = 0.15$) implies a shift of only $0.5 \mu\text{Hz}$ in $\delta\nu_{02}$.

Can $\delta\nu_{02}$ of component B help discriminating between scenarios *c* and *d* in absence of avoided crossing detection? Fig. 7.9 shows that the difference of $\delta\nu_{02}$ at ν_{max} is only $0.2 \mu\text{Hz}$ and reaches $0.5 \mu\text{Hz}$ at $1500 \mu\text{Hz}$. Furthermore, the frequency of $\ell = 2$ modes will be affected by rotational splitting (expected to be $\sim 1 - 1.5 \mu\text{Hz}$), so that an accurate and reliable measurement of the small separation (expected to be around $3 \mu\text{Hz}$) will be a rather difficult task. Other frequency combinations, such as the small separation d_{01} are known to be very sensitive to the core structure of main sequence stars (see e.g. Roxburgh & Vorontsov 2003b and references therein), but the larger number of frequencies needed to compute these small differences, increases even more their observational uncertainty.

7.4.2 Probing the chemical composition gradient in the core

Is there any other information that the knowledge of the frequency of an avoided crossing can give us? The appearance of avoided crossings is due to the evolution of frequencies of gravity modes and their interaction with acoustic modes of similar frequency. The frequency spectrum of gravity modes, on its turn, is mainly determined by the behaviour of N in the central regions of a star ($\nu \propto \int N/r dr$). Furthermore, the mean molecular weight gradient (∇_{μ}) is determined by the evolutionary state, but it can be also modified by different mixing processes taking place in the radiative interior. If the N profile changes because of a different ∇_{μ} , then we could expect a signature in the *avoided crossings* frequencies.

In each of the evolutionary states *a* – *d* we considered, the different mixing processes we analyse (classical and diffusive overshooting, microscopic and turbulent diffusion) provide models with a central structure showing a different ∇_{μ} and therefore different N profiles. In Fig. 7.10 we plot the hydrogen mass fraction and N profiles in the central region of 12 Boo A models in the evolutionary states *b* and *c* resulting from the calibrations with classical overshooting, with (short-dashed lines) and without microscopic diffusion (solid lines), and calibration with turbulent diffusion (long-dashed lines). Though the evolutionary state is the same, the difference of chemical composition gradient (Fig. 7.10 upper panels) is clearly reflected on the Brunt-Väisälä frequency profile (Fig. 7.10 lower

Figure 7.9: The small frequency separation $\delta\nu_{02}$ as a function of frequency in models of component B corresponding to the scenarios $a - d$ described in Fig. 7.1.

Figure 7.10: Hydrogen profile (*upper panel*) and Brunt-Väisälä frequency (*lower panel*) in models computed with overshooting (continuous line), with turbulent mixing (long-dashed line) and with diffusion of H and He (short-dashed lines)

panels), and therefore on the frequency of g-modes and on the properties of the avoided crossings (see Fig. 7.11). Consequently, the determination of mixed-mode frequencies with a precision better than $\sim 2 \mu\text{Hz}$ for frequencies around $650 \mu\text{Hz}$, would allow to determine the properties of the chemical composition profile and, hence, of the physical mechanism responsible for the extra-mixing outside the core. The effect of different $\nabla\mu$ is even larger at lower frequencies: at $500 \mu\text{Hz}$, where the expected mode amplitude is slightly larger than the half of the amplitude at ν_{max} , the difference between overshooting and D_{T} models reaches $5 \mu\text{Hz}$.

We notice that such a valuable inference on the properties of the chemical composition gradient is made possible, in the example presented here above, by a trade-off between two effects. On one hand, the difference in $\nabla\mu$, which is due to a different mixing process, decreases as we consider more evolved models. On the other hand, the number of g modes entering the domain of solar-like oscillations, and therefore the number of avoided crossings, increases as the model evolves. This is the reason why, even though the differences between chemical composition profiles provided by classical overshooting and by D_{T} models increase as we consider less evolved models (see Fig. 7.10, lower panel), the lack of $\ell = 1$ avoided crossing predicted in the domain of solar-like oscillations for the scenarios *c* and *d*, makes difficult to infer information on the detailed properties of the μ gradient.

As mentioned above, models in the second gravitational contraction present $\ell = 2$ avoided crossings in the solar-like spectrum domain. These $\ell = 2$ modes are however less sensitive than $\ell = 1$ modes to the N profile, and the difference between overshooting and microscopic diffusion profiles is not large enough to be reflected in $\ell = 2$ frequency modes. Models in the scenario *c* including turbulent diffusion show, however, very different N in the central region, in particular, the model reaches the same location in the HR diagram with a smaller convective core, and this is reflected on a difference in the frequency of modes undergoing an avoided crossing, of the order of $100 \mu\text{Hz}$ with respect to those in the overshooting models.

Concerning the main-sequence calibrated models (both for A and B components) we note that while in overshooting models $\delta\nu_{02}$ as a function of ν has a slope increasing with the value of the overshooting parameter, for turbulent diffusion models, $\delta\nu_{02}$ shows only a weak ν -dependence. That can be explained in terms of a different effect on the size of the convective core. While, in fact, in overshooting models the increase of α_{OV} implies a larger core, in turbulent diffusion ones the increase of D_{T} parameter decreases $\nabla\mu$ at the border of the convective core, but leaves the core radius almost unaffected. Besides, the convective core for 12 Boo stellar masses is too small, and the difference between $\delta\nu_{02}$ slope for overshooting and D_{T} models not large enough to be detected in the expected solar-like frequencies.

Figure 7.11: $\ell = 0$ and $\ell = 1$ large frequency separation in models of which chemical gradient and Brunt-Väisälä are plotted in Fig. 7.10. Model *Ab* with overshooting $\alpha_{OV} = 0.15$ (continuous line), and model with turbulent mixing (long-dashed line). The different chemical composition gradient (see Fig. 7.10) affects the frequencies of $\ell = 1$ modes undergoing avoided crossings (lower curves) but not the frequencies of radial modes (upper curves).

The effect of other diffusion processes such as the diffusive overshooting or the microscopic diffusion on the μ -profile and on the frequencies of the avoided crossings are similar to those described for the turbulent mixing. The effect of microscopic diffusion is, however, not limited to the core: it also modifies the structure of the envelope by a decrease of the helium abundance in the outer convective zone and by the appearance of a chemical composition gradient below the convective envelope. The combination of these effects leaves, as noticed e.g. in Théado et al. (2005), a clear signature in the frequencies of acoustic modes. In order to fully exploit this seismic signature a high frequency resolution, that only long and uninterrupted observations can provide, is however needed.

7.5 Summary

We have presented a detailed modelling of the binary system 12 Boötis by fitting the available observational constraints: effective temperatures, luminosities, chemical composition, and high precision masses of both components. As result of different 12 Boo calibrations we found a set of possible theoretical scenarios where the secondary is on the main sequence, whereas the primary has already left it. Its precise evolutionary state, however, may vary from the SOC (models *Ac*) to a thick-shell-H-burning phase (models *Aa*) by varying the overshooting parameter α_{OV} from 0.23 to 0.06. These values slightly decrease (by 0.02) if microscopic diffusion is included in stellar modelling. Other central mixing processes, such as diffusive overshooting (described by the β parameter), and a turbulent mixing with a parametric turbulent diffusion coefficient (D_T) lead to the similar results. For each transport processes we found a possible range of values of the parameters α_{OV} , β and D_T that place 12 Boo B in the MS and 12 Boo A between the second gravitational contraction and the sub-giant phase. The only way to place both components in the MS (models *Ad*) is to assume a different efficiency of the mixing process in both components, for instance : $\alpha_{OV,A} = 0.37$, $\alpha_{OV,B} = 0.15$, or $D_{T,A} = 330 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $D_{T,B} = 100 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. With the available observational constraints we are not able, however, to discriminate among the different scenarios and models proposed: it is clear that additional and independent observational constraints are needed.

In Sec. 7.4 we have shown that the detection of the theoretically predicted solar-like oscillations in 12 Boötis would provide a powerful test to discriminate between different scenarios. Indeed, the detection of avoided crossings in the primary oscillation spectrum will allow a robust inference on the evolutionary state of the star and, therefore, on the amount of overshooting (or extra-mixing) from the core. The presence or absence of $\ell = 1$ mixed modes will allow to discriminate between sub-giant and MS models, and the absence of both $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ mixed modes will allow to place 12 Boo A in the MS, before the SOC. This possi-

bility is especially exciting since it would imply that, even for stars with masses so close, the central mixing has a significantly different efficiency, opening the door to important questions concerning transport processes.

As shown in Sec. 7.4.2, for a model in a given evolutionary state, a different chemical composition profile in the core can be due to a different physical process responsible for the extra-mixing. This affects the behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency and hence the frequency of modes of mixed p- and g- character. Consequently, information on the mixing process taking place in the stellar center could be inferred from the mixed mode frequencies. The precision required to reach this goal is, however, evolutionary state dependent. While for a thin-shell-H-burning phase, a precision of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$ should be enough to distinguish between the sharp chemical profile provided by overshooting and the smoother one from a diffusive process, in a slightly more evolved phase (thick-shell-H-burning phase) the effect would be already erased. On the other hand, as stellar age decreases, the number of mixed modes also decrease. As consequence, for models in the second gravitational contraction, information on the mixing process can be derived from $\ell = 2$ mixed modes only if the generated chemical profiles are quite different. For MS models, where no avoided crossings are predicted, the effect of the central mixing on the small separation $\delta\nu_{02}$ is not large enough to distinguish between different transport processes.

Finally, the detection of solar-like oscillations also in the B component, will mainly reduce the uncertainties on the HR location of 12 Boo B, and hence will significantly improve the observational constraints of the system.

In conclusion, we have shown that thanks to the precise knowledge of the masses of 12 Boötis, and the additional constraints due to the binarity, the search and detection of solar-like oscillations in 12 Boo, hopefully by a spectroscopic multi-site campaign of observations, would mean an important step in the understanding of stellar evolution in the mass domain where the convective core appears.

8

Conclusions and future prospects

The work presented in this thesis deals with different strategies adopted in asteroseismology. We here present a brief summary and outline future prospects for each topic addressed in the chapters describing our results (Chap. 4-7).

Inferences from excitation: β Cephei and SPB stars

Recent studies have shown that current models fail to reproduce the instability of the observed modes in some of the best studied β Cep stars (Ausseloos et al., 2004; Pamyatnykh et al., 2004; Handler et al., 2006; Kołaczkowski et al., 2006) as well as the pulsation of B-type stars in low-metallicity environments (see e.g. Kołaczkowski et al., 2006).

Since the theoretical predictions of excitation of pulsations in B stars are largely determined by the behaviour of the opacity in the driving region of the modes, in Chap. 4 we addressed the following questions: which are the current uncertainties on opacity calculations and on the metal mixture adopted in standard stellar models? Do they affect the theoretical predictions of excited pulsation modes in β Cep and SPB stars?

In the driving region of the modes ($\log T \simeq 5.3$) we noticed that differences in opacity up to $\sim 50\%$ can be induced by the choice between OPAL (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) and OP (Badnell et al., 2005) opacity tables, and between two different metal mixtures (Grevesse & Noels 1993 and Asplund et al. 2005).

We find a significant effect on the excitation of pulsation modes. Compared to results obtained with OPAL and Grevesse & Noels (1993), if we consider OP opacities and Asplund et al. (2005) metal mixture, we find that:

- the blue border of the SPB instability strip is displaced towards higher effective temperatures, leading to a larger number of models being hybrid SPB- β Cephei pulsators;
- higher overtone p-modes are excited in β Cephei models and unstable modes are found in a larger number of models with lower metallicities, in particular β Cephei pulsations are also found in models with $Z=0.01$.

These findings help solving the discrepancies between theoretical predictions and observations of β Cep in low-metallicity environments, and the detection of a large domain of excited modes detected in some β Cep and hybrid SPB- β Cep pulsators.

A thorough comparison between observations and models computed with OP-AGS05 opacities is currently ongoing and is of course part of our future projects. First encouraging results have recently been obtained in the modelling of the β Cep star θ Ophiuchi (Briquet et al., 2007b), where OP opacities with AGS05 metal mixture successfully explain the excitation of the observed pulsation modes, whereas the commonly adopted OPAL-GN93 fail. A similar case is that of the β Cep HD

180642 (a COROT primary target) where a preliminary modelling shows that the excitation of the dominant observed mode (identified as a radial mode) can be recovered when using OP–AGS05 opacities (see Aerts et al. 2007). The modelling of other β Cephei stars, such as ν Eri and 12 Lac is still needed to determine if the discrepancies between “standard” models and observations can be explained adopting the new OP opacities and AGS05 metal mixture.

Inferences on stellar cores through gravity modes

In Chap. 5 we analyzed in detail the properties of gravity modes in main-sequence stars. In analogy with the works on white dwarfs by Brassard et al. (1992) and Montgomery et al. (2003), we showed that

- in the case of main sequence stars analytical approximations can be used to directly relate the deviations from a uniform period spacing to the detailed properties of the μ -gradient region that develops near the energy generating core.

We find that a simple approximation of g-modes periods, based on the variational principle of stellar oscillations, is sufficient to explain the appearance of sinusoidal components in the period spacing. The periodicity and amplitude of such component are related, respectively, to the location and sharpness of the μ gradient.

We investigated the properties of high-order gravity modes for stellar models in a mass domain between 1 and 10 M_{\odot} , and the effects of the stellar mass, evolutionary state, and extra-mixing processes (overshooting, diffusion, turbulent mixing) on the properties of the period spacing. In particular, we find that

- for models typical of SPB stars, a chemical mixing that could likely be induced by the slow rotation observed in these stars, is able to significantly change the g-mode spectra of the equilibrium model.

These results are relevant for the asteroseismology of both γ Dor and SPB stars. Depending on the mixing processes acting near the centre, deviations from the constant period spacing predicted by first-order asymptotic approximation can be significant and should not be ignored when developing tools for the seismic modelling of these pulsators.

As we also discussed in Chap. 5 even though a frequency resolution sufficient to resolve closely spaced periods will be provided by the forthcoming space-based observations with CoRoT, an asteroseismic inference on the internal structure of these stars will only be possible for stars with very slow rotation rates, and with reliably identified pulsation modes. *Once these conditions are fulfilled, we will be able to access the wealth of information on internal mixing which, as shown in*

this work, is carried by the periods of high-order gravity modes in main-sequence objects.

In the second part of Chap. 5 we have extended our analysis of the effects of extra-mixing processes to low-order gravity modes and mixed modes. We find that

- turbulent mixing leaves a signature in the oscillation spectrum which differs from that of overshooting, and which can be related to the detailed properties of the sharp variation in N due to the different mixing processes considered.

In β Cephei stars, we find that the turbulent mixing induced by the typical rotation rates observed in these stars affects the frequency difference between non-radial modes of consecutive frequency.

These findings could have important effects on the seismic modelling of the best studied β Cep pulsators (e.g. ν Eri). We consider the modelling of β Cep pulsators including the effects of turbulent mixing near the core, one of the highest-priority projects in our future plans.

Inferences from solar-like oscillations in visual binaries

In Chap. 6 and 7 we discussed how the combination of classical constraints and of solar-like oscillations makes the visual binary systems α Cen and 12 Böötis valuable laboratories to test stellar models.

α Centauri AB

From the observational standpoint, α Cen is a very well constrained system, thanks to the availability of interferometric, seismic constraints, and to a precise determination of the luminosities, masses (bracketing the mass of the Sun, $M_A = 1.105$ and $M_B = 0.934 M_\odot$) and chemical composition.

As described in Chap. 6, when confronted with the problem of modelling the α Centauri binary system including all available constraints, the usefulness of an objective and efficient procedure to fit stellar models to observations becomes clear. We therefore implemented a Levenberg-Marquardt minimisation algorithm to derive the fundamental parameters of the system, and to analyse the dependence of these parameters on the chosen observables, on their uncertainties, and on the “physics” used in stellar modelling. By performing and comparing several calibrations, we were able to find

- a robust determination of the global parameters,
- an indication of the dependence of the mixing-length parameter on the HR diagram location,

and showed how the so-called “surface effects” on the oscillation frequencies can affect a widely used seismic indicator such as the large frequency separation.

The available seismic data are not in favour of a convective core in α Cen A, moreover, the overshooting parameter needed for a convective core to persist after the PMS ($\alpha_{OV} = 0.2$), appears to be too large for a model of the mass and chemical composition of α Cen A (see e.g. Demarque et al., 2004). This conclusion is also strengthened by the comparison with the latest seismic observational data. The effects on the oscillation frequencies of the uncertainty on other physical processes and inputs included in stellar models (such as diffusion, equation of state, etc), were also studied, though no direct inference could be made due to the quality of the current asteroseismic constraints.

In fact, such a study on a specific target makes clear that the asteroseismic inference on the internal structure of this type of stars is currently limited by the poor frequency resolution of single-site, ground-based observations.

The seismology of α Cen is therefore just at its infancy and its future is bright, provided that precise observational seismic data become available. A higher quality set of data will soon be provided by the ongoing combination of Bouchy & Carrier (2002) and Bedding et al. (2004) observational data (Bedding, private communication). Hopefully, in the near future, significantly more precise oscillation frequencies will be determined by long and uninterrupted observations with the project SIAMOIS (Mosser & The Siamois Team, 2007) and with SONG (Grun-dahl et al., 2006), a global network of small telescopes primarily dedicated to asteroseismology.

12 Böötis AB

While the study of α Centauri provides a test of our knowledge of stellar structure in physical conditions that are slightly different from the Sun, the observation of solar-like oscillations in the binary system 12 Boötis ($M_A = 1.416$ and $M_B = 1.374 M_\odot$) will be a relevant step in understanding the structure of intermediate-mass stars. In Chap. 7 we presented a detailed modelling of the binary system 12 Boötis by fitting the available observational constraints: effective temperatures, luminosities, chemical composition, and high precision masses of both components.

As result of different calibrations of 12 Boo we find:

- a set of possible theoretical scenarios where the secondary component is still on the main sequence, whereas the primary has already left it,
- that the precise evolutionary state of 12 Boo B, however, may vary from the second overall contraction, to a thick-shell-H-burning phase by changing the overshooting parameter α_{OV} in the range 0.23–0.06. These values slightly decrease (by 0.02) if microscopic diffusion is included in stellar modelling.

Other central mixing processes, such as diffusive overshooting, and a turbulent mixing lead to similar results. For each transport process we find a possible range of values of the parameters describing the efficiency of the extra mixing that places 12 Boo B in the MS and 12 Boo A between the second gravitational contraction and the sub-giant phase. Our analysis also shows that

- solutions with both components on the main sequence can be found only by assuming an efficiency of the extra-mixing process larger in the primary component than in the secondary.

In order to discriminate among these scenarios, additional and independent observational constraints are needed: these can be provided by solar-like oscillations, that are expected to be excited in both components of the system. *A precise knowledge of the frequencies of solar-like oscillations in the primary component coupled to the precise knowledge of the masses, would allow a robust inference on the evolutionary state of the system and, therefore, on the required amount of extra-mixing in the core.*

A further result of this detailed study is that, for a model in a given evolutionary state, the chemical composition profile near the core depends on the physical process responsible for the extra-mixing. This affects the behaviour of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency and hence the frequency of modes of mixed pressure- and gravity- character. *Information on the mixing process taking place in the stellar centre could be inferred from the frequencies of mixed modes.*

Thanks to the strong scientific motivations resulting from this study, a collaboration between several researchers and institutes (Liège, Leuven, Roma, Genève, Nice) has been set up to prepare a joint proposal for a spectroscopic campaign to observe solar-like oscillations in 12 Boötis. The realisation of the SONG project (Grundahl et al., 2006) would also give the opportunity for a long-term monitoring of this most promising target.

As a spur to future research in asteroseismology we would like to end this thesis with another quote from Sir Arthur Eddington (Eddington, 1920):

In ancient days two aviators procured to themselves wings. Dædalus flew safely through the middle air across the sea, and was duly honoured on his landing. Young Icarus soared upwards towards the Sun till the wax melted which bound his wings, and his flight ended in fiasco. In weighing their achievements perhaps there is something to be said for Icarus. The classic authorities tell us that he was only “doing a stunt”, but I prefer to think him as the man who certainly

brought to light a constructional defect in the flying-machines of his day. So, too, in Science.

Cautious Dædalus will apply his theories where he feels most confident they will safely go; but by his excess of caution their hidden weaknesses cannot be brought to light. Icarus will strain his theories to the breaking-point limit till the weak joints gape. For a spectacular stunt? Perhaps partly; he is often very human. But if he is not yet destined to reach the Sun and solve for all time the riddle of its constitution, yet he may hope to learn from his journey some hints to build a better machine.

Part III

Addenda

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C

Effects of revised input physics on stellar models

In this Appendix we include for reference the properties of calibrated solar models obtained considering different physical inputs (Sec. C.1). Moreover, in Sec. C.2 we present the effects of revised nuclear reaction rates and metal mixture on a larger grid of models than the one considered in Sec. 2.3.

C.1 Solar calibrations

The solar models are calibrated by adjusting the mixing-length parameter α , the initial mass fraction X_0 of hydrogen and the initial mass fraction Z_0 of heavy elements in order to reproduce, at the solar age ($4.57 \cdot 10^9$ yr, Bahcall et al. 1995): the observed luminosity ($3.842 \cdot 10^{33}$ erg s⁻¹, Bahcall et al. 2001), photospheric radius and present ratio (Z/X) of heavy elements to hydrogen in the photosphere. In the solar calibration we adopt a spatial and temporal discretization finer than the standard one: the number of mesh-points in a solar model is typically ~ 2500 and ~ 350 time steps are needed to reach the solar age (including the pre-main sequence phase).

As the value of the calibrated parameters depends on the choices of the physical input, we here present solar models computed with different opacity tables, equations of state, nuclear reaction rates, assumed photospheric abundances, treatment of convection, diffusion . . .

The description of the complete set of calibrations is given in Table C.1, with the following meaning of the acronyms:

- **Opacities:** *OPAL+AF05*: Opal Opacities (Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) complemented at low temperature with Ferguson et al. (2005) opacities. *OP+AF05*: the new Badnell et al. (2005) Opacity Project opacities;
- **Equation of state:** *OPAL01-G31*: Opal 2001 (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002) taking $\Gamma_3 - 1$ from the tables (see Sec. 2.3.2). *OPAL01-Cv*: Opal 2001 taking C_v from the tables. *OPAL05*: Opal 2005. *CEFF*: CEFF equation of state (Christensen-Dalsgaard & Däppen, 1992);
- **Nuclear Reaction rates:** *CF88*: Caughlan & Fowler (1988), *NACRE*: Angulo et al. (1999) rates, *FOR*: including the revised $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate from Formicola et al. (2004);
- **Metal Mixture and metallicity:** *GN93*: Grevesse & Noels (1993) metal mixture and $Z/X = 0.0245$, *AGS05*: Asplund et al. (2005) mixture and $Z/X = 0.0165$, *AGS05+NeCunha*: Asplund et al. (2005) with the increase Ne abundance as determined by Cunha et al. (2006) and a $Z/X = 0.0177$;
- **Atmosphere:** *ATMOSE*: radiative gray Eddington atmosphere with specified opacities, *ATMOSK*: Kurucz (1998) atmosphere joined at the photosphere;
- **Diffusion:** *STD*: diffusion of H, He and Z included in the computations using the routine by Thoul et al. (1994), *D He*: only diffusion of H and He is considered;
- **Convection:** Mixing-length (*MLT*) or Canuto & Mazzitelli (1991) (*FST*) implemented as described in Chap. 6;
- **Overshooting:** The overshooting parameter is specified with the standard notation α_{OV} . $\nabla = \nabla_{\text{rad}}$ in the overshooting region. When $\alpha_{OV} \neq 0$ overshooting both from the core (if any) and the convective envelope is included;
- **Radius:** We considered different values for the solar radius available in the literature. *ROLD*: the value Allen (1973), i.e. $6.9599 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm, *RJCD*: $6.95508 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm (Brown & Christensen-Dalsgaard, 1998) and *RSCHOU*: $6.95680 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm, from Schou et al. (1997).

Results

The parameters resulting from the calibrations and some global properties of the solar models are reported in Table C.2. In particular, we report for each model

Figure C.1: Difference in squared sound speed, in the sense (Sun)-(model S96), inferred from helioseismic inversion. Taken from Christensen-Dalsgaard (2002).

the normalized radius of the base of the convective envelope (r_{CZ}) and the surface helium abundance (Y_S). These values can be compared with those obtained by helioseismic investigations, i.e. $r_{CZ} = 0.713 \pm 0.001$ (as determined by Basu & Antia, 1997) and $Y_S = 0.245 \pm 0.005$ (see e.g. the review by Boothroyd & Sackmann, 2003).

The properties of the calibrated solar models are also described by the following sets of figures:

- Sound speed differences at fixed fractional radius between the models and the standard solar models S96 (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al., 1996), in the sense (model)-(model S96) (pages 287-290). The relative differences in squared sound speed between the Sun and model S96 determined through helioseismic inversion are shown for reference in Fig. C.1. The main physical inputs of models S96 are OPAL96 (Rogers et al., 1996) equation of state and OPAL opacities (Rogers & Iglesias, 1992). Nuclear reaction rates are those described in Bahcall et al. (1995) and diffusion of H, He and Z is included following Michaud & Proffitt (1993). The chemical composition assumed is the one given in Grevesse & Noels (1993).

As noticed in several works (see e.g. Turck-Chièze et al., 1998; Morel et al., 1999; Neuforge-Verheecke et al., 2001), the updates in the physical inputs released after model S96 was computed, generally increase the discrepancies between the models and the Sun.

- Differences between $\ell = 0, 1, 2, 3$ frequencies observed in the Sun and frequencies of calibrated solar models, in the sense (model)-(Sun) (pages 291-294). The observed frequencies are taken from Basu et al. (1997);
- Comparisons between observed and theoretical frequency separations $\Delta\nu_0$ and $r_{02} = \delta\nu_{02}/\Delta\nu_1$. (pages 295-298).

In the case of solar models computed with overshooting (Ov1 and Ov2) a small convective core persists on the main sequence. In model Ov1 the core does not last until the solar age, whereas in model Ov it does. This situation is similar to the case of α Cen A and, as discussed in Chap. 6, the changes in the structure due to the presence of a convective core affect both the frequency separation r_{02} at high frequencies and, even more, $\ell = 1$ modes and thus $\delta\nu_{13}$ and $r_{13} = \delta\nu_{13}/\Delta\nu_0$. The comparison between the observed and theoretical frequency separations presented in page 298 shows that, for the physical input of model Ov2, the appearance of a convective core worsens the agreement between theoretical and observed frequencies.

Mod	OPAC	EOS	NuclR	MIX	ATMO	DIFF	OVER	CONV	R
O1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
O2	OPAL+AF94	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF94	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
O3	OP+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
M1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	AGS05	ATMOSE-AS04-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
M2	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	AGS05+Cunha	ATMOSE-AS04-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
D0	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	No	0	MLT	ROLD
D1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	D He	0	MLT	ROLD
R1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	CF88	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
R2	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
A1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSK	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
E1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL05	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
E2	OPAL+AF05	CEFF	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
E3	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-Cv	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	ROLD
Ov1	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0.2	MLT	ROLD
Ov2	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0.3	MLT	ROLD
F	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	FST	ROLD
Ra0	OPAL+AF05	OPAL01-G31	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	MLT	RJCD
BEST	OP+AF05	OPAL05	NACRE+FOR	GN93	ATMOSE-GN93-AF05	STD	0	FST	RSCHOU

Table C.1: Description of the calibrations of solar models obtained with different choices of opacities (OPAC), equation of state (EOS), nuclear reaction rates (NuclR), metal mixture and metallicity (MIX), atmosphere (ATMO), diffusion (DIFF), overshooting (OVER), description of convection (CONV) and value of the photospheric solar radius (R). See the text for an explanation of the abbreviations appearing in the table.

Mod	X_0	Z_0	α	Y_S	r_{CZ}	$(Z/X)_S$	X_c	T_c (10^7 K)	ρ_c (g cm^{-3})
O1	0.70427	0.02008	1.8045	0.24500	0.71565	0.02450	0.344	1.570	151.7
O3	0.70565	0.02007	1.8183	0.24418	0.71330	0.02450	0.346	1.567	151.8
M1	0.72411	0.01401	1.6738	0.23027	0.73026	0.01650	0.366	1.548	149.4
M2	0.71956	0.01486	1.7162	0.23477	0.72475	0.01770	0.361	1.552	150.6
D0	0.71635	0.01755	1.6708	0.26617	0.72993	0.02450	0.372	1.543	147.5
D1	0.71442	0.18244	1.8236	0.23710	0.71397	0.02450	0.356	1.555	151.5
R1	0.70354	0.02000	1.8193	0.24630	0.71407	0.02450	0.340	1.566	150.0
R2	0.70403	0.02007	1.8065	0.24524	0.71543	0.02450	0.339	1.573	151.8
A1	0.70420	0.02009	1.8521	0.24497	0.71565	0.02450	0.344	1.571	151.8
E1	0.70443	0.02008	2.0075	0.24493	0.71537	0.02450	0.345	1.570	151.7
E2	0.70128	0.02006	2.0062	0.24714	0.71831	0.02450	0.342	1.572	152.5
E3	0.70424	0.02008	1.8474	0.24500	0.71558	0.02450	0.345	1.570	151.7
Ov1	0.70578	0.01975	1.7935	0.24499	0.71700	0.02450	0.391	1.571	142.0
Ov2	0.70272	0.01959	1.7681	0.24498	0.71980	0.02450	0.516	1.569	113.2
F	0.70418	0.02009	0.7060	0.24500	0.71559	0.02450	0.344	1.571	151.8
Ra0	0.70431	0.02007	1.8097	0.24500	0.71548	0.02450	0.344	1.570	151.8
BEST	0.70576	0.02007	0.7149	0.2441	0.71289	0.02450	0.346	1.568	151.9

Table C.2: Global parameters of solar models computed with different physical input as described in Table C.1: initial hydrogen and heavy elements mass fraction (X_0 and Z_0), convection parameter (α), surface helium abundance (Y_S), fractional radius at the base of the convective envelope (r_{CZ}), surface metallicity ($(Z/X)_S$), central hydrogen mass fraction, temperature and density (X_c , T_c and ρ_c)

Sound speed differences (reference: Model S96)

Frequency differences for $\ell = 0, 1, 2, 3$ modes (reference: Sun)

Frequency separations $\Delta\nu_0$, $r_{02} = \delta\nu_{02}/\Delta\nu$ (reference: Sun)

C.2 Nuclear reaction rates & metal mixture

Following the discussion given in Sec. 2.3, we here present the effects of considering revised nuclear reaction rates and metal mixture on a larger grid of models in the mass domain 1-10 M_{\odot} .

Grids of models

We computed grids of stellar models using four different compilations of nuclear reaction rates:

- A:** Caughlan & Fowler (1988) (CF88),
- B:** CF88 + the revised $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$ reaction rate from Formicola et al. (2004) (CF88+Luna),
- C:** NACRE (Angulo et al., 1999),
- D:** NACRE + the revised reaction rate from Formicola et al. (2004).

and we also considered

- E:** a grid of models computed using the metal mixture by Asplund et al. (2005) (AGS05) instead of the one presented in Grevesse & Noels (1993) (GN93), which is assumed in all the other grids above-mentioned.

For each of the five grids, we considered models with the following masses: $M=1, 1.1, 1.15, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5, 2, 4, 6, 10 M_{\odot}$; a chemical composition: $X=0.70$, $Z=0.01$ and $Z=0.02$, and an overshooting parameter $\alpha_{OV} = 0.0, 0.1$ and 0.2 . In the comparisons we take as a reference the grid computed with CF88 reaction rates and GN93 metal mixture.

Set of figures

The comparisons are presented by the following set of figures (where models of grid A are compared with those of grids B,C,D and E):

1. HR diagram showing evolutionary tracks of main-sequence models of $M=1, 1.1, 1.15, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5$ and $2 M_{\odot}$. In each panel a different value of α_{OV} or Z is considered,
2. Evolutionary track on the HR diagram for the $10 M_{\odot}$ model with different Z and α_{OV} ,

3. Fractional mass of the convective core as a function of central hydrogen abundance for models of masses between 1 and 2 M_{\odot} . In 1.15 M_{\odot} models computed with CF88 and $\alpha_{OV} = 0.1$, the central hydrogen abundance has a local maximum in the middle of the main sequence: this is due to the sudden increase of the convective core mass fraction (see Sec. 5.4.1.2 for a brief discussion on the uncertain treatment of convective cores that increase on the main sequence).
4. Fraction of nuclear energy generation rate provided by H-burning through the CNO cycle as a function of X_c .
and, in order to better show the effects on the *pre-main sequence*:
5. HR diagram with only pre-MS models of masses between 1 and 2 M_{\odot} ,
6. Fractional mass of the convective core as a function of the age for a restricted set of masses (1, 1.2, 1.5 and 2).
7. HR diagram with only 10 M_{\odot} pre-MS models.

CF88 vs. NACRE

CF88 vs. NACRE+Luna

CF88 GN93 vs. CF88 with AGS05 Metal Mixture

